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FORMATION OF A SYSTEM FOR ASSESSING THE INTELLECTUAL AND SOCIAL-REPUTATIONAL CAPITAL OF A COMPANY IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

Bulatetskaya Alena Yuryevna

*Doctor of Economic Sciences, Candidate of Sociological Sciences,
Professor*

Perm National Research Polytechnic University

Abstract. *This article analyzes the process of developing a system of indicators for assessing the intellectual and social-reputational capitals of a company within the context of economic digitalization. The composition of the intellectual and social-reputational capital components, as well as the set of indicators for their evaluation, are substantiated. Approaches to measuring the value of intellectual and social-reputational capital are generalized. Elements of a system of financial and non-financial indicators for evaluating components of a company's intellectual and social-reputational capital have been developed.*

Keywords: *digital economy, financial and non-financial indicators, components of intellectual and social-reputational capital, evaluation indicators.*

In the context of the digital economy, systems for assessing a company's intellectual and social-reputational capital require accounting for the specifics of digitalization. Traditional accounting methods, based on the quantitative measurement of goodwill as the difference between the business purchase price and the value of its net assets, do not fully capture the specifics of modern companies. Some aspects that need to be taken into account include: 1) changes in the set of indicators used for assessing intellectual capital under the influence of digitalization trends; 2) incorporation of new forms of capital – digital brands, network communities, digital traces of audience interaction, online partnerships, and ecosystem assets; 3) the application of an interdisciplinary approach to the assessment of reputational capital, integrating big data analytics tools, predictive analytics, scenario modeling, and network analysis; 4) consideration of specific risks and value factors associated with digital business models [1].

Currently, Russian companies disclose separate information about elements of intangible capital, in particular intellectual property assets, business models,

strategies, credit ratings, corporate governance, tax payments, and social and environmental aspects of operations. However, this information is unsystematic and does not allow for a comprehensive understanding of the company's existing intellectual and social-reputational capital, which creates a demand for appropriate disclosure standards and analytical procedures for its assessment. Algorithms for disclosure and analytical methodologies for intangible capital are necessary to identify the company's most valuable assets, evaluate its innovation processes, analyze its reputation from the perspective of stakeholders, and substantiate conclusions regarding the impact of intangible capital on the created value and market capitalization [2, p. 38].

Of the six types of capital identified by the International Integrated Reporting Framework [3, p. 6], intellectual and social-reputational capitals hold particular significance owing to their capacity to generate excess returns and sustain a firm's competitive advantages over a prolonged period [4].

Intellectual Capital can be defined as the knowledge controlled by the company, alongside the system for its generation, dissemination, and constructive use [5, p. 30].

Social-Reputational Capital constitutes institutions and relationships within communities and between them, as well as between stakeholder groups and other groups, along with the capacity to share information to enhance individual and collective well-being [6, c. 100–101].

Social-Reputational Capital comprises two components: the social – connections with stakeholders, and the reputational – stakeholders' trust in the company. The foundation of social-reputational capital is the trust of stakeholders, which arises from understanding their expectations and satisfying their needs, as well as intangible assets associated with the brand and reputation [7].

In order to develop a system of assessment indicators for intellectual and social-reputational capitals, it is first necessary to identify their components by using the International Integrated Reporting Framework (Fig. 1).

The structure of intellectual and social-reputational capitals presented in the diagram differs from several well-known concepts that distinguish the following components and subcomponents of intellectual capital: market assets, human capital, intellectual property, structural capital, partnership capital, customer (relational) capital, Organizational Capital, innovation capital, process capital, network capital, and others.

According to the International Integrated Reporting Framework, intellectual capital comprises two components: organizational capital, which is associated with business management and development processes, and intellectual property, which is directly involved in operational business processes [4].

When evaluating the role of organizational capital, it is necessary to define its functions; the last of the functions listed below is the most significant, as it creates the conditions for the generation of all types of intangible capital: 1) providing the business with all forms of capital (factors of production) and maintaining their

effective interaction; 2) managing the business, establishing a system of labor relations, and ensuring the company's operation; 3) enhancing the business; creating a system for managing new knowledge and supporting the continuous renewal of products and processes.

Fig. 1. Components of Intangible Controlled Capital (Author's Own Development)

Components of organizational capital include, in particular, the following: the mission, vision, and hierarchy of the company's strategies; the financial and organizational structure of the business; information systems and communication tools; management procedures; production process regulations; knowledge bases; databases; internal control systems and managerial accounting.

Thus, in the process of assessing organizational capital, in addition to the business model, the business structure, the hierarchy of its strategies, and the company's infrastructure, the results of innovative activities and innovative mechanisms must also be evaluated [8, pp. 53–63]. The significance of this evaluation module lies in the fact that the changes occurring within the company are the source of its added value.

The 'intellectual property' component includes the following elements: 1) information constituting a commercial secret (design, engineering, technological information, results of research and development, experimental design works, know-how); 2) objects of copyright and related rights (computer software, databases, chip topologies, works of science, art, music, painting, and other art forms); 3) objects of industrial property (patents for industrial designs, plant varieties, inventions); 4) licenses (usage rights based on license agreements: property, land, water, and other natural resources, subsoil, etc.) [9].

Concerning social-reputational capital, it comprises four components related to four groups of stakeholders: insiders (the first group), commodity market participants (the second group), financial market participants (the third group), and society and the state (the fourth group).

As noted, Organizational Capital, which is directly linked to the corporate component of social-reputational capital, plays a crucial role in generating all types of innovations that underpin intellectual and social-reputational capital.

A particularly important role in the assessment of intellectual and social-reputational capital is assigned to the evaluation of the innovation process, specifically: technological innovations, including product, process, and service innovations, which lead to the emergence of identifiable intangible assets in the form of intellectual property and social-reputational capital in the form of a brand; and organizational innovations, which lead to the emergence of unidentifiable capital, namely organizational capital.

In the assessment of social-reputational capital, it is necessary to reflect aspects such as indicators of the corporate, market, financial, and social components; the book and market value of means of identification, in particular the brand; factors influencing the formation and destruction of capital [10; 11]. Furthermore, in evaluating these types of capital, it is essential to demonstrate their impact on market capitalization and fundamental value. At the same time, it should be taken into account that the excess of market capitalization over book value is associated with the presence of intangible capital, whereas the excess of book value over market capitalization is related to ineffective company management or specific conditions of its operation (notably, government regulation).

The key aspects of assessing the components of intellectual and social-reputational capital are presented in Figure 2.

Information disclosed for each component of intellectual and social-reputational capital is generalized based on the following groups of indicators.

The first group of indicators provides an assessment of the organizational capital of the company, determining its capabilities to form the other components of intellectual and social-reputational capital [2, p. 44]. To assess organizational capital, it is necessary to analyze the main components of the business model, namely: the products, their quality, price, and margin; the markets in which they are operated; the sales channels used; the key resources, including production, intellectual, natural, human, and social-reputational; the key business processes, including innovative and investment processes, procurement, production, logistics, and sales.

To comprehend the value of organizational capital, information regarding the company's structure is also required, including data on its subsidiaries and dependent companies, which constitute levels within the company's structure: the first

level – value-added creation: manufacturing companies; the second level – servicing the manufacturing companies: service, procurement, sales, licensing, financial, and project companies; the third level – management of manufacturing and servicing companies, consolidation, and profits: holding, subholding, and management companies; The fourth level involves profit generation and the implementation of strategic control: the ultimate beneficiaries.

Fig. 2. Key Aspects of Assessing Intellectual and Social-Reputational Capital (Author’s Original Development)

The next information block characterizing Organizational Capital is data on the hierarchy of the company’s strategies, which comprises three levels: top level – corporate strategy, middle level – business strategies of the company’s business units, and third level – functional strategies (market, investment, financial, etc.). When disclosing strategy information, data on the anticipated changes in market conditions, sales volume forecasts, as well as the volume and directions of future

investments, are required. Strategic analysis is particularly essential for forecasting the future condition of the business.

To assess the company's infrastructure and the sophistication of the management technologies employed, information regarding the company's ERP systems should be analyzed.

The second group of indicators for assessing intellectual capital characterizes the Intellectual Property Assets and the company's initiatives directed at the development of intellectual capital, acquisition of innovations, research and development, and intangible technological innovations; on the improvement of Organizational Capital – corporate culture, business model, organizational structure, infrastructure, ERP systems, business processes, procedures, technologies, technical and software equipment [2, pp. 44–45]. This group of indicators characterizes intellectual property and Organizational Capital and enables the assessment of: the effectiveness of innovation acquisition methods – internal generation, acquisition, borrowing; Efficiency of knowledge management methods – codification and personalization of knowledge; Efficiency of own research and development units and productivity of their employees; Efficiency of costs for the formation of intellectual capital, as well as their dynamics, structure, and relative indicators – per employee, as a percentage of revenue, and as a percentage of total investments.

Resulting indicators of intellectual capital creation – company-owned Intellectual Property Assets, their book and fair value, as well as indicators of three groups of interrelated innovations: renewability of managerial and organizational technologies – from evolutionary organizational development to radical business process reengineering; updating of production technologies – costs associated with acquiring new technologies, the proportion of technologies meeting contemporary requirements; updating of products – the proportion of new products; stage of the product life cycle.

The third group of indicators is designed to assess social-reputational capital with regard to corporate governance [12, pp. 112–119; 13, pp. 87–91], in particular, the board of directors [14, pp. 71–83] and personnel; These indicators complement the characteristics of organizational capital; they should provide users of the reporting with an understanding of the level of professionalism and integrity of the company's top management, as well as the loyalty, engagement, and productivity of the personnel. To this end, it is necessary to assess the following information [15]: corporate culture, values, management philosophy, code of conduct, ethical norms and values, traditions, and company symbols; transparency in business control – accessibility of information regarding beneficiaries, transparency of the corporate governance structure, and the activities of corporate governance bodies; indicators of the control structure – the aggregate share of the three largest shareholders; share of shares owned by management; share of shares owned by members of the board

of directors; share of participation of the state or municipality in the authorized capital, existence of a special right ('golden share'); share of shares owned by foreign participants; characteristics of the board of directors; share of independent, non-executive, and executive directors; frequency of board of directors meetings; committees as part of the board of directors; functions and types of the board of directors: ceremonial, operational, strategic, advisory, supervisory; remuneration of members of the highest corporate governance bodies.

Indicators of social-reputational capital with regard to personnel provide an opportunity to assess the level of their trust in the company and its top management [11, pp. 202–205]. For such an assessment, it is necessary to analyze the following aspects [6, pp. 104–105]: standards of social support for employees; the composition, structure, and dynamics of social investments; remuneration levels and their compliance with regional and sectoral standards; the degree of wage differentiation; indicators of employee engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty; personnel turnover indicators – staff turnover rate, inflow turnover, outflow turnover; health and industrial safety indicators – occupational injury rates, occupational diseases, and the total number of fatal workplace accidents; indicators of employees' professionalism development and career progression; the number of complaints concerning labor relations practices.

The fourth group of indicators social-reputational capital reflects the trust of market entities. When assessing customers, it is necessary to consider the specifics of the markets (B2B or B2C), since the interaction strategy with end consumers – whether individuals or legal entities – has its own particular characteristics. In particular, when assessing social-reputational capital in relation to customers, it is necessary to evaluate the following aspects [6, p. 106]: brand value, degree of brand recognition; customer loyalty and satisfaction, consumer loyalty index; stability of the customer base, indicators of its turnover; indicators of customer concentration, share of the largest customers in revenue; average purchase volume per customer, profit attributable to one customer; advertising expenses, product promotion expenses, the proportion of commercial expenses in revenue; market capacity, the company's market share in both physical and monetary terms in key markets, and market price segment.

Indicators of social-reputational capital related to suppliers are also essential for understanding the company's operational resilience and its ability to generate value. For such an assessment, attention should be focused on characteristics such as [6, p. 106]: indicators of cooperation with suppliers, as well as supplier loyalty and turnover indicators; indicators of supplier concentration, the share of the largest suppliers in the volume of deliveries; reliability of suppliers, urgency and uninterruptedness of deliveries; optimality of suppliers regarding price and quality of the supplied products; characteristics of procurement regulations, violations, and complaints concerning the organization of the procurement system.

Social-Reputational Capital is also realized in relationships with competitors when mutual understanding is reached, which transforms into mutually beneficial market interactions, enabling improvement of the business environment, enhancing the investment attractiveness of the industry, and increasing the value created [11]. Indicators of social-reputational capital regarding competitors are aimed at evaluating the intensity of competition in the markets; for this purpose, the following indicators are analyzed [6, pp. 106–107]: market concentration indicators, producers' market shares and their dynamics, the share of imports in the market, market openness to new entrants; characteristics of the resource base, competitors' product and pricing policies, competitive advantages; company participation in industry alliances, involvement in strategic alliances, instances of joint lobbying of interests; presence of facts of price wars, facts of unfair competition, and other conflicts with competitors.

The fifth group of indicators of social-reputational capital reflects the financial component, i.e., the trust of investors and creditors, and characterizes the company's access to sources of equity and borrowed capital on the one hand, and its attractiveness as an object of investment and lending on the other [6, p. 107]: stability of relations with key creditors; company credit rating; level of debt burden, interest rate, contract terms; emission history; characteristics of securities issues; company beta coefficient, required return on equity, weighted average cost of capital; distribution policy indicators – amount and frequency of dividend payments, volume of funds allocated for share repurchases, other profit distribution methods; company capitalization indicators; level of capital and current profitability of investments in the company's shares.

The sixth group of indicators social-reputational capital characterizes the social component (society and the state) [11]. Indicators relating to society reflect the social significance of the company [6, p. 108]: the volume, composition, structure, and dynamics of social investments made by the company, including investments in projects for the creation and reconstruction of social infrastructure facilities; social, charitable, and sponsorship projects of the company; resources allocated for supporting culture, sports, municipal institutions, and public organizations; the level of public support for the company; the website citation index of the company; the presence of positive information about the company in the press.

Indicators of social-reputational capital concerning the state should characterize the company as a taxpayer; in addition, it is important to comprehend those relationships with the state that may exert a significant influence on the company's activities. As key characteristics of this dimension of social-reputational capital, the following indicators may be employed [6, p. 108]: tax burden, including its breakdown by types of taxes and levels of the tax system; participation in government programs and procurement competitions; licenses obtained for the execution of specific types

of activities; existence of government contracts within the operational portfolio; government support received by the company; tax benefits and tax credits; investment grants; other disbursements received from government authorities; indicators of the availability of administrative resources.

The final stage of assessing the components of intellectual and social-reputational capital is the evaluation of how these forms of capital influence the value generated by the company. The degree of this influence is evaluated by the dynamics of market capitalization, Tobin's q ratio, the fundamental value, and its ratio to book and replacement values [16]. At the same time, the impact of individual components of capital on the value generated can only be assessed through expert judgment; this influence cannot be determined by calculation [17].

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**KNOWLEDGE AND ITS ROLE IN SHAPING
THE CONSCIOUSNESS OF THE YOUNGER GENERATION:
PREPARATION FOR THE NEW WORLD ORDER**

Kharlanov Alexey Sergeevitch

*Doctor of Economic Sciences, Candidate of Technical Sciences, Full
Professor*

*Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation,
Moscow, Russia*

Abstract. *The author examines the process of knowledge accumulation and considers historical analogies concerning its integration into the consciousness of the younger generation from the standpoint of harmonious and comprehensive development, emphasizing the evolution of pedagogical innovations as an organic synthesis of the scientific and technological revolution (STR), the development of class relations, and the challenges confronting the state in the post-industrial era and within the ‘knowledge economy.’ The research methods comprise historical analogies and the analysis of information utilized in the intergenerational transmission process, which consolidates the ongoing transformation of acquired competencies. These competencies reflect novel responses to existing challenges and help mitigate the barrier of resolving the ‘conflict between generations’ as a pivotal task involving the cumulative acquisition of skills and capabilities for sustainable and indispensable development. One such example of brain impact identified by the author is custom-developed neural algorithms which, as part of the ecosystem of a growing organism, shape its consumption culture and enhance the ability to evaluate responses to informational stimuli through sleep regulation and programming bookmarks of emotional perception.*

Keywords: *youth, NBICS, AI, Big Data, digital twins, avatars, ecosystem, Industry 4.0, creative sleep, UN SDGs, generational conflict, innovations, innovation theory, Joseph Schumpeter, behavioral economics, creative industries, metaverses, immersiveness, Daniel Kahneman, Richard Thaler. Iran, USA, Israel.*

The world of March 2026 reveals that the blazing Middle East, a leaderless Venezuela, and an energy-deprived Cuba outline a global chaos world order, wherein the will of the ‘strongest in the world’ is being imposed in anticipation of the

capitulation of national sovereignties and the full acceptance of the new neocon order. This order is presented to the younger generation from a standpoint of compulsory involvement and active participation across all theaters of military operations, without the right to their own salvation.

The prevailing paradigm of development in any society encompasses the ability to accumulate skills honed over centuries for self-sufficient advancement, addressing current challenges and future threats that specifically and civilizationally accompany nations, thereby testing peoples' adequacy and evolutionary adaptability. [1] Therefore, any historical and social changes following a period of upheaval invariably leave, ultimately, enduring values that define the true spirit of each ethnos and its pace of adaptation in a world marked by climatic and aesthetic threats, ongoing conflicts over territories, and control over sources of self-sustenance (from food security to the technological standards required for the safe operation of infrastructure and other societal institutions). [2]

Physiologically formulated and proven, based on the hierarchy of values, personality development – according to Abraham Maslow's views and its evolving demands – has always originated from vital needs and the real necessities of a person in food and shelter, the security of life and work, and the aspiration for a genuine understanding of one's place in spiritual and professional growth. Strikingly, this growth is rooted in the harmony created by peaceful and creative sleep, which today is individually optimized through AI-driven neuroalgorithms for the digital twin of each person. These tasks today are developed based on personal data that global corporations steal or purchase from operators and hackers to create digital twins, which, like avatars, will be able to receive informational loads during their development within corresponding metaverses. [3;5]

The metaverses themselves, as the foundation of the ecosystem of the controlled and subconscious user/client of the future buyer/accumulator, become part of the formation of the “consumer of the future,” who, within the concept of Marketing 6.0, seeks to maintain a position at the intersection of creative industries, acting unconsciously and impulsively, while immersed in a search for a kind of “nirvanic calm and fleeting comfort.” [4] The latter is achieved through repeated engagement of the individual in the worlds of dreams and surrounding reality via psychosomatic immersion into a state of semi-forgetfulness, euphoria, and unconscious vigilance – a dream within a dream and wakefulness – during chaotic wandering through animated worlds generated by virtual and augmented reality. These mechanisms immediately enable not only the near-complete immersion of the individual into informational flows but also delineate a matrix of opportunities and potentially demanded competencies. This can be regarded as an innovative solution in the education of the sleepwalking individual, devoid of moral and ethical constraints, unrestrained by their ignorance or inferiority, and lacking accountability for the

reception of inclusive impact provoked by societal responses to certain defects, developmental delays, or pathologies, considered part of hypnotic deviant behavior. Here, both healthy and ill individuals can experience a ‘euphoria of freedom,’ which permits unrestricted fantasies that absolve them of responsibility for all that transpires, since such an ‘absorption of informational patterns,’ like sponges, formally remains a theory of dreaming first described in the 19th century by Sigmund Freud. Naturally, this eminent psychologist and neurophysiologist could never have envisaged that the advancement of science and the consequent shift in societal motivation – driven by an excess of goods and services – would enable the subliminal erotic and base desires to engage with massive emotional overgrowths, where psychological expectations and artificial realities merge into a form of conscious delirium, bordering on psychosis, generating dependency and cultivating addictions and persistent demands for their recurrence through endorphin cocktails and heightened sensations alien to the actual existence of such individuals.

Thus, the methods previously tested by global governance institutions during pandemic shocks, along with the transition to online formats of various educational, control, and practical implementation options for learners of different ages, represented merely the first stage of innovation in the development of consciousness – viewed from the perspective of provoking its emotional sphere (ranging from fear of COVID death to frustration and indifference manifested in unlimited shopping accumulation, slogans such as ‘you only live once,’ ‘after us the flood,’ ‘to be forever young, forever drunk,’ etc.). The subsequent stage involved the return of the ‘saved’ individuals from rational perception back into the framework of behavioral economics as articulated by Daniel Kahneman and Richard Thaler, who utilize a creative basis for unrestrained consumption characterized by a hypertrophied Superego and irrational aberrations during the process of internalizing new life standards – standards that had deteriorated following the experience of enforced isolation or even pandemic-driven self-destruction in their cells, apartments, or offices. At the same time, objectively, distance learning technologies have fostered not only the possibility of partial disengagement from the process of knowledge assimilation but also the capacity to manipulate interactive communication opportunities within virtual spaces, to avoid complying with required requests in real time, skillfully combining the functionalities of gadgets and the internet with actual and systemic informational injections or supportive content. The learner came to understand that the geophysical environment is not always solely a benefit but can also represent an escalating threat to their freedom and self-esteem, since the digital environment at any moment may become a source of personal data leakage, a target for hacker cyberattacks, and subject to cognitive threats from various actors capable of discrediting, intimidating, or paralyzing the will of an ordinary person within the ‘learner-computer’ system. [5]

At the same time, the most consistently transformative yet enduring innovation of an accumulative nature can be regarded as the Soviet experience of various master classes and open lectures unveiling the ‘secrets of professional mastery,’ interaction within creative circles, participation in lecture fora, visits to venues of collaborative scientific and creative engagement, and applied network pedagogy that fosters cognitive abilities and supports informed decision-making regarding future professional paths.

Joseph Schumpeter, as a representative of the Austrian economic school, argued – according to the theory of innovations – that innovation must remain a fundamental prerequisite for the modernization and development of any state. Such a state is obliged to ensure confidence that the ever-growing needs of society are met by addressing the emerging demand through market mechanisms or by implementing planning based on forecasting and an understanding of the actual vulnerabilities of the ethnic groups residing within its territory. For example, this was formerly systematically and effectively demonstrated within the framework of the same planned socialist economy, exemplified by the cooperative and diversified activities of the CMEA states. Today, it is brilliantly confirmed in the emerging robot-humanoid paradigm of Industry 4.0, as previously articulated by Klaus Schwab, representing an environment of continuous education for both machines and humans aimed at the possible expansion of capabilities and unique competencies that unify production and distribution processes. [6] The learning process itself thus becomes an argument in the growth function of accumulated knowledge, which can lead both quantitatively and qualitatively to various synergetic effects, multiplying the symbiosis of different forms of application in practice and in the process of shaping an educational trajectory within an industry, university, or scientific research space, such as a cluster, campus, startup, or greenfield.

The solution to the so-called ‘sleeping innovation,’ which is already planned for mass implementation beginning with infants from the cradle, has been realized by Elon Musk’s robot nanny for his children. This system applies a symbiosis of AI and Big Data to prototype digital twins, which, according to the CEO of Tesla and SpaceX, should be capable from childhood of living between worlds, preserving their individuality, and valuing the freedom of both real and imagined spaces. At the same time, the task of maintaining the creative component within an individual resides between harmony and rest, where the fundamental condition remains calm and healthy sleep, which enables simultaneous development and learning. According to the concept proposed by global governance institutions, this will yield a new entity – the ‘rational human’ and the ‘rational consumer’—representing the next stage of evolution for the ‘beta’ generation (from 2025 to 2039). [4;7]

This in no way infringes upon the rights of the ‘alpha’ generation to irrational consumption in their pursuit of affiliation with celebrities within behavioral

economics and the creative industries, but it imposes a filter on the innovative development of knowledge transmission between its source and the consuming element. Whereas earlier a tutor could be a robot for a living child, today a programmer can act as a teacher for a robot within the context of AI development in machine and deep learning, large linguistic models, and generative neuro-algorithms. These technologies are currently at a transitional stage toward higher AI advancement (the intermediate phase until 2100 involves complex aggregations of machines and quantum and ultrafast network computing structures – cobots and collaborative robots – progressing toward refinement to the level of a Superintellect, which ‘digital nomads’ predict will emerge after 2100). [7]

Furthermore, the convergence of trends in the humanization of robots (especially cobots) and the dehumanization of humans increasingly withdrawing into metaverses and the Internet of Things will culminate at a point of effective coexistence. At this juncture, the unified capabilities and creative potential on both sides will depend on innovations and continuous learning, which will be refined in the quest for adaptability and adequacy by selecting ever more sophisticated methods and offering increasingly subtle mechanisms to enhance uniqueness – and thus exclusivity – as a form of ‘quality mark’ from the perspective of psycho-somatic development and the overcoming of cognitive dissonances and aging at physiological and scientific-technical levels. [8]

Iran’s struggle against Israel and the United States for its survival reveals that the world refuses to learn from past mistakes, wars, and conflicts, hurtling instead toward an era marked by ignorance and intolerance, religious fanaticism, and extremism among people who have utterly lost faith in traditional values. This is evident when, during the sacred month of Ramadan, hundreds of schoolgirls can be killed, along with the supreme leader of all Shiites – demonstrating that his path as a mullah and martyr was perceived as the only viable response to the policies of ignoramus and provocateurs who redraw earthly borders and human consciousness. They precisely demonstrate that, having loved Evil in the name of their own ambitions and adhering exclusively to their professed set of decisions called ‘systemic Good,’ based on Old Testament conceptions and interpretations of civilizational challenges, one can once again crucify and destroy that for which the font of all religions was established, and for which God was crucified – God who grants everyone love and mercy in the name of salvation, regardless of nations and without the right to condemn a neighbor, provided that he too repents of his sins and turns the other cheek, in order to save both himself and the one who acts unlawfully but does not realize it, the offender...

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THE ROLE OF KEY INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGIES IN ESTABLISHING A DIGITALLY ADAPTIVE ENTERPRISE ECOSYSTEM

Tashkinov Aleksei Grigorievich

*Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Perm National Research Polytechnic University*

Abstract: *This article explores the transformative impact of key Industry 4.0 technologies on modern enterprise production systems. It provides a comprehensive analysis of how the integration of cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things (IoT), big data analytics, and cloud computing is revolutionizing manufacturing environments. The study examines specific applications, such as predictive maintenance, real-time supply chain optimization, and the creation of “digital twins” for process simulation. By evaluating case studies and current industrial trends, the article demonstrates how these technologies enhance operational efficiency, flexibility, and product quality. It concludes by discussing the strategic implications for managers and the necessary steps for successful technological adoption in the journey toward a smart factory. Practical recommendations for the implementation of a digital adaptive ecosystem in the context of Industry 4.0 were developed. The implementation of the concept of a digital adaptive ecosystem, based on management concepts, allows for the development of a unified digital transformation strategy to achieve a synergistic effect and ensure the competitiveness of industrial enterprises in the context of Industry 4.0.*

Keywords: *Industry 4.0, digitally adaptive ecosystem, production system, enterprise, smart factory.*

Introduction

Today, an increasing number of organizations are improving customer service by leveraging Industry 4.0 technologies, and they are expanding their value proposition creation processes through analysis derived from current product usage data. The digital transformation process is affecting all businesses, regardless of their industry, as digitalization is both a vital necessity and a competitive advantage.

At the same time, as companies approach digital transformation, they often rethink their internal organization. This includes the company’s structure, its

relationships with employees, its relationships with customers/clients, and even the presentation of new digital models to the market, as well as digital transformation projects that compel others to respond. The focus is on gaining an advantage in the competitive landscape. However, companies that view digital technologies solely from a profit perspective fail to consider important aspects that are inextricably linked to the interaction of all elements of the production and economic system with the company's strategic core. These aspects could soon lose their competitive advantage in the market [1].

Given this situation, the purpose of this study is to develop an integrated approach to enterprise management in the context of Industry 4.0. The objectives are: to describe the key elements of a smart factory and to substantiate the feasibility of applying this approach using a smart factory within an enterprise.

Materials and Methods

This paper adopts a multi-stage research methodology to operationalize the concept of an adaptive production ecosystem. The initial stage involves a critical analysis of key Industry 4.0 technologies to determine their functional roles within an integrated enterprise management system. Subsequent stages focus on the architectural design of the ecosystem, detailing the successive integration of these technologies to build a responsive and intelligent smart factory.

This study is based on the formation of successive stages of building a smart factory within the framework of an integrated approach to enterprise management in the context of Industry 4.0.

Results

Recent and comprehensive research confirms that digital transformation through Industry 4.0 technologies is fundamental to improving the operational efficiency of manufacturing systems. This conclusion is supported by a significant body of research emphasizing the critical importance of integrating these technologies to achieve seamless convergence within a digitally adaptive ecosystem.

To solve this problem, many authors propose using Industry 4.0 technologies. For example, one study suggests using a number of digitalization tools in the field of cargo handling and logistics, such as RFID sensors, electronic document management, cloud systems, and a one-stop shop system. This ranges from the implementation of advanced Internet of Things (IoT) sensors to the strategic use of artificial intelligence (AI) and blockchain [2]. Another study proposes using cloud computing, artificial intelligence, machine learning, the Industrial Internet of Things, and others for various sectors of the economy. The combined use of these technologies allows not only to change a particular business process, but also to completely restructure the industry, introducing a product that did not exist

before [3]. One scientific publication examines the concept of digital transformation of production — Industry 4.0. The concept of a “smart” (digital, virtual) factory serves as the technological core [4].

As one of the solutions, within the framework of developing an integrated approach to enterprise management in the context of Industry 4.0, we propose creating conditions for the development of smart production, which is carried out by going through the main sequential stages.

Next, we’ll describe the smart factory’s operation in terms of applying an integrated approach. Previously, our system used statistical data collected manually or not at all to analyze production operations. This hinders access to accurate information for assessing the current state and forecasting the future state of production. In our case, regarding this approach, all the necessary information can be accessed in real time via the Internet of Things. Some IoT technologies simulate reality, test various digital scenarios, and utilize digital twin technology. A digital twin of an industrial enterprise is its copy in a virtual environment. The function of a digital twin is to reproduce processes and operations at the enterprise with high accuracy, which allows for solving a wide range of operational problems. A digital twin in production ensures accurate forecasting of production volumes and orders and helps determine the optimal amount of equipment for organizing the production process and the required inventory of production resources. This technology evaluates the peak and optimal performance of each unit in the production chain to forecast contract volumes and helps monitor equipment wear under various loads. Digital twins are also effective in the operation of high-tech equipment. Furthermore, such digital solutions are used to evaluate the impact of digital technology implementation and the commissioning of process, engineering, and testbed equipment. In our case, artificial intelligence can be connected to data to manage a wide range of functions, including staff personalization, process optimization, and sophisticated analytics used to understand the potential value of new products and services [6].

Based on this, let us consider the constituent elements of the concept, which include the essence, purpose, objectives, principles, presented schematically in Figure 1.

The proposed concept of the Digital Adaptive Enterprise Ecosystem is based on five complementary principles, the combined action of which generates a synergistic effect that qualitatively transforms the industry system.

1. Bimodal architecture.

This principle consists of combining a stable “core” (digital transformation strategy, digital competencies, finance) with flexible, self-organizing project teams and digital platforms.

Digital Adaptive Enterprise Ecosystem– is a self-learning cyber-physical-social system that proactively adapts to changes through the synergy of artificial intelligence, organizational flexibility, and digital technologies, meeting the requirements of the resource-based structure in the context of Industry 4.0

The Goal of the Digital Adaptive Ecosystem– increasing the strategic sustainability and competitiveness of the OPES by ensuring the ability to proactively adapt to the challenges and opportunities of the external and internal environment within the framework of the new resource structure in the context of Industry 4.0

The objectives of the Digital Adaptive Ecosystem are:

- ensuring technological flexibility and integration;
- development of adaptability and intelligence of the system;
- formation and management of the ecosystem (network effect)
- ensuring security and stability;
- ensuring the effectiveness of adaptive management of the production system

Principles of the Digital Adaptive Ecosystem:

- bimodal architecture;
- management based on data and digital twins;
- development of adaptive potential as a strategic goal;
- network-centricity and ecosystem-centricity;
- intellectualization and autonomy

Fig. 1. The concept of a Digital Adaptive Industrial Ecosystem

2. Management based on data and digital twins.

The digital twin of an industry system becomes a central element of the control loop, implementing cybernetic principles and enabling predictive analytics and scenario modeling in near-real time.

3. Development of adaptive potential as a strategic goal.

Management is aimed at the constant growth and renewal of four types of capital: technological, human, organizational and social.

4. Network-centricity and ecosystem-centricity.

The industry system is positioned not as a closed hierarchy, but as a node in a supply and innovation network. Management is shifting from administrative control to coordination and the creation of rules for interaction within the ecosystem.

5. The principle of intellectualization and autonomy.

Senior management sets the “rules of the game” (framework, KPIs, risk tolerance limits) within which operating units have a high degree of autonomy and are capable of self-organization to solve problems.

Thus, the essence of the Digital Adaptive Enterprise Ecosystem is the creation of a flexible system where synergy between ecosystem participants, the organization, and technology becomes the primary mechanism for proactive adaptation. The concept overcomes traditional gaps by integrating various methodologies into

a single management framework, where synergies are purposefully generated as the primary source of sustainable competitive advantage.

Thus, the description of the presented stages and the smart factory as part of an integrated approach to enterprise management in the context of Industry 4.0 offers advantages and has practical applications in manufacturing [5].

The novelty of the digital adaptive ecosystem of an industrial enterprise in the context of Industry 4.0 lies in the synthesis of the philosophical principles of lean manufacturing (creating a continuous flow of value and eliminating waste) with the technological capabilities of digital production (end-to-end data integration, artificial intelligence, and the Industrial Internet of Things), which gives rise to a fundamentally new class of self-learning and self-optimizing production systems capable of proactive adaptation, emergent behavior, and the generation of network effects, overcoming the fundamental limitations of traditional deterministic models and creating sustainable competitive advantages through the speed of learning, rather than through static efficiency.

Thus, we have examined in detail the architecture, advantages, and operating principles of a digital adaptive ecosystem, allowing us to see the overall picture of the enterprise's future. However, between today and this ambitious goal lies a path that requires not only technological solutions but also strategic planning, organizational transformation, and phased implementation.

Discussion

A review of the relevant literature [1], [2], [3] confirms the measurable benefits of embedding digital technologies into established enterprise management frameworks. This analysis is complemented by an examination of advanced artificial intelligence techniques within industrial Industry 4.0 applications. The findings indicate that successful implementation is heavily contingent on effective prioritization. Achieving this requires the establishment of consistent internal communication channels that bridge the gap between transformation leaders and daily system users. While this collaborative approach diverges from the traditional practices observed in financial institutions, the literature consistently identifies cross-functional collaboration as a cornerstone of successful digital transformation [4].

This study presents an integrated approach to enterprise management in the context of Industry 4.0. It describes the stages and benefits of implementing a smart factory in manufacturing, aimed at increasing the operational efficiency of the production and economic system and improving enterprise performance [5]. To be competitive in the market, enterprises must be willing to experiment, learn from mistakes, and quickly adapt to changing market dynamics [6]. Therefore, business agility and the ability to anticipate emerging trends are crucial for success in a competitive environment. Furthermore, uncertainty and instability are

characteristic of the cyber-physical world [7]. An enterprise's ability to overcome these shocks depends on its resilience and adaptability. At its core, the role of Industry 4.0 in enterprise management lies in the use of digital technologies that leverage data and connectivity to develop intelligent networks characterized by a high level of collaboration, ultimately contributing to a significant increase in overall industrial productivity [8].

Conclusion

This study set out to examine how key Industry 4.0 technologies contribute to the development of an adaptive production ecosystem. Our investigation has successfully addressed the initial research questions by uncovering previously underexplored areas and validating findings through both scientific reasoning and practical application. The resulting methodology rests on a dual foundation: first, enriching the theoretical landscape of adaptive enterprise management, and second, delivering actionable, step-by-step techniques for the practical integration of Industry 4.0 technologies.

Thus, the presented results form a comprehensive solution that not only enables the implementation of a digital adaptive ecosystem architecture but also ensures the company's systematic preparation for the accompanying transformational changes. This includes strategic digital transformation planning, effective management of related projects, and, ultimately, the achievement of sustainable development goals for the industry's production and economic system.

Future work will focus on methodological and practical support for industrial enterprises, specifically assessing their digital maturity and the economic efficiency of the digital adaptive ecosystem.

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CURRENT LEVEL AND DYNAMICS OF DIGITALIZATION IN THE SCO MEMBER STATES

Melibaeva Gulnara Achilovna

*Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Higher School of Business and Entrepreneurship under the Cabinet
of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan,
Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan*

Tursunova Malika Anvarovna

*Doctoral Student
Higher School of Business and Entrepreneurship under the Cabinet
of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan,
Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan*

Abstract: *The article analyzes the current level of digital transformation in the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, identifies the main trends and features of digitalization processes in various countries of the region. Based on the analysis of statistical data and scientific publications, key directions of digital development, existing barriers and prospects for deepening digital cooperation between SCO states are determined.*

Keywords: *digitalization, SCO, digital economy, information technologies, digital transformation, international cooperation*

INTRODUCTION

The Shanghai Cooperation Organization, which brings together Russia, China, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, India, Pakistan and Iran, represents one of the largest regional integration mechanisms, covering about half of the world's population and a significant share of global economic potential.

In the context of global digital transformation, the development of digital technologies and the digital economy acquires strategic importance for ensuring the competitiveness and sustainable development of the member states of the organization [1]. Digitalization of the economy and public life is becoming a key factor in the modernization of national economies, increasing labor productivity, improving the quality of public services, and forming new models of economic interaction between the countries of the region [2].

The relevance of this study is determined by the need for a comprehensive analysis of the current state of digitalization processes in the SCO countries, the identification of general patterns and specific features of digital transformation in different national contexts, as well as the determination of promising directions for deepening digital cooperation within the organization.

METHODOLOGY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The methodological basis of the research is a comprehensive approach that includes the analysis of official statistical data from international organizations, national statistical agencies of the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, analytical materials from leading research centers, as well as a systematic review of scientific publications devoted to the issues of digitalization in the region.

The study employs methods of comparative analysis to compare the indicators of digital development across different states, content analysis of scientific literature and strategic documents, as well as synthesis of the obtained data in order to form a holistic understanding of the dynamics of digitalization within the SCO space.

The theoretical basis of the study is formed by the works of leading specialists in the field of digital economy and international economic cooperation. Studies show that SCO countries demonstrate significant differentiation in the level of digital development, which is обусловлено differences in economic potential, technological infrastructure, and institutional conditions [3].

China occupies leading positions in the region in terms of the scale of the digital economy, the volume of investments in digital technologies, and the development of digital infrastructure, implementing ambitious strategies of digital transformation and actively promoting initiatives for the creation of the Digital Silk Road [4].

Russia and India also demonstrate high potential for digital development by implementing large-scale national programs for the digitalization of the economy and public administration [5].

The Central Asian republics, despite certain lag in absolute indicators, demonstrate stable growth dynamics of the digital sector and actively introduce digital technologies in various sectors of the economy [6].

Scientific literature emphasizes the importance of international cooperation in the field of digitalization, including the harmonization of regulatory and legal frameworks, the development of cross-border digital infrastructure, exchange of experience and technologies, as well as the formation of common approaches to the regulation of digital markets [7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An analysis of the current state of digitalization in the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization reveals several key trends and distinctive features. The People's Republic of China demonstrates the most impressive results

in terms of digital transformation, with the scale of its digital economy exceeding several trillion US dollars and accounting for a significant share of national GDP. China is a global leader in the adoption of e-commerce technologies, mobile payment systems, artificial intelligence, and the deployment of 5G infrastructure, which provides a strong technological foundation for the further expansion of the digital economy [8].

The Russian Federation is actively implementing the national program “Digital Economy,” aimed at developing digital infrastructure, expanding digital platforms and services, and introducing cross-cutting digital technologies across key sectors of the economy. India has also demonstrated remarkable growth in the digital sector, particularly in the areas of information technology, software development, and digital service provision, while actively advancing national initiatives related to digital identification and digital payment systems.

The Central Asian states, including Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Tajikistan, exhibit positive dynamics in the process of digitalization by implementing national digital transformation strategies, actively introducing e-government systems and digital public services, and expanding telecommunications infrastructure [9].

Pakistan and Iran are also undertaking considerable efforts to develop the digital sector despite existing economic and geopolitical challenges.

The main barriers to accelerating digitalization in the region include the uneven development of digital infrastructure, the digital divide between urban and rural areas, a shortage of qualified specialists in the field of information technology, differences in regulatory frameworks governing the digital sphere, as well as challenges related to cybersecurity and data protection [10].

At the same time, SCO member states possess significant potential for deepening digital cooperation, including the creation of a unified digital space, the development of cross-border e-commerce, joint investment projects in digital technologies, and the establishment of common standards for the digital economy.

Table 1. Digital Development Indicators of SCO Member States
(2023–2024)

Country	Share of Digital Economy in GDP, %	Internet Penetration, %	Number of Internet Users, million
China	42,8	77,5–78,0	1092
Russia	~5,0*	92,0	130
India	11,7	52,0–70,0	954–1030
Kazakhstan	n/a	95,0	19,5
Uzbekistan	n/a	83,3	29,5

Kyrgyzstan	n/a	70,0+	~5,0
Pakistan	n/a	~36,0	87

Note: Data compiled from CNNIC (2024), ITU (2023), Statista (2024), DataReportal (2024), and CAICT (2024). The indicator for the Russian Federation reflects the share of the ICT sector in GDP.

An analysis of digital development indicators reveals significant differences among SCO member states. China demonstrates the highest figures for both the absolute size of the digital economy and its share of national GDP, reaching 42.8% in 2023. China’s internet penetration rate is approximately 77.5%, slightly lower than that of developed countries. However, in absolute terms, the country boasts the world’s largest internet user base — over 1.09 billion people. India ranks second in terms of internet users, but its internet penetration remains relatively low — approximately 52–70%, depending on the methodology. Central Asian states are demonstrating rapid growth: Kazakhstan has reached 95% internet penetration, and Uzbekistan, 83.3%.

Figure 1. Ranking of SCO member states according to the UN e-Government Development Index (EGDI 2024)

Source: UN E-Government Survey 2024, United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs.

The results of the UN e-Government Development Index (EGDI 2024) demonstrate that Kazakhstan occupies a leading position among SCO member states, rising to 24th place globally with a score of 0.9009. The country also ranks first among

landlocked countries and leads the CIS. Russia ranks 43rd with an index of 0.8532, maintaining its position among countries with a very high level of e-government development. China ranks 35th, demonstrating significant progress in the digitalization of public services. Uzbekistan moved up to 63rd place, joining the group of countries with a high level of development. These indicators demonstrate the targeted policies of states in the region to implement e-government and digitalize public services, while there remains potential for further cooperation in this area.

CONCLUSION

The analysis shows that SCO member states are demonstrating a steady trend toward digitalization of their economies and public life, although significant differences in the level of digital development persist among individual countries. China, Russia, and India are leading the digital transformation in the region, boasting developed digital infrastructure, a large domestic market for digital goods and services, and significant investments in research and development. The Central Asian republics, Pakistan, and Iran are showing positive momentum, but face a number of structural constraints and barriers. To ensure sustainable and balanced digital development within the SCO region, it is necessary to strengthen multilateral cooperation mechanisms, including the creation of joint digital platforms, the harmonization of regulatory frameworks, the development of human capital, and the exchange of best practices. Deepening digital partnerships within the SCO will contribute to enhancing the competitiveness of member states' economies, creating new opportunities for businesses and citizens, and strengthening the region's position in the global digital economy.

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**METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF COMPARING WELFARE
LEVELS OF DIFFERENT COUNTRIES:
CAUSES OF REGIONAL INEQUALITY**

Lisitsyna Yuliya Aleksandrovna

Postgraduate

Moscow University of the Humanities,

Moscow, Russia

***Abstract.** The article examines modern methodological approaches to comparing the welfare levels of different countries. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of such indicators as purchasing power parity and the Gini coefficient (for income and assets). Based on data from international organizations, Russian statistical sources, as well as information from domestic and foreign studies, key trends in global and regional inequality are identified. The author highlighted factors of quality of life differentiation, including the country's resource endowment, quality of the institutional environment, level of social mobility of the population, scale of the state, and level of technological progress. A conclusion is made about the need to form inclusive institutions to ensure sustainable economic development.*

***Keywords:** social inequality, Gini coefficient, purchasing power parity (PPP), quality of life, human capital, institutional environment, social mobility, economic development.*

In the context of globalization and the strengthening of international economic integration, the problem of comparing the level of well-being across individual countries gains particular relevance. Significant differences in the level of economic development, institutional environment, and income distribution mechanisms lead to substantial differentiation in the quality of life of the population, both within a single country and between countries when comparing their indicators.

For example, nominal indicators (a salary of \$ 6,000 in the USA versus \$ 2,000 in Poland) do not reflect the real quality of life due to differences in the cost of goods, works, and services. In this regard, for correct cross-country comparisons, the **purchasing power parity (PPP)** indicator is used.

When recalculating incomes using PPP, only Luxembourg, Switzerland, Norway, and the UAE enter the group of countries with an annual income exceeding

\$20,000 per capita. Most countries, including Russia, fall within the range of \$2,500 to \$7,500.

The **Gini coefficient** is also used as the main tool for assessing inequality, reflecting the degree of deviation of the actual income distribution from absolute equality. To calculate the coefficient, data on the incomes or assets of citizens of a particular country are used. A value of 0 corresponds to absolute equality, while 1 corresponds to absolute inequality (when all goods belong to one person).

Additionally, one should consider the **Human Development Index (HDI)**, calculated by the UN, which reflects not only the income level but also the quality of life of the population. The index is based on three key aspects: a long and healthy life, access to knowledge, and a decent standard of living.

For a more comprehensive analysis, it is advisable to consider a set of indicators. Table 1 presents comparative data for the world's most developed countries.

Table 1. Comparative Indicators of Welfare Levels Across Countries
[2, 4, 6, 9, 10]

Country	GDP per capita (PPP, USD)	Gini ratio (income)	Human Development Index (HDI)
Норвегия	82 000	0,27	0,961
США	76 000	0,41	0,921
Германия	66 000	0,31	0,942
Россия	30 000	0,40	0,822
Польша	37 000	0,30	0,876

At the same time, the **Lorenz curve** is used for the graphical interpretation of the Gini coefficient. Figure 1 presents data for Norway, the USA, and Russia.

Based on the data presented, it is evident that the curve for the USA deviates the most from the line of absolute income equality, indicating a higher level of social differentiation in the country. Norway, in contrast, is closer to equality, while Russia's indicator is intermediate.

At the same time, Norway also combines a high HDI level with a relatively low level of inequality, whereas in the USA a high level of development is accompanied by more significant income differentiation.

Thus, a country's high level of economic development and GDP size do not always coincide with a low level of inequality (Gini index) and even distribution of benefits within it, which confirms the need for a comprehensive approach to assessing well-being.

According to Federal State Statistics Service data, the Gini coefficient in Russia in recent years remains at the level of about 0.39–0.40 (see Figure 2), which indicates the stability of social inequality [2]. Bank of Russia studies for 2024

show that the key factor of differentiation is not so much the wage level as the concentration of income from capital and assets [3].

Fig. 1. Lorenz curve for Norway, USA and Russia [10]

Fig. 2. Gini coefficient for the Russian Federation for 1995–2023 [2]

It is worth noting that measuring inequality exclusively by income has limitations, since it does not take into account accumulated wealth — poor segments of the population may hide income due to fear of losing it, and the rich — due to the use of offshore schemes.

Figure 3 shows the global distribution of incomes.

According to World Inequality Lab data, global inequality is characterized by a high concentration of income and assets: the top 10% of the wealthiest population accounts for more than half of world income. At the same time, wealth distribution estimates indicate an even higher concentration of capital.

Fig. 3. Global income distribution [8]

Foreign experience demonstrates the existence of various models of welfare distribution. Thus, Scandinavian countries are characterized by a high level of income redistribution and a developed social protection system, which contributes to reducing inequality. Meanwhile, in the USA, a different model is observed, where a high level of economic development is combined with a high concentration of capital.

Therefore, the Gini index by assets (real estate, securities) is considered more objective, which in the global ratio is 0.889, critically close to absolute inequality [5]. At the same time, a high level of inequality is observed in the USA (0.85), Russia (0.88), Sweden, and Arabian Peninsula countries, while the most even distribution of assets is observed in Slovakia, Qatar, and Belgium (where the Gini index is below 0.6).

In this regard, a paradox arises: contrary to the general trend, according to which rich countries (such as Canada, Europe, Japan) demonstrate high internal equality, other developed countries, for example, the USA and Sweden, are exceptions — high concentration of capital among the elite, along with a developed economy, creates a significant gap.

As Thomas Piketty notes, in the long term, the return on capital exceeds economic growth rates, leading to even greater wealth inequality. The author also

notes that, despite changes in the global economy, the main conclusions from earlier studies remain relevant today [7].

Economic science does not provide a definitive answer on the **primary causes of such inequality**. Nevertheless, it is possible to identify several key aspects:

1. Resource base: the presence of natural resources or fertile land creates a basis for primary capital accumulation. However, this condition is not sufficient due to the phenomenon of the “resource curse”, when income from raw materials is concentrated in the hands of a narrow elite without developing the middle class.

2. Quality of institutions: the presence of private property protection, judicial independence, etc. Institutions should be inclusive (i. e., ensuring sustainable long-term welfare growth), rather than extractive (aimed at short-term but insufficiently sustainable growth)[1, c. 9].

3. Low mobility of the population of poor regions (psychological barriers and lack of funds for relocation) reinforces the “poverty trap”. According to OECD data (2023), the transition from lower groups to middle ones occurs slowly and also depends on the country [4]. On average, it takes 4–5 generations to move from the low-income group to the middle class, which indicates high stability of socio-economic differences.

4. Scale and territorial heterogeneity of the country.

5. Level of scientific and technical progress and access to technologies.

However, it should be noted that low inequality alone does not guarantee the economic prosperity of the country. If the country’s population is homogeneous but uniformly poor, this rather hinders the development of the state than stimulates it. Economic growth requires a more complex configuration: the presence of an entrepreneurial elite capable of generating capital; a stable middle class as the basis of domestic demand; consistent investments in human capital and education, as well as the formation of working social lifts. Only the combination of these elements forms a truly balanced society.

The analysis conducted showed that comparing the welfare level of different countries requires a comprehensive approach that takes into account both quantitative and qualitative characteristics of socio-economic development. The use of purchasing power parity and the Gini coefficient allows for a more accurate assessment of the standard of living and the degree of inequality, but these indicators do not reflect the full range of the processes under consideration

The identified paradoxes, in particular the combination of a high level of economic development with significant wealth inequality, confirm the key role of institutional factors. The quality of state institutions, the level of social mobility, access to education and technologies have a determining influence on the distribution of welfare.

In addition, the research results indicate that a low level of inequality in itself is not a guarantee of sustainable economic growth. Effective development is possible only with a balanced interaction of entrepreneurial activity, a developed middle class, and inclusive institutions.

Thus, the priority direction of state policy should be the creation of conditions for increasing social mobility, developing human capital, and reducing structural disproportions in the distribution of income and assets.

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LABOR MARKET AS A NEW ELEMENT IN M. PORTER'S COMPETITIVENESS MODEL

Muzalevsky Yaroslav Yuryevich

Postgraduate

Moscow International University,

Moscow, Russia

Prokudin Vladilen Andreevich

Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Moscow International University,

Moscow, Russia

Abstract. *The article substantiates the inclusion of the labor market as an independent element in M. Porter's model of competitive advantage. A new component is proposed — the organizational-institutional labor factor (LOF), reflecting the quality of labor market institutions. A comparative analysis of the labor markets of ten BRICS and EU countries was conducted, including the calculation of integral competitiveness indices (ICI). A minimal gap of 9.6 points has been identified between the blocks in terms of institutional characteristics of the labor market. Two opposing models of labor market organization have been identified: the European 'organized flexibility' and the 'unorganized flexibility' of BRICS countries.*

Keywords: *labor market, Porter's model, competitiveness, institutional flexibility, social partnership, labor mobility, BRICS, European Union, integral index.*

Introduction

Michael Porter, in his work 'The Competitive Advantage of Nations' (1990), proposed the 'diamond of competitive advantage' model, which includes four interrelated elements: factor conditions, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and firm strategy and rivalry [15, p. 73]. However, labor characteristics were attributed exclusively to factor conditions — as resource parameters (productivity, qualification). The institutional environment of the labor market — labor legislation, social partnership mechanisms, labor mobility — is not distinguished as a separate element in the model.

As V. P. Andreev notes, competitiveness is determined not only by production factors but also by the ability of countries to create effective institutional conditions

[1, p. 45]. I. S. Belova highlights that the institutional specificity of labor markets differs significantly between developed and developing economies [2, p. 78].

The central thesis of the study is that the labor market should be identified as an independent element in Porter’s model. An organizational-institutional labor factor (LOF, Labor Organization Factor) is proposed, including: 1) institutional flexibility of the labor market; 2) effectiveness of social partnership; 3) labor mobility and the quality of management. LOF does not duplicate factor conditions (FC): FC describes resources, whereas LOF represents the institutions through which these resources are organized [6, p. 48; 7, p. 125].

Objective: to substantiate the inclusion of the labor market as a new element in Porter’s model and to perform its quantitative assessment for BRICS and EU countries.

Fig. 1. Porter’s Diamond Model of Competitive Advantage

Methods and Materials

Methodology: systems approach, comparative analysis, Pearson correlation analysis, ratio-to-frontier normalization, scenario analysis. Data sources: IMF (WEO, 2024), World Bank (HCI 2020; WGI 2023), WEF (GCI 4.0, 2019), WIPO (GII 2024), OECD, ILO (ILOSTAT), IMD (WCY 2024).

The modified model includes six components. The ICI (Integrated Competitiveness Index) is used for integral assessment:

$$ICI = \sqrt[6]{FC \times DC \times RS \times FS \times IF \times LOF}$$

where FC — factor conditions; DC — demand conditions; RS — related and supporting industries; FS — firm strategy; IF — institutional factors;

LOF — organizational-institutional labor factor. Normalization using the ratio-to-frontier method:

$$X_{\text{norm}} = \frac{X}{X_{\text{max}}} \times 100$$

Data from 10 countries were analyzed: 5 EU countries (Germany, France, Italy, Spain, Poland) and 5 BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa).

Results

Table 1. Component indices of competitiveness

Country	FC	DC	RS	FS	IF	LOF	ICI
Germany	99.5	93.0	95.9	100.0	100.0	95.1	97.2
France	96.3	88.3	74.6	92.4	93.6	76.3	86.5
Italy	84.6	80.7	78.5	82.0	74.6	68.6	78.0
Spain	86.3	77.3	66.7	86.2	86.3	74.1	79.1
Poland	77.7	68.0	69.8	76.7	72.9	74.7	73.2
China	62.6	90.2	93.1	84.6	59.0	79.7	77.0
Russia	65.8	67.5	59.8	64.9	32.3	69.2	58.1
India	45.4	71.6	63.6	73.6	56.5	66.3	62.0
Brazil	51.6	63.3	56.0	64.5	45.7	64.0	57.1
South Africa	45.5	55.2	49.0	62.0	57.4	61.6	54.8

Authors' calculation.

Germany leads in all components (ICI = 97.2). China (ICI = 77.0) surpasses all EU countries except Germany and France in DC (90.2) and RS (93.1). China's LOF (79.7) is higher than France's LOF (76.3) due to institutional flexibility of the labor market.

Calculation example:

$$ICI(\text{Germany}) = \sqrt[6]{99,5 \times 93,0 \times 95,9 \times 100,0 \times 100,0 \times 95,1} = 97,2$$

Table 2. LOF breakdown (normalized values)

Country	Institutional flexibility	Social partnership	Labor mobility	LOF
Germany	86.1	100.0	100.0	95.1
France	66.7	80.0	83.3	76.3

Country	Institutional flexibility	Social partnership	Labor mobility	LOF
China	100.0	52.9	87.2	79.7
Russia	90.3	47.1	70.5	69.2
India	76.4	49.4	74.4	66.3
South Africa	58.3	68.2	57.7	61.6

Institutional flexibility — an advantage of BRICS: China (100.0) and Russia (90.3) outperform France (66.7) and Italy (62.5). Social partnership — an advantage of the EU: Germany (100.0) significantly exceeds Russia (47.1).

Correlation analysis: $r(\text{LOF}, \text{ICIs}) = 0.850, p < 0.002$. Correlation $\text{FC} \leftrightarrow \text{LOF} = 0.729$ (below the multicollinearity threshold of 0.80), confirming that LOF measures an independent institutional dimension.

Table 3. Average values per block

Block	FC	DC	RS	FS	IF	LOF	ICI
EU	88.9	81.5	77.1	87.5	85.5	77.8	82.8
BRICS	54,2	69,6	64,3	69,9	50,2	68.2	61,8
Gap	34,7	11,9	12,8	17,6	35,3	9,6	21,0

LOF shows the smallest gap (9.6 points) — the labor markets of BRICS countries are closer to the EU level than for any other component. The largest gap is observed in IF (35.3) and FC (34.7).

Discussion

The results confirm all four research hypotheses. H1: LOF does not duplicate FC ($r = 0.729$); the extended model provides a more differentiated picture. H2: LOF is strongly correlated with ICIs ($r = 0.850, p < 0.002$). H3: the LOF gap (9.6) is minimal among the six components. H4: a 20% improvement in LOF yields an increase in the ICI of BRICS countries by 1.7–2.4 points; regression indicates a multiplier of 1.33.

Two models of the institutional structure of the labor market have been identified. European “organized flexibility” (flexicurity): strong social partnership, developed institutions of collective bargaining, moderate flexibility. The BRICS model of “unorganized flexibility”: high institutional flexibility, minimal restrictions on hiring and firing, but weak social partnership.

Practical recommendations: development of institutions of social partnership in BRICS countries (the experience of the German Mitbestimmung model); preservation of a competitive advantage in flexibility during the implementation of reforms; enhancement of labor mobility within integration associations.

Conclusion

The necessity of including the labor market as an independent element in M. Porter's model of competitive advantage was substantiated and quantitatively assessed. The proposed organizational-institutional labor factor (LOF) measures the institutional environment of the labor market and does not duplicate factor conditions ($r = 0.729$).

A comparative analysis of 10 BRICS and EU countries revealed the smallest discrepancy between the blocks precisely in the institutional characteristics of the labor market (9.6 points), indicating a significant competitive potential of the labor markets in the BRICS countries.

In the course of studying the activities of international economic blocs at Moscow International University, the necessity of including an element of national labor market competitiveness in M. Porter's 'diamond' model was substantiated, enabling a more precise calculation of the integral competitiveness index (ICI) for BRICS and EU countries.

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**MANAGEMENT INDICATORS AT CII ENTERPRISES
IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES:
SELECTION LOGIC AND METHODOLOGICAL JUSTIFICATION**

Kravtsov Alexey Yakovlevich

Postgraduate Student

Synergy University, Moscow, Russia

Scientific Advisor — Khabarov V. I.

Doctor of Economics, Professor

Abstract. *The article presents the methodological rationale and logic underlying the formation of a system of thirteen management performance indicators for the implementation of digital technologies at critical information infrastructure (CII) enterprises. The criterion for selecting indicators is substantiated: each must specifically capture the management-driven component of production losses, rather than the aggregate financial result. The source of each indicator is described — standard metrics from reliability theory and quality management, the HRA method, as well as proprietary constructs. The relationship of the system with the mechanism by which digital technologies influence management processes is demonstrated.*

Keywords: *CII; performance indicators; digital technologies; human factor; functional safety; managerial effect; operationalization.*

Relevance of the problem: when an industrial CII facility implements a new automation system, the standard question posed is: ‘To what extent have costs been reduced?’ However, it is equally important to consider another question: ‘To what extent has management improved?’ This distinction is fundamental. Financial metrics record the outcome but do not clarify whether the improvement resulted from the technology itself being more efficient or from management decisions becoming more precise and timely. Conventional financial instruments for evaluating the effectiveness of digitalization — such as return on investment, net present value, and cost-benefit analysis — do not fully reflect the managerial impact of implementing digital technologies, as some benefits “may not be realized immediately and may have an intangible nature” [1]. For CII facilities, this distinction holds direct practical significance. Losses resulting from suboptimal decisions in

goal-setting, planning, organization, motivation, and control — the share of defects, failures, and incidents caused by managerial decisions or personnel actions rather than physical processes or equipment wear — often exceed 50% of total losses [2]. It is precisely this component that decreases with improved management effectiveness and that digital transformation indicators must capture. Such indicators can subsequently serve as a foundation for the development of systems and methodologies aimed at making appropriate managerial decisions [3][9].

The objective of this article is to disclose the logic of selection and the methodological justification for a system comprising thirteen indicators applicable to measuring the managerial effect of digitalization in CII enterprises.

It can be posited that the sole managerial mechanism underlying the effect of digitalization is the reduction of variability in managerial decisions and personnel actions. Since the digital system restricts the range of possible operator actions — through algorithmization, warnings, digital prompts, automatic control of regulation compliance, and even by providing step-by-step procedural support and monitoring of operator actions. In hazardous situations, or in cases of incorrect instruction execution, a warning is issued and transition to the next step is permitted through validation of the completed action [4]. The decision-making experience undergoes a fundamental change: whereas previously it depended directly on individual experience, the system now establishes a defined corridor of permissible actions.

In turn, this mechanism generates three aspects that require specific indicators for evaluation:

- 1) Reduction of defects of managerial origin — when operational modes are set automatically or monitored in real time;
- 2) Reduction of management-induced failures and downtime — when maintenance shifts from reactive to predictive;
- 3) Reduction of personnel errors and decrease in erroneous actions — when algorithms constrain variability and improve compliance with regulatory procedures.

From this logic, three blocks of indicators directly derive: product quality, operational reliability, and functional safety.

Among the large number of indicators that can be included in the system, it is necessary to establish criteria for their consideration. In this study, it is proposed to apply three conditions simultaneously. An indicator should measure the management-induced component of a phenomenon, rather than its aggregate outcome; therefore, it is important to capture its managerial nature. Thus, the defect rate coefficient K_d

by itself does not distinguish between defects due to physical processes and defects caused by operator error. Therefore, it is necessary to supplement this indicator with the index I_{ud} , which accounts for the proportion of defects attributable

to management processes. Such an indicator is capable of reflecting changes in the management process induced by digital technologies. It is also important that the indicator sensitivity to digitalization be measured specifically in response to digital management technologies, rather than solely under the influence of market conditions, raw material prices, or other external factors. This condition must exclude financial aggregates and macro-indicators. The third indicator is operationalizability. The indicator must be measurable under actual conditions of an industrial facility without specialized scientific equipment — based on data that the enterprise already collects or can begin collecting through standard management instruments.

These thirteen indicators are heterogeneous in origin; seven are authorial constructs, and five are standard metrics already in use. And one is the author's aggregation of standard components. In this article, it is important to establish this distinction.

Table 1 — Management Process Performance Indicators: Source and Justification

№	Code	Status	Source	Managerial Content
1	BLOCK I QUALITY	Кд	Standard	GOST R ISO 9001; TQM. Total defectiveness — the initial basis for isolating the managerial component. [7]
2		Иуд	Author's	Operationalization of the 5 Why / 8D method. The share of defects attributable to managerial causes is a key sensitive indicator of the block.
3		Сб	Standard	Cost of Quality (Feigenbaum, Crosby). Monetary expression in rubles of losses due to defects.
4		Ккур	Author's	Normalized dynamics of the reduction in Kd relative to the baseline period. Digitization progress indicator.
5	BLOCK II RELIABILITY	λγ	Author's	Operationalization of Root Cause Analysis (RCA). Failure frequency attributed to managerial causes — an analogue of Iud for reliability.
6		Кг	Standard	GOST 27.002–2015, Clause 3.2.4. Managerially reinterpreted: an increase in Kg during digitalization is a consequence of the transition to predictive maintenance. [6]

7	BLOCK III FUNCTIONAL SECURITY	MTTR	Standard	GOST 27.002–2015; MIL-HDBK. MTTR reduction during digitalization is a consequence of accelerated diagnostics and standardization of restorative work. [6]
8		Kup	Author’s	Operationalization of RCA for downtime. The proportion of management-related downtimes is a target indicator of EAM/CMMS systems.
9		Iun	Authorial indicator (analog of OEE)	Prototype — OEE (Nakajima, 1988). Components have been reinterpreted: instead of technical efficiency — the management component.
10		Pop	Standard (HRA)	THERP Method: Swain & Guttman (NUREG/CR-1278, 1983); Reason J. (1990). Probability of erroneous action within the managerial procedure. [8]
11		Krcs	Author’s	Regulatory compliance as a managerial category. Proportion of procedures executed in compliance with regulation — an indicator of execution discipline.
12		Ksvr	Author’s	Timeliness of managerial decisions. Proportion of decisions made within the normative timeframe — an indicator of the temporal aspect of functional safety.
13	Ifb	Authorial convolution	Additive convolution (Saaty, 1980): $Ifb = \alpha_1(1-Pop) + \alpha_2Krc + \alpha_3Ksvr$. Integral index; Intervention threshold $Ifb < 0.70$.	

Legend: yellow background — authorial indicator; white — standard. Source: compiled by the author.

This article intentionally excludes metrics such as: Information security. Cybersecurity metrics (data protection, attack resilience) — as this constitutes an independent subject area with its own regulatory framework [5]. Such a system of indicators can be utilized as metrics for addressing functional safety as a managerial category: the ability of the management system to prevent erroneous actions by personnel. Financial indicators such as EBITDA, profitability, and unit production cost are influenced by numerous factors beyond management quality. Therefore, they are excluded based on the criterion of ‘sensitivity to digitalization’: reductions in unit cost may result from changes in raw material prices or the acquisition of more powerful equipment, rather than from improvements in managerial decisions. Metrics as neurocognitive indicators of personnel workload

possess theoretical interest, as they are challenging to operationalize in production environments without specialized equipment and fail to pass the third filter.

Conclusion

In this study, the proposed system of thirteen indicators is founded on three bases. *Logical*: each indicator records the management-driven component of losses, rather than the aggregate result. *Methodological*: seven proprietary indicators are derived through the operationalization of management requirements using standard tools (RCA, 5 Why, cause classifiers); five standard metrics are substantively reconsidered, but not mathematically; one is a proprietary aggregation. *Practical*: all thirteen indicators are measurable in real conditions without special equipment.

The system is intended for use in two contexts: as a tool for monitoring the performance of the digital transformation program at a specific CII facility, and as a criterial basis for evaluating the managerial effect of alternative digital initiatives.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ONLINE REPUTATION MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF MEDICAL ORGANIZATIONS IN RUSSIA AND OTHER COUNTRIES

Kanalina Yuliia Sergeevna

Postgraduate

*Scientific Research Institute of Healthcare Organization and Medical
Management, Department of Health of the City of Moscow,
Moscow, Russia*

Abstract. *This article provides a comparative analysis of reputation management mechanisms in state medical organizations in the Russian Federation and abroad, specifically focusing on Germany and France. The study aims to identify differences in organizational models of interaction with digital platforms. Based on a comparative institutional analysis, the key barriers to the implementation of relevant management solutions in the public sector of Russian healthcare have been identified. The development of information technologies, digitalization, and the implementation of telemedicine technologies and artificial intelligence within national healthcare systems create prospects for the emergence of new services and platforms facilitating interaction between patients and healthcare professionals. When selecting a provider of medical services, patients pay particular attention to the reputation of the medical organization or the individual physician. Thus, reputation in the digital environment becomes a key intangible asset influencing patient flow and the efficiency of hospital management. This article provides an analysis of technological platforms and managerial procedures for reputation management in the healthcare sector in the Russian Federation, Germany, and France. The article proposes mechanisms for adapting international experience to enhance the effectiveness of reputational risk management in government clinics in Russia.*

Keywords: *reputation management, digital platforms, healthcare management, strategic management, patient-centeredness.*

Introduction

The world's population is continuously growing. According to the United Nations (UN) forecast, the global population will increase to 9.7 billion by 2050 [1].

National healthcare systems face a number of challenges due to the ongoing rise in costs associated with delivering medical care to the population. Moreover, in some countries, expenditures are increasing at a rate exceeding the pace of economic growth [2]. Global challenges faced by life and health protection systems — associated with demographic aging, the spread of infectious diseases, and shortages of qualified personnel and resources — are pertinent to countries with developed healthcare systems. Healthcare chronically suffers from a shortage of resources (doctors, nurses, availability of diagnostic services, etc.) [3].

Digital transformation in healthcare represents a global trend that imposes new requirements on management systems within medical organizations. According to the WHO (World Health Organization) global digital health strategy for 2020–2025, information technologies are becoming one of the key tools for ensuring accessibility and the high-quality evaluation of healthcare services [4]. Currently, approximately 80% of the population in developed countries possess modern smartphones and actively use them to select medical clinics when seeking healthcare services.

The research problem stems from the insufficient elaboration of issues concerning the comparative analysis of management mechanisms for handling online reputation specifically within the public sector. Existing studies frequently concentrate on private clinics or on the technical aspects of digitalization, thereby neglecting organizational and managerial models [5].

The scholarly work by L. S. Salnikova in the field of reputation management emphasizes the transformation of business reputation into a critical intangible asset in the context of the digital economy [6]. The public healthcare sector in the Russian Federation is characterized by a high degree of regulation, which creates specific conditions for reputation management. At the same time, countries of the European Union demonstrate alternative approaches, where digital platforms are integrated into the service quality management system [7].

The aim of this article is to identify key differences in the management mechanisms of online reputation formation in the Russian Federation and other countries, and to determine the potential for applying foreign experience to Russian healthcare institutions. The scientific novelty consists in the approach proposed by the author to the comparative analysis of not only technological platforms but also procedures for managing reputational risks.

Research methods

This study is based on the method of comparative institutional analysis, which enables identification of differences in the rules and norms regulating managerial activities across different national healthcare systems. The object of the study was the reputation management systems of medical organizations. The subject matter concerns management mechanisms and digital platforms in the Russian Federation

and other countries (using the examples of France and Germany). The following tools were utilized for data collection and processing:

Content analysis of digital platforms. The functional features and moderation policies of the main aggregators in Russia ('ProDoctors', 'NaPopravku'), as well as in Germany and France ('Doctolib', 'KelDoc'), were analyzed.

Analysis of the regulatory framework. Administrative and regulatory restrictions influencing management were examined (Federal Law No. 323-FZ dated November 21, 2011, "On the Fundamentals of Health Protection of Citizens in the Russian Federation" [8] and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which establishes a system of fully independent supervisory authorities responsible for monitoring and ensuring compliance with legislative requirements [9]).

A limitation of this research is its focus on the public sector, as private clinics may employ different business models for reputation management. The empirical foundation comprised open-access data from the period 2020–2023 [10].

Research findings

The comparative analysis revealed significant differences in the regulatory environment and management practices.

Regulatory environment and data protection.

In European Union countries, the GDPR regulation provides a high level of protection for patients' personal data, which paradoxically facilitates the publication of verified reviews. Platforms must verify users, but the data is anonymized for the public. In the Russian Federation, the development of the electronic service 'My Health' enables patient identification via a personal account on the Unified State Services Portal; however, commercial aggregators often face issues with fake reviews due to less stringent verification requirements [11].

A more detailed examination of management mechanisms reveals the key approaches to reputation management in medical organizations (Figure 1).

Figure 1 — Key approaches to reputation management in medical organizations. Compiled by the author

A more detailed consideration of the European model reveals that in practice its implementation consists of doctors and clinic administration independently

stimulating patients to leave reviews following their appointments. A regulated system for responding to negative feedback is in place. In certain countries (for example, Germany), platform ratings indirectly affect patient distribution within the mandatory insurance system [12].

Regarding domestic practice, the Russian model is especially manifested in the state hospitals of the Russian Federation. Concerning responses to complaints, they frequently occur under the influence of regulatory authorities (Roszdravnadzor, Ministry of Health, Moscow Department of Health). Staff motivation to engage in online reputation management is low due to the lack of corresponding key performance indicators (KPIs) in job descriptions [13].

Technological capabilities and integration.

In the EU, digital platforms commonly act as comprehensive CRM systems for clinics, integrated with appointment calendars and electronic medical records. For example, the platform 'Doctolib' facilitates reputation management through the convenience of scheduling appointments. In Russia, platforms more often function as directories. Integration with unified state information systems is currently in the implementation phase, which complicates the automation of feedback collection.

The impact on patient flow.

According to research data, approximately 70% of patients in the EU select a physician based on online ratings [14]. In the Russian Federation, this figure is increasing, but currently stands at about 50%: 48% of Russians review feedback about a physician on the internet and social media before scheduling an appointment. Only 22% of respondents are willing to schedule an appointment with a physician without any prior knowledge about them [15].

The business reputation of medical organizations.

A particularly significant aspect is the issue of the professional reputation of medical organizations. Currently, the institution of medical mediation in Russian practice is still in its developmental stage. Medical organizations often conduct independent monitoring of negative reviews and provide responses to them. At the same time, the experience of the USA and European countries clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of medical mediation, significantly reducing the frequency of recourse to the judicial system in dispute resolution [16]. In this regard, it is advisable to adopt a strategic course aimed at developing medical mediation as an institution interacting with all interested parties. Figure 2 reflects the positive aspects of the development of this institution for a medical organization.

In addition to the figure, it should be noted that mandatory user verification must be mandated in practice when posting a review. An optimal option may be to link the profile to the Gosuslugi portal.

It should also be noted that the development of the institution of medical mediation may require funding for educational institutions specializing in training

professionals with expertise in both medicine and law. This raises the question of designating the development of this institution as a state strategic interest. Figure 3 presents a systemic interpretation of the operation of medical mediation.

Figure 2 — Positive aspects of the development of the institution of medical mediation in Russia. Compiled by the author

Figure 3 — Systemic interpretation of the functioning of medical mediation. Compiled by the author

In addition to the figure, it should be noted that, to strengthen oversight of the institution of medical mediation, the establishment of a supervisory body with a governmental foundation appears advisable. One possible option is the ‘State Union of Medical Mediators.’ It should also be noted that the mediator formalizes the entire set of legal documents with the patient, which, in the event of a subsequent

publication of a negative review, despite the compensations provided, could serve as official sources for ensuing discussions.

It is also important to emphasize that the institution of medical mediators will require extensive public awareness campaigns to ensure maximum notification of the population. It is advisable to display advertisements on monitors in the waiting areas of polyclinics, hospitals, and multifunctional centers. Furthermore, it is essential to incorporate a dedicated section on government portals such as Gosuslugi and Mos.ru, allowing direct appeals to medical mediators.

Discussion and Conclusion

The results obtained permit the interpretation of the identified differences through the prism of managerial efficiency. Foreign experience demonstrates that online reputation should not function as a separate role of the press office, but rather as an integral component of the healthcare quality management system. In Russian state hospitals, this mechanism remains insufficiently developed due to bureaucratic barriers, the lack of an integrated system linking portals with unified state information systems, and the absence of clear verification processes.

To enhance the management system in Russian state medical organizations, it is proposed to adapt the following mechanisms:

1. Implementation of regulations for managing digital reviews. It is imperative to develop job descriptions for administrative personnel and the press office, encompassing platform monitoring and protocols for responding to negative feedback. This aligns with personnel management principles, whereby precise regulation enhances work efficiency [17].

2. Integration of reputation metrics into the KPI system. The influence of the online rating should be taken into account when incentivizing department employees and their supervisors. This will establish an economic incentive to enhance service quality.

3. The utilization of data analysis technologies. The implementation of artificial intelligence-based tools for sentiment analysis of reviews enables a shift from manual to automated management, which corresponds to trends in high-performance medicine [18].

4. The active development of the institution of medical mediation, which minimizes legal disputes related to Article 152 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation [19] (protection of honor, dignity, and business reputation), serves to prevent instances of unfair competition and reduce the occurrence of negative health consequences for patients.

5. To ensure maximum public awareness of the institution of medical mediators, it is advisable to implement large-scale social advertising campaigns utilizing platforms such as medical institutions, government service portals, and multifunctional centers.

In conclusion, it can be asserted that reputation management in public clinics within the Russian Federation necessitates a shift from formal monitoring toward proactive strategic management. Digital reputation is increasingly becoming

a feedback mechanism enabling real-time adjustments to managerial decisions. The adaptation of leading global practices is feasible when considering the specifics of national legislation and the imperative of data protection. A promising direction for further research involves examining the impact of artificial intelligence algorithms on the moderation of medical reviews and their role in mitigating reputational crises.

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STRATEGIC PLANNING DOCUMENTS OF ARCTIC STATES

Gordienko Alexey Nikolaevich

Federal Research Center “Kola Science Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences”,

Apatity, Murmansk Region, Russia

Abstract. *A brief overview of the main strategic national documents of countries that have established their geopolitical ambitions in the Arctic is given, and a brief analysis of the key directions of these documents is conducted, taking into account the institutional mechanisms of implementation.*

Using the example of legal data from 2022–2026, a transformation of approaches has been identified, moving dynamically from open international cooperation to a protected national agenda.

The originality of the research is characterized by the comparison of legal institutional mechanisms and the relevance of the data according to primary sources. These materials may be of interest for scientific forecasting of the development of international relations in the Arctic at the present stage and in the short term.

Keywords: *Arctic region, strategic planning, national strategies, institutional mechanisms, international cooperation, geopolitics*

Introduction

The Arctic macroregion, in the context of geopolitical transformation and natural-climatic changes, is gaining special geostrategic significance for the states that comprise it. All 8 states of this macroregion have their strategic planning documents that enshrine the principles and directions of nationally oriented policies of the governments of these countries.

According to the classification of the Arctic Council [4], Arctic states are those countries that have parts of their territory located beyond the Arctic Circle, that is, north of the conventional boundary at 66°33'44" north of the equator: the Kingdom of Denmark (considering Greenland), Iceland, Canada, the Kingdom of Norway, the Russian Federation, the United States of America, the Republic of Finland, and the Kingdom of Sweden. At the same time, the Arctic sector of the United States of America is a part of the territory of Alaska, separate from the main territory of the country. Iceland can only be conditionally called an

Arctic state, as it does not have a single square meter north of the Arctic Circle (but claims a section of the continental shelf extending into the Arctic zone). Iceland can only be conditionally called an Arctic state, since it does not have a single square meter north of the Arctic Circle (but claims an area of the continental shelf that extends into the Arctic zone). Denmark is considered part of the Arctic states only if Greenland is included in its territory: losing control over this autonomous territory would lead to Denmark being pushed out of the ‘Arctic club.’ Finland and Sweden have no access to the seas of the Arctic Ocean and do not build Arctic coastal infrastructure.

Despite the existence of work on individual national strategies, their analysis, based on a comparison of the strategic legal acts of all major players in the Arctic ‘field,’ is absent. In this regard, a study using a verified practical methodology [1] taking into account the latest events of 2022–2026, it remains relevant. Most of the available reviews are based on data from 2018–2022 [2], [3] which requires their rethinking and adjustment in the context of the radical change of the geopolitical situation after 2022.

The main sources and objects of the study are documents of strategic planning adopted in national legal regimes regarding the Arctic region. There are various categories of legal acts in the official legislation of Arctic states: national Arctic strategies, polar strategies, foreign policy concepts with an Arctic section, programmatic statements, and other doctrinal documents containing an Arctic component. The greatest attention in strategic documents is given to provisions in the field of defense and security, up to the actions of the armed forces in the Arctic. The task of this brief study is to provide a short overview of the main strategic documents, highlighting the strategic characteristics that either unite or differentiate these countries.

The main strategic documents of the Arctic states

A common factor of all strategic documents of Arctic states is a deterrent adaptation to the processes of geopolitical tension between Arctic powers and other external players seeking to gain the maximum possible access to Arctic natural resources, by any means, including military, to establish a priority position in the Arctic.

As the five main countries with direct access to the Arctic Ocean (Russia, Canada, Denmark, Norway, and the United States), they exercise the right to develop natural resources within their maritime zones of economic influence. The strategic tasks in this context are to achieve maximum economic return, energy independence, and sustainable development of national sections of the northern territories. The main strategic documents of the Arctic states (currently in force) are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Main strategic documents of Arctic states

State	Document	Adoption Period
Kingdom of Denmark (including Greenland)	Kingdom of Denmark Strategy for the Arctic [5]	2011, 2022
Iceland	Iceland's Policy on Matters Concerning the Arctic Region [6]	2021, 2024
Canada	Canada's Arctic and Northern Policy Framework [7]	2019
	Our North Strong and Free: a Renewed Vision for Canada's Defence [8]; Defense Policy [9]	2024
Kingdom of Norway	The Norwegian Government's Arctic Policy [10]	2017, 2020, 2021
Russian Federation	Fundamentals of the State Policy of the Russian Federation in the Arctic for the period up to 2035 [11]	2008, 2020
	Strategy for the Development of the Arctic Zone of the Russian Federation and Ensuring National Security up to 2035 [12]	
United States of America	National Strategy for the Arctic Region [13]; National Defense Strategy	2013, 2019, 2022, 2024
Kingdom of Sweden	Sweden's Strategy for the Arctic Region [14]	2020, 2025
Republic of Finland	Finland's strategy regarding Arctic policy [finl. Suomen arktisen politiikan strategia, swed. Finlands nya arktiska strategi] [15]	2021

The policy of Arctic states, like all of them — members of the North Atlantic Military Alliance (except for the Russian Federation), is integrated and inseparable from NATO's collective policy [16]. At the same time, the development of a strategic document is only the first stage in shaping the state's Arctic policy. The success of its implementation directly depends on the presence of effective coordination mechanisms between government bodies, the scientific support sector, and business structures interested in the development of industry in the Arctic. An analysis of the institutional architecture allows not only to identify the formal existence of a strategic act but also to assess the maturity of national approaches to managing Arctic issues.

Based on numerous data and taking into account the analysis previously conducted by specialists [17], [18] the following periodization of the development of Arctic strategies is proposed:

1st initial stage (2008–2013): formation of the first national strategies, focus on international cooperation, recognition of the exclusive role of the states bordering the Arctic Ocean (Ilulissat Declaration 2008) [19];

2st initial stage — Deepening (2014–2018): the dissemination of experience in strategic planning activities in the Arctic to the development of strategies of non-Arctic states, distributed by political bloc's institutionalization of observer positions in the Arctic Council, emphasis on scientific cooperation in the Arctic;

3rd transformational stage (2019–2024): 'securitization' of the Arctic agenda, revision of strategies in the context of a geopolitical crisis, emergence of new radical documents in Arctic countries (USA, Canada, 2024), presentation of the Arctic agenda in strategic defense-related documents.

A comparative analysis of the key positions of the aforementioned documents shows the current focus of the Arctic agenda: defense and security, economic interests (primarily the development and extraction of mineral resources), scientific cooperation, as well as ecological balance. The common tasks in the documents of the USA and Canada regarding ensuring sovereignty in the Arctic include the defense of the Northwest Passage, investments in strengthening critical northern infrastructure, and the economic development of the macro-region. In the Arctic foreign policy concept, a strategy is proposed for Canada taking into account the change of political forces in the USA and considering possible changes in American policy in the Arctic direction [20].

Security issues imply a transformation of approaches from the stable state [constans condicio] of military forces and means toward strengthening the power bloc in the Arctic with these means. This dynamic is most clearly seen in the strategic documents of Sweden and Finland: from neutral rhetoric to an emphasis on military tasks in the context of NATO's Arctic policy and in connection with the country's accession to NATO.

Who is called to govern in the Arctic territories?

Based on the study of the structures of state organization and administration, four types of institutional models are distinguished, based on the composition of national systems of state bodies and administration. Their distribution for Arctic states is presented as follows.

The consistent buildup of the military component in the Arctic is openly declared by the United States: strategic ambitions are reflected in strategic documents and supported by unprecedented military and infrastructure programs. The beginning of 2026 is marked by the publication of the new U. S. National Defense Strategy [21], in which the Arctic took one of the central places.

Table 2. Distribution of institutional models for Arctic states based on the structures of state organization and governance

State	Type of institutional models	The main coordinating bodies of power and administration
Kingdom of Denmark (including Greenland)	Only through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (B)	Arctic Affairs Bureau of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark (dat. Büro für Arktis Udenrigsministeriet)
Iceland	Only through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (B)	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Iceland (isl. Utanríkisráðuneytið)
Canada	Target agency (agencies) (A)	Crown–Indigenous Relations and Northern Affairs Canada, Global Affairs Canada
Kingdom of Norway	Interdepartmental (C)	Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Climate and Environment
Russian Federation	Interdepartmental (C)	State Commission on Arctic Development Issues; Commission of the State Council of the Russian Federation on the direction «Northern Sea Route and the Arctic»; Council for the Protection of the National Interests of the Russian Federation in the Arctic (as part of the Maritime Collegium of the Russian Federation); Ministry for the Development of the Russian Far East and Arctic
United States of America	Interdepartmental (C)	Arctic Working Group of U. S. National Security Council (NSC)
Kingdom of Sweden	Only through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (B)	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Sweden (Sveriges utrikesministerium) Secretariat of Polar Research (Sekretariatet för polarforskning)
Republic of Finland	Only through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (B)	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Finland (Suomen ulkoministeriö)

Type distribution: A — target department (12.5%); B — coordination through the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (50%); C — interdepartmental model (37.5%). D — science-policy interface (not yet presented).

A key organizational change in the US Arctic strategy was the revision of military responsibility zones: since May 2025, the Unified Command Plan has provided for the transfer of Greenland from the area of responsibility of the European Command (EUCOM) to the jurisdiction of the United States Northern Command (NORTHCOM) [22]. Now the defense of Greenland by the United States is considered within the same strategic context as the defense of the continental United States, Canada, and Alaska, which strengthens the role of the North American Aerospace Defense Command (NORAD).

Strategic documents of the European northern countries responded by shifting the competence of managing Arctic relations with Russia onto the United States, limiting themselves to domestic policy (with the possible exception of Norway, which asserts itself as a sovereign regulator of all legal relations regarding the Svalbard archipelago, which has a key geographical position for controlling the North Atlantic and the actions of the Russian Northern Fleet based on the Kola Peninsula) [23].

Priority attention to defense in Canada's strategic documents is justified as deterring threats in the Arctic, significant for the North American continent as a whole, and this position is shared by the United States [24].

In modern strategic documents of the Russian Federation, unlike their previous editions, the development of national security infrastructure is declared in opposition to the decisions and actions of other Arctic states, and socio-economic development projects in one way or another correspond with the defense agenda.

General goals are present in the Arctic strategy (for example, for Denmark, Norway, Sweden, and Finland), and include such goals as strengthening the country's authority in the Arctic, defense and security, trade interests, environmental protection, the status of northern regions, international cooperation in the Arctic, the development and promotion of scientific research in the Arctic, as well as the preservation of the traditional activities of indigenous peoples. Finland's practical territorial policy in the Arctic is limited to the development of the area of Lapland, primarily located in the Arctic zone. This is confirmed by the active application of the Regional Development Act and the implementation of the European Union's regional and structural policy. [25], which specifies the mechanisms for supporting northern territories. Based on the Arctic strategy and this law, provincial programs and plans are adopted, which are initiated by consortia of municipal authorities for a period of four years.

Based on the economic blocks of the strategies presented, transport corridors are becoming increasingly important each year for countries with the largest Arctic territories. For Russia, these are the Northern Sea Route (NSR) and the Trans-Arctic Transport Corridor (TTC). The latter is a strategic infrastructure project of Russia aimed at creating a unified system of routes connecting the regions of

Siberia, the Urals, and the Far East with the ports of the NSR and access to global trade routes.

The creation of the TTC is a factor both in Russia's presence in global inter-state economic processes and in the development of its own strategic interests in the accelerated development of optimally located near-Arctic territories, comfortable for organizing efficient logistics and establishing new transcontinental transport corridors. [26]. In the context of strategic documents, there is a sufficient number of projects for the development of meridional and latitudinal directions of the country's transport highways, including those endorsed by the instructions of the Head of State, among which are the projects of the Northern Latitudinal Route [27], [28], [29].

Regarding Canada — the Canadian Northern Corridor, a concept proposed in 2016 by a team from the University of Calgary, it involves developing a route approximately 7,000 km long, comprising roads, railways, pipelines, power and communication networks, traversing the northern part of Canada and connecting to Arctic maritime routes. Additionally, the Arctic Corridors Research Project is considered strategic — the development of a network of local Arctic maritime transport corridors with low environmental impact.

The strategic documents of all Arctic states mentioned above contain provisions declaring relations with the indigenous peoples residing in their traditional settlement areas. At the same time, they establish the legal basis for guarantees of the unique socio-economic and cultural development of small indigenous peoples, but practical actions in this area are mostly carried out through special legislation and even by international societies with special consultative status at the UN, such as the documents of the Inuit Circumpolar Council (ICC), [grenl.: Inuit Issittormiut Siunnersuisooqatigiiffiat] [30] and the Saami Council, which are normative-political, but not governmental. Of course, Russia should be excluded from the list of such countries, where a set of practical measures of state support for the indigenous peoples of the Arctic is established and regulated by a federal law act [31].

Priority and universal projects, convenient for each country, include scientific cooperation, which ensures the development of all sectors of life in the Arctic. Among the international scientific community, there is no doubt about the thesis that before extensively exploring and developing the Arctic, it must be thoroughly studied. In Russia, this is illustrated by the fact that under the State Commission on Arctic Development, a Scientific Arctic Council has been formed, and more than 500 organizations in 50 regions conduct scientific research on Arctic-related topics (of which only 10 constitute the Arctic zone of the Russian Federation).

The possibility of scientific activity (including, at the present stage, the establishment of permanent scientific facilities) is used by Arctic states to involve

non-Arctic ones, under the aura of dominant strategic declarations. It is precisely through scientific and scientific-technical participation in the Arctic circle of states that Greece [32], Italy [33], Poland [34] and Switzerland [35] have established themselves. At the same time, Arctic and other countries, even those that do not have an Arctic segment of their territory at all, in their documents today do not conceal their ambitions to participate in the development of strategic natural resources on the Arctic shelf [36], [37].

A modern driver of strategic interest in the Arctic region is, to a significant extent, the climate agenda. [38]. The common denominator for all Arctic strategies is the protection of fragile natural systems. At the same time, in all Arctic countries, with the exception of Russia, there are no separate legislative acts aimed at supporting territories located in special climatic zones. The objects of scientific assessment are the rapid climate change, the entire Arctic ecosystem, the reduction of animal populations in the Arctic zone, the settlement of Arctic territories, and the introduction of animals and plants from warmer regions into the waters. It is considered important to identify trends, preserve, and develop the self-restoration of the Arctic ecosystem, taking into account cross-border pollution of its coastal territories and the waters of the Arctic seas of the Arctic Ocean.

In addition, within the framework of the adaptation program to the processes of global warming, there is a general direction of minimizing the consequences of permafrost (eternal frost) degradation. It is positioned as strategically significant in the scientific and scientific-technical fields, for the industrial sector and infrastructural development in the Russian Federation, Canada, the Scandinavian countries, as well as in a number of non-Arctic states represented in the Arctic Council as observers.

Conclusion

The following conclusions can be noted.

1) The proposed typology requires further empirical research on the correlation between the type of model and the degree of implementation of the objectives stated in the strategies of Arctic states.

2) A comparison of the provisions of strategic documents of the countries of the Arctic macroregion makes it possible to track unifying trends and tendencies of integration of Arctic states, to understand: in which areas and which countries have the opportunity to activate their activities, combine their forces and resources, or jointly adhere to neutrality. For clarity, this can be presented in the form of an indicator table (Table 3).

In this regard, the relevance of studies that include an analysis of the implementation of Arctic strategies (gap between rhetoric and action) in their updated versions, and the strategies of states joining as observers of the Arctic Council, remains.

Table 3. Unifying tendencies and trends of integration of Arctic states based on strategic planning documents

Indicator \ State	State							
	Denmark (incl. Greenland)	Iceland	Canada	Norway	Russia	USA	Sweden	Finland
Participation in military blocs operating in the Arctic	+	+	+	+		+	+	+
Defense and security, deployment of armed forces in the Arctic	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Protection of the population and territories in emergencies	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Involvement of non-Arctic states			+	+	+	+		
Comprehensive development of mineral resources	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Mineral extraction on the shelf	+	+	+	+	+	+		
Development of Arctic port infrastructure	+	+	+	+	+	+		
Development of infrastructure and logistics in remote areas of the Arctic	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Global transport projects			+		+	+		
Conducting active scientific activity in the Arctic	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Climate agenda	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Environmental agenda	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Development of agriculture in Arctic territories				+		+	+	+
Minimization of the consequences of permafrost (eternal) degradation	+		+	+	+	+		+
Regulation of issues of indigenous small-numbered peoples living in the Arctic	+		+	+	+	+	+	+

Correlation analysis makes it possible to track the relationship between the type of institutional model and the degree of achievement of strategic interests. The prospects for applying the declared strategic principles and ambitions of Arctic states provide an understanding of the potential for organizing activities in Antarctica. [39].

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PROBLEMS WITH USING THE DIGITAL RUBLE IN FOREIGN TRADE TRANSACTIONS

Duskaeva Milena Rinatovna

Student

Rostov State University of Economics (RINH),

Rostov-on-Don, Russia

Scientific Advisor — Alimova Olga Viktorovna

Associate Professor

Rostov State University of Economics (RINH),

Rostov-on-Don, Russia

Abstract: *The article explores the legal and practical challenges of using the digital ruble as a means of payment for foreign trade contracts. It analyzes the conflict between the national regime of the digital ruble platform and the principles of cross-border capital flows, as well as the issues of jurisdictional immunity and currency control. Special attention is given to the uncertainty surrounding the legal nature of the digital ruble in the context of international private law, the technological barriers of a centralized platform, and the lack of unified international agreements. The author substantiates the need to harmonize approaches within the framework of interstate associations (EAEU, BRICS) for the integration of central bank digital currencies into foreign trade turnover.*

Keywords: *digital ruble, foreign trade activity, international settlements, CBDC, currency law, cross-border payments, Bank of Russia, central bank digital currency.*

The introduction of a digital ruble into civil circulation, the legal regime of which was enshrined in Federal Law of July 24, 2023 No. 340-FZ “On Amendments to Certain Legislative Acts of the Russian Federation,” marks a new stage in the development of the national payment system, but its extrapolation to the sphere of international settlements is associated with a number of intractable collisions [1]. First of all, the problem of using the digital ruble in foreign trade rests on its unique legal nature, combining signs of non-cash funds and utilitarian digital rights, which creates uncertainty in the choice of applicable law and the status of obligations to foreign counterparties [12]. From the point of view of

private international law, the key obstacle is the territorial binding of the digital ruble platform: since the operator is the Bank of Russia, and all records on the movement of funds are stored exclusively in its infrastructure, there is a risk of recognizing such assets as under the sovereign control of the issuing state, which contradicts the principle of extraterritoriality of commercial transactions [11]. Moreover, the current currency legislation, regulated by the Federal Law “On Currency Regulation and Currency Control,” does not yet contain direct indications of the possibility of qualifying the digital ruble as a payment currency under foreign trade contracts, which creates a legal vacuum for residents seeking to use the new tool for settlements with non-residents [2].

Additional complexity is introduced by the technological architecture of the digital ruble, based on the principle of centralized administration, which contradicts the decentralized essence of cross-border trade, built on trust in independent financial intermediaries [12]. Unlike cryptocurrencies, where the validation of transactions is distributed, the digital ruble requires opening a wallet directly on the platform of the Central Bank of the Russian Federation, which for a foreign buyer or seller means the need to obey Russian identification procedures and, potentially, disclosure of information subject to national laws on the protection of personal data (for example, GDPR in Europe) [13]. This circumstance can provoke a conflict of public order, in which the fulfillment of obligations in digital rubles will be impossible for the counterparty due to the ban on data transfer in jurisdictions that do not provide an adequate level of information protection. In addition to jurisdictional conflicts, the issue of currency risks and instability of law enforcement practice is acute: despite the fact that the digital ruble is nominated in the legal monetary unit of the Russian Federation, its use in foreign trade transactions requires separate coordination of currency clauses and dispute resolution mechanisms, since arbitration courts have not yet formed a uniform approach to the qualification of loss of access to a digital wallet or technical failures during cross-border transfer [11].

It is important to note that attempts to integrate the digital ruble into international settlements are faced with the absence of unified international treaties similar to those governing traditional bank transfers (for example, the Geneva Conventions on bills of exchange or the UNCITRAL model rules) [12]. Currently, the interaction of CBDC platforms (digital currencies of central banks) of different countries is at the stage of conceptual pilot projects, and the Russian legal system is forced to adapt unilateral mechanisms, which increases transaction costs for foreign economic activity participants due to the need to include detailed conditions on the applicable law and the procedure for settling losses in case of platform failures [2]. The problem of ensuring public order and national security interests cannot be ignored either: expanding the perimeter of the use of the digital ruble outside the Russian Federation automatically expands the area of responsibility of the Bank of Russia as

an operator, entrusting it with unusual functions of monitoring cross-border flows, which were traditionally performed by the system of correspondent accounts of commercial banks. As a result, the beneficiaries of the introduction of the digital ruble in foreign trade settlements can be only limited jurisdictions included in integrated currency unions (for example, within the EAEU), where harmonization of financial legislation has been achieved, while for settlements with counterparties from “third countries” the use of the new instrument will remain exotic rather than a real alternative to the dollar or the euro [6].

Analysis of the latest changes in legislation, which come into force on September 1, 2026, only confirms this thesis. Federal Law No. 23.07.2025, dated 248-FZ, amending certain legislative acts, as well as accompanying Bank of Russia regulations, is aimed solely at the accelerated development of the internal circulation of the digital ruble [4]. The legislator establishes the obligation to use a universal payment code for transfers of digital rubles by individuals in favor of legal entities, individual entrepreneurs and persons engaged in private practice, and also imposes an obligation on platform participants to provide such an opportunity [5]. At the same time, neither this Federal Law nor the Bank of Russia by-laws, including Regulation No. 03.08.2023 of 820-P, as amended, contain provisions governing the cross-border transfer of digital rubles or interaction with foreign payment systems. Thus, legal regulation purposefully preserves the digital ruble as a purely intranational payment instrument, without creating a regulatory framework for its use in foreign economic activity.

This circumstance fundamentally changes the vector of research: if earlier it was possible to talk about the presence of a legal vacuum and uncertainty, then from September 1, 2026, a conscious legislative policy arises that excludes the digital ruble from the sphere of cross-border settlements. The introduction of the obligation for credit institutions to provide operations using a universal payment code is aimed at building a closed national payment ecosystem, where the interests of currency control and public order dominate the needs of foreign trade turnover. This approach, being justified from the point of view of financial security and sovereignty, actually neutralizes the prospects for using the digital ruble as a means of international settlements in the foreseeable future. Consequently, the key problem lies not only in the absence of international agreements, but also in the absence of a national legal framework that allows cross-border circulation of digital currency, which makes earlier assumptions about its potential use in foreign economic activity premature.

Summing up, it should be stated that the updated legislation on the digital ruble, which will enter into force on September 1, 2026, has created a full-fledged legal basis for its circulation, however, this legal framework is designed in such a way that it focuses the use of the digital ruble exclusively on intranational payment turnover [7–13].

An analysis of new regulatory requirements, including the introduction of a universal payment code and the mandatory use of it when transferring individuals in favor of legal entities and persons engaged in private practice [5], shows that the legislator at this stage solved the problem of forced implementation of the digital ruble in internal settlements. There are no mechanisms for the cross-border use of digital currency, as well as the procedure for interaction with foreign payment systems, in the current version of the regulatory framework.

Thus, we can conclude that the obligation to use the digital ruble, established by current legislation, currently applies only to the sphere of internal settlements. For the full integration of the digital ruble into foreign economic activity, the next stage of legislative work is required, which should be aimed at amending the currency legislation and developing mechanisms for cross-platform interaction with the digital currencies of the central banks of partner countries, primarily within the EAEU and BRICS. Consequently, overcoming the identified problems is possible only by supplementing national legislation with special norms on the cross-border circulation of the digital ruble and the subsequent unification of standards at the international level.

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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ANXIETY AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN YOUNGER AND OLDER ADOLESCENTS

Kiseleva Ekaterina Alexandrovna

*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Russian State University for the Humanities,
Moscow, Russia*

Malyantovich Kristina Georgievna

*Russian State University for the Humanities,
Moscow, Russia*

Abstract. *Contemporary adolescents develop today in conditions of uncertainty and constant change in the modern world, which contributes to an increased level of anxiety. The transition to middle and senior grades, examinations, and the necessity of choosing a profession — all of these become stress factors for the modern adolescent. This occurs against the backdrop of psychophysiological changes and transformations in interpersonal relationships, which make adolescents more vulnerable: it is during adolescence that anxiety is especially pronounced and becomes a stable personality trait. In this regard, the study of types of anxiety in adolescents and the causes of their occurrence in the modern world is becoming increasingly relevant. This article presents the results of a study on the relationship between the level of emotional intelligence, its components, and various types of anxiety among younger and older adolescents.*

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, state anxiety, personal anxiety, school anxiety, interpersonal anxiety, self-esteem anxiety, magical anxiety, adolescents, the relationship between emotional intelligence and anxiety levels.*

Anxiety is one of the most significant issues in the modern world, as ongoing socio-economic, political, and technological changes contribute to the emergence of feelings of unease, worry, and unexplainable concerns about the future among individuals. In the psychological dictionary, anxiety is defined as ‘an individual psychological characteristic manifested by a person’s predisposition to frequent and intense experiences of anxiety states, as well as a low threshold for their occurrence’ [Great Psychological Dictionary 2002, p. 500].

The concept of anxiety was introduced into psychology by S. Freud. He described it as a reaction to an unknown threat [Prikhojan 2000] and noted that in such cases, situations associated with feelings of helplessness from the past are repeatedly imagined by the individual. Horney also noted that anxiety manifests as an excessive reaction to a threat, which may be imaginary [Zavorueva 2007, pp. 101–111].

Ch. Spielberger proposed distinguishing the concept of “anxiety” from that of “anxiousness.” The former, in his view, is an emotional state characterized by tension and worry, which arises in response to the occurrence of a situation that may pose a threat. He defined anxiousness as a stable personality trait [Spielberger 2008, pp. 85–99]. This classification is frequently utilized by psychologists at present.

According to A. M. Prikhozhans argue that a normal level of anxiety is necessary — it facilitates adaptation to reality [Miklyeva, Rummyantseva 2004]. However, heightened anxiety may exert a negative disorganizing influence on an individual’s activity and perception of the world. Spielberger noted that an individual with pronounced anxiety tends to perceive danger in the surrounding environment more readily than an individual with a low level of anxiety. Individuals with elevated anxiety are more susceptible to the effects of stress [Spielberger 2008, pp. 85–99].

The negative impact of elevated anxiety is particularly pronounced among adolescents: they experience reduced self-esteem [Mazur 2019, pp. 237–239] and academic achievement [Dmitrieva, Evdokarova, Popova 2019, pp. 104–106], encounter greater difficulties with social adaptation [Khabiev 2020, pp. 170–179], are more vulnerable to bullying [Kalinkina, Kamrakova, Erykalova 2023, pp. 420–422], and are classified as at risk for the development of deviant behaviors and emotional personality disorders [Romanenko 2019, pp. 619–697]. It is precisely during adolescence, when self-awareness and one’s attitude toward oneself are formed, that anxiety becomes established as a stable construct [Prikhojan 2000]. Lebedinsky emphasizes that anxiety becomes particularly pronounced during this period [Romanenko 2019, pp. 619–697]. Therefore, it is essential to investigate factors that may contribute to reducing its level among adolescents.

Many researchers note a close relationship between the development of anxiety and the emotional domain. For example, K. Izard stated that anxiety is a complex syndrome, comprising fear as the predominant emotion, as well as the interactions of fear with basic emotions, notably anger, guilt, shame, suffering, and interest [Izard 2008, pp. 108–123]. A. M. Prikhodjan indicated that the emotional aspect predominates within this complex psychological entity. Accordingly, we hypothesized that there may be a relationship between anxiety and the level of emotional intelligence.

The concept of emotional intelligence (hereinafter — EI) is relatively new, and to date, there is no unified definition of it. The study of this construct has been conducted by P. Salovey, J. Mayer, R. Bar-On, D. Goleman, G. G. Garskova, I. N. Andreeva,

E. P. Ilyin, D. V. Lyusin, E. A. Sergienko, among others. P. P. Salovey and J. Mayer, in defining EI, focused on human cognitive abilities, R. Bar-On, in contrast, included exclusively personal characteristics in it, while D. Goleman emphasized other aspects. Lussin integrated both approaches. Despite conceptual differences, researchers generally agree that individuals with a higher level of Emotional Intelligence better understand the emotions they experience themselves and those of others, and are also better able to express and regulate them, which enhances effectiveness in communication and activities (I. N.). Andreeva notes that individuals with high EI adapt more easily in society [Andreeva 2004, pp. 12–13].

Research indicates that anxiety is indeed related to an individual's ability to recognize and regulate emotions. For example, it has been found that higher levels of emotional intelligence in preschool children are associated with lower levels of anxiety [Polishchuk 2021, pp. 25–30]. Similar findings have been obtained for older adolescents [Mazur 2019, pp. 237–239].

However, the role of Emotional Intelligence in the issue of anxiety has not yet been sufficiently explored. In our view, the specific features of anxiety manifestations in younger and older adolescents with varying levels of Emotional Intelligence development, as well as the associations between different types of anxiety and the components of Emotional Intelligence, have not been clearly delineated. This article presents the results of a study aimed at identifying the relationships between various types of anxiety and Emotional Intelligence, including its individual components, in younger and older adolescents.

To collect empirical data, the Children's Manifest Anxiety Scale (CMAS), the Adolescent Manifest Anxiety Scale (CMAS), the Students' Trait Anxiety Scale adapted by A. M. Prikhoyan, and the Emotional Intelligence Test by D. V. Lyusin (EmIn) were used. To determine whether there is a relationship between anxiety and EI in adolescents, Spearman's correlation coefficient was applied. To compare the samples in terms of anxiety levels and emotional intelligence development levels, the Mann-Whitney U test was employed. Calculations were conducted using SPSS.

The study surveyed 41 participants enrolled at GBOU Moscow 'School No. 843.' Among them, 21 were fourth-grade students aged 9 to 11 years, and 20 were in grades 10 to 11 aged 15 to 16 years. In the younger group, 48% were girls (10 participants) and 52% were boys (11 participants); in the older group, 75% were girls and 25% were boys (15 and 5 participants, respectively).

According to diagnostic results, both younger and older adolescents exhibit normal levels of explicit, general personal, school-related, self-evaluative, and interpersonal anxieties (data presented in Table 1), indicating that this level is necessary for individual adaptation. Younger adolescents demonstrate a normal level of magical anxiety. In contrast, this type of anxiety is generally not characteristic of older adolescents.

Comparative analysis using the Mann-Whitney U test revealed no statistically significant differences in the levels of explicit ($p=0.309$), personal ($p=0.109$), school-related ($p=0.056$), self-evaluative ($p=0.36$), interpersonal ($p=0.938$), and magical ($p=0.14$) anxieties between younger and older adolescents. Thus, the formation of anxiety depends more on personal characteristics and the adolescent's position in significant domains of life than on age.

Table 1. Mean Anxiety Indicators for Younger and Older Adolescents

	Younger Adolescents (n=21)	Older Adolescents (n=20)	Significance of Differences
Explicit Anxiety	6.1	6.4	—
General Personal Anxiety	4.7	3.0	—
School Anxiety	4.2	3.4	—
Self-Evaluative Anxiety	4.5	3.4	—
Interpersonal Anxiety	5.6	4.5	—
Magical Anxiety	3.9	2.2	—

Figures 1 and 2 show that slightly more than half (52%) of younger adolescents and half (50%) of older adolescents experience elevated explicit anxiety. Of these, 14% of younger and 15% of older adolescents exhibit a very high level of explicit anxiety and are therefore classified within the risk group. Such anxiety may be associated with actual maladjustment of the student in areas of life significant to them, or it may exist despite objectively favorable circumstances and result from personal conflicts, low self-esteem, and other individual characteristics.

Among younger pupils, 10% of students were identified for whom anxiety is not characteristic. These pupils can indeed scarcely experience anxiety due to their individual characteristics and life circumstances. However, such an excessively strong calmness may indicate a defensive mechanism.

Increased general Personal Anxiety, which manifests in a wide variety of situations, is characteristic of 29% of younger adolescents and 10% of older adolescents.

School-related situations induce slightly elevated anxiety in 10% of younger adolescents, and very high anxiety in 10% of both younger and older adolescents. These students are particularly anxious, for example, during tests, when receiving test scores, when receiving a reprimand from a teacher, and in other similar situations.

Elevated self-evaluative anxiety is present in 29% of younger adolescents and 15% of older adolescents. An at-risk group based on this scale is identified only among younger adolescents (10%); these students perceive very high anxiety related to self-attitude, which indicates disruptions in self-esteem development and personal conflicts.

Figure 1. Levels of manifest anxiety in younger adolescents

Figure 2. Levels of manifest anxiety in older adolescents

Table 2 illustrates the distribution of subjects in both groups across the levels of general personal, school-related, self-esteem, interpersonal, and magical anxieties.

Situations involving communication elicit increased anxiety in nearly half (47%) of younger adolescents and one quarter of older adolescents. The at-risk group includes a higher proportion of younger adolescents (33%) compared to older adolescents (5%). Communication situations, such as when it is necessary to ask a question to a stranger or when individuals are being observed during their activities, elicit very high anxiety in them.

Anxiety in situations related to mystical fears increases in 20% of younger adolescents and 5% of older adolescents.

Furthermore, across all types of anxiety in various situations, participants were identified who are fundamentally not prone to anxiety. However, it is possible that they prevent unpleasant experiences from entering consciousness, defending themselves against such experiences through denial.

Table 2. Anxiety levels in various situations among younger and older adolescents (abbreviations: younger — younger adolescents, older — older adolescents)

	General Personal Anxiety		School Anxiety		Self-Evaluative Anxiety		Interpersonal Anxiety		Magical Anxiety	
	younger	older	younger	older	younger	older	younger	older	younger	older
Absence of anxiety	33%	50%	38%	50%	33%	55%	29%	25%	48%	70%
Normal anxiety level	38%	40%	43%	40%	38%	30%	24%	50%	33%	25%
Slightly elevated anxiety	14%	5%	10%	0%	19%	15%	14%	15%	10%	0%
Clearly elevated anxiety	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	5%	0%	5%
Very high anxiety	5%	5%	10%	10%	10%	0%	33%	5%	10%	0%

Table 3 indicates that, according to the Lucina emotional intelligence test, both groups exhibit an average level of emotional intelligence — they demonstrate a fairly good understanding of emotional expressions.

However, younger adolescents exhibit low average scores in Interpersonal Emotional Intelligence and Understanding One’s Own Emotions, primarily due to a very low score on the Scale of Understanding Others’ Emotions. They demonstrate lower proficiency in recognizing and identifying others’ emotions and show reduced ability to manage others’ emotions.

Older adolescents exhibit low scores on the scales of Understanding One’s Own Emotions and Managing One’s Own Emotions. They demonstrate less proficiency in identifying and regulating their own emotions. This may be attributable to hormonal changes.

Analysis using the Mann-Whitney U test demonstrated statistically significant differences in three components of emotional intelligence between younger and older adolescents. Older adolescents have higher levels of interpersonal emotional intelligence ($p=0.002$), as well as greater understanding of emotions ($p=0.021$), particularly in understanding others’ emotions ($p=0.002$). No significant differences were identified in the levels of overall ($p=0.457$) and intrapersonal ($p=0.147$) emotional intelligence, emotion regulation ($p=0.676$), regulation of one’s own ($p=0.249$) and others’ ($p=0.000$) emotions, understanding of one’s own ($p=0.456$) and others’ ($p=0.154$) emotions, or control of emotional expression ($p=0.447$).

Table 3. Mean values of Emotional Intelligence indicators in younger and older adolescents

	Younger Adolescents (n=21)	Older adolescents (n=20)	Significance of Differences
Overall Emotional Intelligence (OEI)	79.7	84.0	—
Interpersonal Emotional Intelligence (Interpersonal EI)	36.0	45.0	+
Intrapersonal Emotional Intelligence (IEI)	43.7	39.0	—
Understanding Emotions	35.7	41.0	+
Emotion Management	44.0	43.0	—
Understanding Others’ Emotions	18.0	25.0	+
Managing Others’ Emotions	18.0	20.0	—
Understanding One’s Own Emotions	17.8	16.0	—
Managing One’s Own Emotions	13.4	11.0	—
Expression Control	12.5	11.0	—

Tables 4 and 5 indicate that slightly less than half (48%) of younger adolescents exhibit low to very low levels of overall emotional intelligence (hereinafter OEI), whereas among older adolescents such results are observed in 40%. Twenty-nine percent of younger and 35% of older adolescents demonstrate high to very high OEI scores.

The interpersonal emotional intelligence indicator (hereinafter IEI) is comprised of the subscales Understanding Others' Emotions and Managing Others' Emotions. Low levels of EI are observed in the majority of younger adolescents (71%) and in 20% of older adolescents. At the same time, 19% of younger and 45% of older adolescents exhibit high and very high scores on this measure. Thus, within the older group of participants, there is a greater proportion of adolescents capable of accurately understanding the experiences of others, based on intuition and the external manifestation of emotions, for example, as reflected in voice, facial expressions, and gestures. Additionally, there is a greater proportion among them who consider themselves capable of eliciting certain emotions in others.

The intrapersonal emotional intelligence indicator (hereinafter — IEI) is calculated as the sum of scores on the subscales Understanding One's Own Emotions, Managing One's Own Emotions, and Expression Control. This indicator is at low and very low levels in 29% of younger adolescents and more than half (55%) of older adolescents. Conversely, it is at high and very high levels in 48% of younger adolescents and 35% of older adolescents. In both the younger and older groups of subjects, an equal proportion of individuals—20%—demonstrate a high and very high ability to recognize and identify their own emotions, understand their causes, and describe them. At the same time, among older adolescents (45%), there is a greater proportion of individuals whose Understanding One's Own Emotions is at low and very low levels compared to younger adolescents (38%). Furthermore, among younger adolescents (38%), there is a higher proportion of individuals with a high and very high ability to regulate their emotions, evoke and maintain desirable emotions, and keep undesirable emotions under control than among older adolescents (5%). This ability is underdeveloped in 38% of younger adolescents and 50% of older adolescents. Among younger adolescents, a greater proportion are capable of managing the external manifestations of their emotions, such as inhibiting irritation, concealing embarrassment, and controlling facial expressions: 67% compared to 50%. Twenty-four percent of younger adolescents and 45% of older adolescents have difficulty managing the external manifestations of their emotions. These outcomes concerning the understanding and regulation of emotions in older adolescents may be associated with the fact that they have already undergone significant hormonal changes, which complicates their ability to comprehend and control their emotions.

Table 4. Levels of Development of Emotional Intelligence and Its Components in Younger Adolescents

	Very High High	High	Medium	Low	Very Low
Overall Emotional Intelligence (OEI)	10%	19%	24%	14%	33%
Interpersonal Emotional Intelligence (Interpersonal EI)	5%	14%	10%	29%	43%
Intrapersonal Emotional Intelligence (IEI)	19%	29%	24%	14%	14%
Understanding Emotions (UE)	5%	0%	29%	24%	43%
Emotion Management (EM)	24%	10%	38%	5%	24%
Understanding Others' Emotions (Understanding Others' Emotions)	5%	0%	14%	24%	57%
Managing Others' Emotions (Managing Others' Emotions)	0%	24%	38%	14%	24%
Understanding One's Own Emotions (Understanding One's Own Emotions)	10%	10%	43%	19%	19%
Managing One's Own Emotions (Managing One's Own Emotions)	24%	14%	24%	14%	24%
Expression Control (Expression Control)	19%	48%	10%	10%	14%

Table 5. Levels of Development of Emotional Intelligence and Its Components in Older Adolescents

	Very High High	High	Medium	Low	Very Low
Overall Emotional Intelligence (OEI)	15%	20%	25%	15%	25%
Interpersonal Emotional Intelligence (Interpersonal EI)	15%	30%	35%	20%	0%
Intrapersonal Emotional Intelligence (IEI)	5%	30%	10%	15%	40%
Understanding Emotions (UE)	5%	10%	45%	30%	10%
Emotion Management (EM)	5%	35%	15%	30%	15%
Understanding Others' Emotions (Understanding Others' Emotions)	10%	35%	25%	20%	10%

	Very High High	High	Medium	Low	Very Low
Managing Others' Emotions (Managing Others' Emotions)	15%	20%	40%	25%	0%
Understanding One's Own Emotions (Understanding One's Own Emotions)	10%	10%	35%	10%	35%
Managing One's Own Emotions (Managing One's Own Emotions)	5%	0%	45%	25%	25%
Expression Control (Expression Control)	15%	35%	5%	25%	20%

Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was used to identify a statistically significant relationship between the level of emotional intelligence development and levels of various types of anxiety. The results for younger adolescents are presented in Table 6, and for older adolescents in Table 7.

In both groups, a significant negative correlation between overall emotional intelligence and explicit anxiety was identified. Among the components of EI, explicit anxiety in both younger and older adolescents shows significant negative correlations with intrapersonal emotional intelligence, understanding of one's own emotions, emotional regulation, and management of one's emotions. In younger adolescents, the manifestation of overt anxiety is also associated with the ability to regulate the external expression of their emotions.

In younger adolescents, personal, self-esteem, and interpersonal anxieties exhibit significant negative correlations with global EI, intrapersonal EI, emotion regulation, understanding their own emotions, managing their own emotions, and expression control. Self-esteem and interpersonal anxieties also show negative correlations with managing others' emotions. Magical anxiety exhibits a negative association with intrapersonal EI, emotion regulation, specifically of one's own emotions, and expression control.

In older adolescents, personal, self-esteem, and magical anxieties demonstrate a significant association with intrapersonal emotional intelligence. Personal and interpersonal anxieties have a negative correlation with expression control; self-esteem anxiety is negatively correlated with regulation and understanding of emotions, understanding of one's own and others' emotions, and expression control; magical anxiety is negatively correlated with understanding of emotions.

No significant correlation was found between school anxiety, overall emotional intelligence, and its components in both groups.

Table 6. Relationship between anxiety and EI in younger adolescents

Anxiety	Overall EI	Intrapersonal EI	Understanding Emotions	Emotion management of emotions	Managing Others' Emotions	Understanding One's Own Emotions	Managing One's Own Emotions	Expression Control
Explicit	-0.590**	-0.726**	-0.535*	-0.596**	-0.449*	-0.866**	-0.436*	-0.517*
Overall personal anxiety	-0.535*	-0.719**	-0.383	-0.628**	-0.385	-0.700**	-0.495*	-0.660**
Self-assessment	-0.604**	-0.739**	-0.411	-0.690**	-0.476*	-0.669**	-0.573**	-0.611**
Interpersonal	-0.558**	-0.660**	-0.350	-0.630**	-0.494*	-0.642**	-0.604**	-0.487*
Magical	0.410	-0.595**	-0.378	-0.470*	-0.326	-0.586**	-0.327	-0.576**

*. The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed).
 **. The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

Table 7. Correlation between anxiety and EI in older adolescents

Anxiety	Overall EI	Intrapersonal EI	Emotion Management	Understanding One's Own Emotions	Managing One's Own Emotions	Expression Control
Explicit	-0.455*	-0.570**	-0.457*	-0.618**	-0.451*	-0.180
Overall personal anxiety	-0.276	-0.460*	-0.390	-0.426	-0.313	-0.664**
Self-assessment	-0.378	-0.597**	-0.471*	-0.529*	-0.534*	-0.689**
Interpersonal	-0.262	-0.410	0.345	-0.409	-0.212	-0.551*
Magical	-0.337	-0.472*	-0.34	-0.452*	-0.278	-0.438

*. The correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (two-tailed).
 **. The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed).

Our study showed that there are no significant differences in the manifestations of different types of anxiety between older and younger adolescents. Anxiety does not depend on age. Its development is more influenced by adolescents' personality traits and their positive or negative conditions in domains significant to them.

The data obtained confirm that anxiety, both as a personality construct and as a state in various situations among adolescents, is closely linked to the development of the emotional domain. These results correspond with earlier studies on anxiety and Emotional Intelligence in preschool children [Polishchuk 2021, pp. 25–30] and older adolescents [Sinkevich, Tuchkova 2020, pp. 345–347], which

identified a significant inverse relationship between anxiety and Emotional Intelligence within these groups.

According to our study, in older adolescents, the interpersonal component of Emotional Intelligence, understanding emotions, and specifically Understanding Others' Emotions, are more developed than in younger adolescents. In this regard, when developing programs for younger schoolchildren, it is important to focus on these areas. Furthermore, it was found that for both groups, the development of Intrapersonal Emotional Intelligence is particularly important, as its level shows a significant negative correlation with various types of anxiety.

Thus, we have examined which types of anxiety are manifested in adolescents of different ages, which components of Emotional Intelligence are more or less developed in them, and, most importantly, how the levels of anxiety relate to the developmental levels of Emotional Intelligence components in the selected groups.

The study yielded the following conclusions:

1. A review of the literature indicated that adolescents with elevated anxiety experience greater difficulty adapting to society. In contrast, a high level of emotional intelligence development facilitates greater effectiveness in communication and activity.

2. An inverse relationship exists between emotional intelligence and state anxiety in both younger and older adolescents: participants with a higher overall level of emotional intelligence demonstrated lower levels of state anxiety.

3. In younger adolescents, there is a negative correlation between personal, self-evaluative, and interpersonal anxiety and overall emotional intelligence.

4. Among the components of EI, intrapersonal emotional intelligence exhibits the most associations with different types of anxiety: IEI in younger adolescents has a significant negative correlation with manifest, personal, self-evaluative, interpersonal, and magical anxieties, while in older adolescents it correlates negatively with manifest, personal, self-evaluative, and magical anxieties. This indicates that adolescents who have a better understanding of their own emotions and are capable of managing them, controlling their external manifestations, are generally less anxious and experience lower levels of anxiety in various situations.

5. There is no significant correlation between school anxiety among younger and older adolescents and overall emotional intelligence and its components. This may be related to the fact that elevated school anxiety was not identified in the majority of younger and older adolescents who participated in the study.

6. There are no significant differences in the levels of school-related, self-esteem, interpersonal, and magical anxieties between younger and older adolescents.

7. Older adolescents exhibit more highly developed interpersonal Emotional Intelligence, Understanding Emotions, and particularly Understanding Others' Emotions. This indicates that older adolescents better understand the emotions of

others and are capable of managing them, as well as more accurately discerning and identifying emotions in general.

The conducted study made it possible to identify pertinent issues and to outline directions for further research. Thus, in the course of the study, we established that the emotional domain is critically important during adolescence. Many adolescents exhibit elevated anxiety; for instance, an increased level of state anxiety was identified in 52% of younger and 50% of older adolescents. Moreover, there is a reciprocal relationship between various types of anxiety and the level of development of emotional intelligence, particularly intrapersonal emotional intelligence. For example, adolescents who are better able to recognize and regulate their emotional experiences and their external expressions demonstrate lower levels of state anxiety.

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THE INFLUENCE OF WOMEN'S SELF-IMAGE ON THEIR CHOICE OF MARRIAGE PARTNER

Shaikina Elena Aleksandrovna

*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Luhansk State Pedagogical University*

Abstract. *The article focuses on investigating the relationship between the structure of an individual's self-image and women's preferences in selecting a marriage partner. The relevance of this study stems from the increasing importance of psychological factors in building marital relationships and the insufficient understanding of how a woman's self-image shapes her criteria for a potential spouse. The results obtained can be applied in family counseling practice and in designing programs aimed at fostering a mature approach to forming a family.*

Keywords: *self-attitude, choice of marriage partner, selection criteria, self-acceptance, self-confidence, marital preferences, psychological compatibility.*

The issue of choosing a marriage partner is one of the fundamental problems in family and personality psychology. In contemporary society, characterized by transformations in the institution of marriage, rising divorce rates, and shifts in gender roles, the investigation of underlying psychological factors affecting the development of marital preferences gains particular significance [4, p. 46].

One of these factors is the self-attitude of the individual — a complex emotionally evaluative construct which, according to V. V. Stolin and S. R. Pantileev, represents the expression of the personal meaning of the 'I' and encompasses both an overall positive or negative feeling toward oneself and more specific components: self-respect, auto-sympathy, self-interest, and the anticipated attitude from others. Self-attitude develops in the process of socialization and largely determines the character of interpersonal relationships, including intimate personal ones.

Researchers note that 'young people with a positive self-attitude are more inclined to marry when they feel ready and confident in themselves' [4, p. 49]. However, the question of how various components of self-attitude relate specifically to partner selection criteria remains underexplored.

The aim of our study is to identify the characteristics of the relationship between the structural components of women's self-attitude and their preferences in choosing a marriage partner.

Self-attitude is understood as an emotionally evaluative system that expresses the personal meaning of the 'I' and encompasses several specific modalities.

The study employed the following methods: the 'Methodology for Studying Self-Attitude' by S. R. Pantileev, which enables the identification of the self-attitude structure across nine scales — closedness/openness, self-confidence, self-guidance, reflected self-attitude, self-worth, self-acceptance, self-attachment, internal conflict, and self-blame — as well as the author's questionnaire titled 'Criteria for Choosing a Marriage Partner.' [2]:

In developing the questionnaire, we based our approach on theoretical foundations positing that the choice of a marriage partner is a multifactor process involving intertwined evolutionary, social, and psychological determinants. In contemporary psychology, the following groups of criteria are distinguished [5]:

- socio-economic: income level, education, professional status, housing conditions;
- physical: external attractiveness, health, physical fitness;
- personal-psychological: intelligence, kindness, sense of humor, responsibility, emotional stability;
- compatibility criteria: shared values, interests, psychological type, attachment style.

The sample of our study consisted of 106 women aged between 23 and 49.

The author's questionnaire 'Criteria for Choosing a Marriage Partner' is designed to identify women's preferences regarding a potential husband. Participants were asked to rate the significance of the following characteristics of a potential marriage partner on a scale from 1 (not significant at all) to 5 (critically important):

1. High income level of the potential spouse.
2. High social status and prestige of the partner's profession.
3. External attractiveness of the partner.
4. Intellect and level of education of the partner.
5. Psychological compatibility (shared views, values, interests).
6. Reliability and responsibility of the partner.
7. Emotional closeness and mutual understanding.
8. The partner's conformity with the expectations of your social environment (parents, friends).
9. Willingness to accept the partner's shortcomings in light of their positive qualities.
10. Do you consider that a partner should be more successful than you in the professional or financial sphere?

Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was employed to identify the relationships between self-attitude indicators and responses to the questionnaire items.

Correlation analysis revealed significant positive associations between the 'Self-confidence' scale and questionnaire item No. 2 regarding the importance of a partner's high social status. Women who perceive themselves as confident, strong-willed, and capable of commanding respect tend to have higher expectations regarding their partner's social status. This aligns with data indicating that high self-esteem allows a woman to pursue a partner of higher status.

The Self-worth scale also demonstrated a positive correlation with question No. 1 concerning the partner's high income. Women who perceive the value of their own personality tend to expect an adequate, from their point of view, 'evaluation' in the form of material provision from the man.

Interestingly, the Reflected self-attitude scale positively correlates with question No. 8 regarding the partner's conformity to the expectations of the surrounding social environment. The more a woman is focused on how others perceive her, the more important social approval of her choice becomes.

No significant correlations were identified between the 'Methodology for Studying Self-Attitude' scales and question No. 3 concerning external attractiveness. This may be due to the fact that the importance of appearance is a more universal and evolutionarily conditioned criterion, less influenced by self-attitude, or to social desirability mechanisms whereby women tend to downplay the importance of appearance in self-reports.

The most significant correlations were observed between measures of self-sympathy (a secondary factor) and items reflecting the importance of psychological closeness.

The 'Self-Acceptance' scale demonstrated a positive correlation with item No. 5 on psychological compatibility and item No. 7 on emotional closeness. Women who accept themselves with all their strengths and weaknesses also seek in a partner not external attributes, but a profound inner similarity and the capacity to be understood. They are capable of establishing mature relationships based on dialogue.

The 'Self-Acceptance' scale also positively correlates with question No. 9 concerning the willingness to accept a partner's shortcomings. Self-acceptance constitutes the basis for accepting another individual.

The 'Self-Guidance' scale is positively linked to question No. 6 regarding the significance of a partner's reliability and responsibility. Women who represent an 'inner core' for themselves seek a similarly autonomous and dependable partner who does not tend to shift responsibility onto external circumstances.

The 'Internal Conflict' scale revealed a negative correlation with question No. 5 concerning psychological compatibility. A high level of intrapersonal conflicts and tendencies toward rumination complicate the formulation of clear

compatibility criteria, or such women fundamentally doubt the possibility of harmonious relationships.

The 'Self-Confidence' scale showed a negative correlation with question No. 10 regarding the necessity of the partner's superiority. The higher a woman's self-confidence, the less she requires her partner to be more successful than herself. Conversely, low self-confidence (characterized by self-doubt and dissatisfaction with oneself) is associated with seeking a partner who would 'compensate' for these feelings by possessing a higher status.

The results of the study conducted confirm the hypothesis of significant correlations between the structural components of women's self-attitude and the criteria they prefer when selecting a marriage partner.

Components of self-attitude associated with social desirability and an external evaluation orientation (self-confidence, self-worth, reflected self-attitude) correlate with the selection of a partner based on socio-economic criteria and an orientation toward societal approval.

Components of self-attitude related to self-affection and internal self-acceptance (self-acceptance) constitute the foundation for an orientation toward psychological compatibility, emotional closeness, and acceptance of a partner's shortcomings. This aligns with contemporary findings on the growing significance of incorporating psychological factors into partner selection.

The level of internal conflict and self-blame may impede the development of clear and healthy criteria for partner choice, shifting the focus either to compensatory mechanisms (such as the search for a 'strong' partner) or exacerbating the neurotic nature of the relationship.

These findings can be applied in psychological counseling to help women become aware of their marital preferences and modify them through the harmonization of their self-image.

Thus, the study demonstrates that the choice of a marriage partner is neither a random nor an exclusively socially conditioned process. It is deeply rooted in the structure of personality, primarily in its self-attitude. Women with different self-attitude profiles tend to select different partners and assess the significance of their qualities differently. A harmonious self-attitude, founded on self-acceptance and self-respect, provides a basis for a mature choice oriented towards the values of compatibility and emotional closeness. A potential direction for future research is the investigation of analogous relationships within a male cohort, as well as the analysis of the dynamics of these relationships at various stages of marriage.

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THE MODEL OF A SYSTEM OF STRUCTURED MEANINGS

Bazhutina Svetlana Borisovna

*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Luhansk State Pedagogical University*

Abstract. *The article examines the issue of semantic distortion of signs and lexical meanings in the contemporary informational environment, which can alter their commonly accepted meanings, including within individual consciousness. This, in turn, results in a distortion of the understanding of the surrounding world. According to the author, the creation of a systematic structure of the value-semantic sphere can serve to counteract this process. The article presents an experimentally derived Model of a system of structured meanings and provides examples of various types of value-semantic structures.*

Keywords: *sign, meaning, sense, personal dichotomous construct, semantic layers, components of the Model of the system of structured meanings.*

In the modern world, many significant components of human existence undergo violent chaotic destabilization, which can ultimately result in the destruction of the familiar foundations of individuals' lives, numerous external and intrapersonal conflicts, crises, and the collapse of the systemic bases of humankind's very existence. The process of disordering has affected the mental sphere of individuals as well: the very foundation of the verbal sign system — the semantic content of the sign, the essential content of which was proposed by G. Frege (1848–1925) in his renowned 'semantic triangle,' where the vertices denote the sign-word and the lexeme, specifically: the sign, which substitutes for a particular object; the meaning — which fixes its instrumental or mental content, common to those equally using the object, phenomenon, or state; and thirdly, the personal sense (a concept introduced later by A. N. Leontiev), which presupposes the presence of individual semantic nuances in the perception of the sign by a particular person. In the course of learning, individuals aimed to align their personal meaning as closely as possible with the generally accepted meaning of the sign. At present, due to the development of the Internet and the ability of each individual to propagate their 'particular viewpoint,' the academic (as reflected in dictionaries) content of the sign has become distorted and at times altered beyond recognition. Consequently, the issue of preserving the

substantive systemic structuring of the value-semantic domain of the individual within its foundational realities assumes critical importance[15].

In psychology, both foreign and Russian, this problem has been addressed by various scholars. Among them are E. Yu. Artemieva, Rokich, Schwartz, B. S. Bratus, S. S. Bubnov, A. R. Luria, D. A. Leontiev, E. Yu. Pochetaeva, M. S. Yanitsky, and many others [1; 5; 7; 10; 14; 20]. It should be noted that while foreign scholars most frequently identify as the most significant meanings in the structure those related to everyday human existence: safety, health, work, communication with other people, and so forth [16; 17], Russian scholars focus their particular attention on social, culturological, and spiritual-moral meanings [4; 5; 8; 11; 12; 13]. In our research, we endeavored to develop this idea into a logical explanation of the ‘Model of the System of Structured Meanings.’ Let us briefly outline the logic of our investigations.

In the diagnostic experimental studies that we have been conducting since the 2000s, a large and diverse battery of methods was employed, the selection of which was guided by the idea put forward by many researchers in the semantic sphere — that the semantic content of a sign for an individual is determined, besides the logical explanation of the purpose of an object, phenomenon, situation, state, or concept, by their functional meanings, structural features, and origins, but most importantly by the quality of the emotional attitude of the perceiving subject [1; 4]. Therefore, the methodologies selected by us were required to reflect not only the content meaning of the signs but also the respondents’ emotional attitudes toward them. In this article, we will not describe the entire set of methodologies or the data obtained through them; for illustrative purposes, we will only present the results of Etkind’s ‘Color Relation Test’ methodology with the stimulus material we proposed and a somewhat refined research procedure [18]. In the course of the research, we succeeded in identifying the following.

1. The formation of the structure of meanings and values, as J. Kelly posited [6], occurs under the influence of personal dichotomous constructs. It was experimentally demonstrated that the use of one of the oldest constructs consciously recognized by humanity, the construct of ‘good/evil’, which signifies the emergence of spiritual and moral principles within a person, enables the identification of the characteristics of the structure of an individual’s semantic sphere. Moreover, any experimental sample invariably distinguishes three groups. “Normals” are subjects who accept “good” and reject “evil.” “Deformers” unequivocally either accept or reject both “good” and “evil,” or accept “evil” but do not accept “good.” “Those Determining” (this group has generally been younger in age than all others) are subjects who did not distinguish the poles, showing indifference toward both “good” and “evil.”

2. Depending on the group to which respondents were assigned, they consistently demonstrated acceptance or rejection of the proposed stimulus material in an identical logical sequence: words from different semantic layers — the ‘pre-conscious’

layer (mother, father, good, evil, pain, fear, God, everything I do not accept in this life — even 3-year-old children respond adequately to these signs with their attitudes); the layer of socio-ethical meanings (joint activity, power over people, governance over them, my responsibility for the actions and deeds I perform, physical pleasures, comfort, various bodily enjoyments and pleasures, the ability to correctly and argumentatively justify my point of view to others, various dependencies on whatever (or whoever) it may be, my will, the ability to regulate my behavior and control myself during the realization of life plans, etc.); a stratum of contemporary culturological meanings (the mentality of Russians, their culture, language, history, the future of Russia; democratic ideas of modern Europe and the USA); a stratum of spiritual and moral meanings (honor and dignity of the individual, my Conscience, my personal freedom of choice).

It was assumed that meanings within the “strata” were weakly structured, since the percentage proportions of negative and positive choices fluctuated in experimental samples from year to year; however, the following regularity was consistently observed: the “norm” group exhibited the highest percentage of positive choices across all socially significant, culturological, and spiritual-moral notions; the choices of the “self-defining” group were fewer and more contradictory in percentage terms; whereas the “deformers” demonstrated a greater propensity than others toward dependencies and aggression. This will be illustrated by the diagnostic results of the most recent 2025 sample.

Table 1.
Indicators of positive choices by respondents of three groups across several stimulus categories of the CTO methodology

Signs, Meanings, Lexemes	“Norm” (140 respondents)		“Deformers” (115 respondents)		“Definers” (53 respondents)	
	Number of choices (+)	Percent-ages%(+)	Number of choices (+)	Percent-ages%(+)	Number of choices (+)	Percent-ages%(+)
Human honor and dignity	100(+)	72 %	44(+)	38 %	27(+)	51 %
Various dependencies on any entity or circumstance	24(+)	17 %	55(+)	48 %	16(+)	30 %
My mother	112(+)	80 %	49(+)	43 %	31(+)	58 %
My conscience	95(+)	69 %	39(+)	34 %	27(+)	51 %
Respectful attitude toward a person	100(+)	72 %	37(+)	32 %	26(+)	49 %
Evil	0(+)	0 %	84(+)	73 %	33(+)	59 %
Myself	119(+)	85 %	52(+)	45 %	32(+)	60 %
Violence against a person and their humiliation	17(+)	12 %	68(+)	59 %	11(+)	21 %

My responsibility for the actions and deeds I perform actions and deeds	82(+)	59%	41(+)	36%	27(+)	51%
My personal freedom	108(+)	77%	48(+)	42%	31(+)	58%
Creative and inventive activity	90(+)	64%	48(+)	41%	32(+)	60%

3. The systematization of semantic strata into an integral structure takes place as subjects acquire the qualities of adult self-identity. These qualities are grouped into three principal semantic components, which enable the maintenance of equilibrium within the entire value-semantic sphere of the personality: the component of meanings related to joint, constructive, and creative activity; the component of meanings pertaining to various self-phenomena; and the component of meanings of substantive interpersonal relationships. The components of the model emerge during the ontological development of the human species, as their joint life becomes increasingly complex and organized, accompanied by the differentiation of ethnoses and nations (components of substantive relations) [9; 15]; during the development of the complex mechanism of human identity (components of I-phenomena) [19]; and through the joint activities and communication of people—the most crucial factor in changes to the psyche in general, the formation of consciousness therein, and the cultivation of personality in the individual [9; 11]. The analysis of the obtained data demonstrated that there are strong correlations between the meanings of components across all three groups at a significance level of $P < 0.01$ according to the Student's t-test. The correlations between the meanings of components vary by group and reflect the characterological features of the value-semantic sphere of their members [2; 3].

• Thus, in the “norm” group, the category “I myself” exhibited positive correlations with “my future adult life,” “personal freedom of choice,” and the value “having the opportunity to create for the benefit of my Homeland, my people.” The ability to hear another’s position and accurately, argumentatively defend one’s own viewpoint positively correlates with the capacity to perceive one’s life and the development of one’s country as life-affirming. ‘Creative labor’ demonstrated positive correlations with ‘my Conscience,’ ‘honor and dignity of a person,’ and ‘respectful attitude toward a person,’ while ‘my Conscience’ correlated with ‘responsibility for the actions and deeds performed.’

• In the group of ‘deformers,’ positive correlations were found among the meanings of signs: ‘I myself’ positively correlated with ‘spiritual and moral values,’ ‘honor and dignity of a person,’ ‘accumulation of material values,’ ‘respectful attitude toward a person,’ ‘freedom,’ and ‘responsibility.’ At the same time, ‘violence against a person, humiliation of him’ exhibited a direct correlation with the value of family, which is further confirmed by the low percentages of acceptance of ‘mother’ and ‘father’ by these respondents. The category ‘my creative

labor' demonstrated a positive correlation with 'personal freedom of choice,' but showed no correlation with 'responsibility for the chosen actions and deeds.' Notably, the lexeme 'computer games and various kinds of "journeys" across the network' (with 50% positive selections in the group) displayed several negative correlations: with the desire 'to have power over people and to be able to manipulate them,' with the values of self-improvement and 'participation in building a just, humane society,' as well as with the 'mentality and culture of Russia.' As can be seen, respondents in the group 'avoid' comprehension and participation in important socially significant acts of human life by retreating into the virtual world. Furthermore, the correlations observed among the 'distorters' allow us to conclude that their semantic preferences are most likely shaped by pressure from authoritarian personalities, as evidenced by the highest proportion of 'acceptors' of various types of dependencies within this group.

- The 'definers' exhibited significantly fewer correlational links between meanings compared to other groups, although in this group, the threshold for correlation significance in the analysis was lowered to $p < 0.05$ due to the small number of respondents (53 individuals). Thus, the category 'Myself' exhibited a positive correlation only with spiritual and moral values and with 'father.' 'Creative labor' showed only a single negative correlation with 'evil'; evidently, for these respondents, only creation represents a substantial alternative to 'evil.' Notably, within the group, 'my Conscience' was positively associated with 'mother,' 'future adult life,' 'good,' 'personal freedom of choice,' and 'evil,' whereas 'respectful attitude toward a person' was contrasted with 'power over people and manipulation thereof,' thereby underscoring the group's relatively tolerant stance towards evil while simultaneously manifesting explicit rejection of manipulative actions directed at individuals.

These are by no means all the correlations identified during the diagnostic experiment between the personal meanings of representatives from different groups. We have provided only certain examples illustrating the ambiguity in the participants' understanding of the same signs. Nevertheless, even from these examples it is evident that the less systematized an individual's meanings are by the dichotomy of 'good/evil', and the more the content of this dichotomy is disrupted within their consciousness, the less capable they are of establishing warm interpersonal relationships, the less self-sufficient and autonomous they become, and the more they tend to fall prey to various kinds of dependencies. Thus, working with the content of meanings, with their proper structuring in the human mind, can counteract semantic chaos, which is a specific reflection of the chaos of our real life.

In conclusion, we highlight another important aspect of our 'Model of the System of Structured Meanings.' Numerous connections have been identified between the content of personal meanings from different semantic layers and the categories: 'my personal freedom of choice' and 'my responsibility for the actions and deeds'

undertaken.' In the analysis of the literature, particularly in the works of scholars within the existential psychological framework, as well as in our research on the perceptions of youth and adults regarding the category of 'adulthood,' two qualities were identified — freedom of choice and responsibility for one's actions. Both qualities were recognized as fundamental markers of an autonomous, self-sufficient, active, and creatively humanistically oriented personality. Consequently, our 'Model...' cannot be considered complete without two components that frame and direct its further development: the meanings of individual freedom of choice and the content of responsibility for one's committed actions and deeds. It is precisely through choices that the direction of human activity is determined, reflecting its constructive and creative nature, the character of relationships with others, while the degree of responsibility for one's actions enables the regulation of one's own behavior, self-reflection, and self-assessment as a person.

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PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-DETERMINATION OF PEDAGOGICAL STUDENTS

Marusenko Elena Andreevna

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor
Volodymyr Dahl Lugansk State University*

Aliyev Shaig Akber oglu

*Postgraduate Student
Lugansk State Pedagogical University*

Abstract. *This article examines key psychological issues influencing the process of professional self-determination of students majoring in teaching. Based on an analysis of scientific literature and empirical research, the main factors hindering the development of a stable professional identity in future teachers are identified. The study demonstrates that issues of professional self-determination are related to both the personal characteristics of students and the organizational aspects of the educational process. Recommendations are offered for optimizing psychological support for students majoring in teaching during the professional self-determination stage.*

Keywords: *professional self-determination, students majoring in teaching, professional identity, psychological support, motivation, career development.*

Professional self-determination among students specializing in pedagogy constitutes a complex and multifaceted process involving the formation of a conscious career choice and the construction of an individual trajectory of professional development. The relevance of this issue stems from the fact that the quality of professional self-determination of future educators influences not only their personal career satisfaction but also the overall effectiveness of the education system.

According to research by Zeer E. F., Rudey O. A., and Klimova E. A., students enrolled in pedagogical programs frequently encounter difficulties in the awareness of their professional choice, which results in a high level of dissatisfaction with their profession at the onset of professional practice. Psychological issues emerging during university studies can substantially affect the development of professional identity and motivation towards pedagogical work.

The aim of this article is to analyze the principal psychological challenges of professional self-determination among students specializing in pedagogy and to propose scientifically substantiated approaches to their surmounting.

One of the most significant challenges is the motivational uncertainty experienced by students in selecting the teaching profession. Studies indicate that a considerable number of students enrolled in pedagogical programs enter higher education institutions not on the basis of a conscious and intrinsically motivated choice, but rather under the influence of external factors: parental recommendations, ease of admission, the geographic convenience of the university for the applicant, and the lack of alternative options [2; 3; 4; 5].

This situation leads to the formation of external motivation, which does not facilitate the development of a genuine professional identity. Students motivated by external factors are often disengaged from the educational process, demonstrate little initiative in the development of professional competencies, and are more likely to drop out or change their field of study.

Psychological research by K. A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya identifies a discrepancy between the expectations of students enrolling in pedagogical higher education institutions and the actual content of a teacher's professional activities. Students often develop an idealized conception of the teaching profession, failing to fully recognize the complexity, responsibility, and social challenges that a teacher will encounter in practical professional activity [1].

This discrepancy may result in disappointment when students face the actual aspects of pedagogical work: high emotional demands, conflict situations, and the necessity for continuous self-improvement. The psychological experience of such a discrepancy can lead to a crisis of professional identity at the early stages of training.

Many students specializing in pedagogy experience uncertainty regarding their capabilities in teaching practice. This is reflected in low professional self-esteem, doubts about their communicative competencies, their ability to manage the educational process, and to interact with diverse learner groups.

Psychological research by S. L. Rubinstein demonstrates that the level of professional self-esteem is closely connected with the formation of professional identity. Students with low self-esteem of their pedagogical competence most often either drop out or choose less responsible positions within the pedagogical hierarchy [7].

Pedagogical activity requires specific personal qualities: patience, empathy, tolerance, stress tolerance, and readiness for self-sacrifice. However, not all students possess a sufficient level of development of these qualities or are aware of their necessity.

The problem consists in the fact that, during the process of professional self-determination, students often fail to conduct an objective self-assessment of the correspondence between their personal characteristics and the requirements of the pedagogical profession. This results in the selection of a profession that is

inconsistent with personal attributes, subsequently leading to professional burnout and attrition within the educational field.

Internal psychological factors influencing the professional self-determination of students specializing in pedagogy include the following:

- personal maturity — the readiness to accept responsibility for one's own professional choice and development;
- developed reflective capacities — the ability to critically evaluate one's own abilities, values, and motives;
- level of development of professional interests — the establishment of a stable interest in pedagogical activity;
- self-efficacy — the conviction in one's own capacity to successfully perform pedagogical activity.

External factors have a significant impact on the process of professional self-determination:

- family environment — parental attitudes towards the teaching profession, material support;
- university educational environment — quality of training, availability of practical training, professional counseling;
- socio-economic conditions — status of the teaching profession in society, level of remuneration;
- information environment — availability of reliable information regarding the content of professional activities.

The following methodological approaches are effectively employed in the investigation of the psychological aspects of professional self-determination among students of pedagogical specialties:

1. The person-centered approach implies considering the individual characteristics of students when organizing the process of professional self-determination.
2. The activity-based approach emphasizes the importance of engaging students in various forms of pedagogical activity.
3. The systems approach enables the consideration of professional self-determination as an integral component of the professional training system.
4. The developmental approach aims at the formation of new psychological structures that contribute to a conscious professional choice.

Analysis of scientific literature and empirical studies (Zeer, 2003; Pryazhnikov, 2010; Klimov, 2004) highlights the following empirically validated issues:

- The first issue is the high proportion of students who experience doubts regarding the correctness of their professional choice. Survey data indicate that 35–45% of students in pedagogical programs harbor doubts about their choice.
- The second issue concerns the inadequate psychological support provided to students during the process of professional self-determination. In the majority

of pedagogical higher education institutions, specialized psychological assistance programs aimed at the formation of professional identity are lacking.

– The third issue involves the absence of a systematic selection process for applicants based on psychological criteria determining suitability for the teaching profession. Consequently, students with personal characteristics incompatible with the professional requirements are admitted.

Effective resolution of the identified problems requires integrating theoretical knowledge of the psychology of professional self-determination with practical measures for organizing psychological support for students. This includes:

– development of psychological tests and methodologies for assessing readiness for pedagogical practice;

– conducting psychological consultations and career guidance activities;

– inclusion of specialized disciplines in the curriculum to foster reflection and self-awareness.

– organization of early teaching practice opportunities that enable students to gain experience in authentic pedagogical activities;

– establishment of support groups and mentorship provided by more experienced educators.

Based on the analysis conducted, the following scientifically substantiated recommendations are proposed:

– enhancement of the applicant selection process through the introduction of psychological testing aimed at evaluating the correspondence of personal characteristics to the demands of the teaching profession;

– development of individualized professional growth trajectories by creating opportunities for students to select elective courses and specialization areas in accordance with their personal interests and capabilities;

– expansion of practical training — broadening internship programs beginning from the early years to foster realistic understanding of the profession;

– organization of psychological support — establishment of a specialized psychological counseling service for students;

– development of professional reflection — integration of training sessions and seminars into the curriculum to facilitate the development of self-analysis and self-assessment skills;

– development of motivational readiness — conducting motivational interviews and incorporating content relating to the meanings and values of pedagogical activity into the curriculum;

– development of emotional competence — conducting training sessions on emotional intelligence and stress resilience;

– formation of communicative skills — organizing interactive classes aimed at developing the capacity for constructive interaction;

– work on the values and meaning of pedagogical activity — conducting philosophical and psychological discussions regarding the significance of education and the role of the teacher in society [2; 4; 5; 6].

The challenges related to the psychological aspects of professional self-determination among students of pedagogical specialties represent a significant issue for the system of higher pedagogical education. The problems identified during the analysis — motivational uncertainty, the discrepancy between professional expectations and reality, low professional competence, and insufficient personal readiness — necessitate a comprehensive approach to their resolution.

The proposed recommendations entail a systemic transformation of the approaches to professional training of future educators, incorporation of psychological support at all stages of education, and the fostering of skills in professional reflection. The implementation of these measures will enhance the quality of professional self-determination among students, decrease the rates of dropout and transfer to other fields of study, as well as contribute to a more successful adaptation of graduates of pedagogical universities to their professional careers.

It is important to emphasize that the successful professional self-determination of students in pedagogical specialties represents not only an individual challenge for each student but also a socially important issue, the resolution of which influences the quality of training future generations. In the context of a dynamically evolving educational landscape and the societal challenges confronting the education system, it is imperative that pedagogical universities devote particular attention to the psychological support of students' professional development.

The integration of the proposed organizational, psychological-pedagogical, and personal-development measures within the framework of future teachers' training will establish favorable conditions for the conscious and responsible selection of the teaching profession. This, in turn, will contribute not only to the personal and professional growth of students but also to the strengthening of the prestige of the teaching profession in society.

Prospects for further research in this field include the development and validation of specialized psychological support programs, the creation of reliable tools for diagnosing the professional readiness of students for pedagogical activities, as well as the examination of the effects of implemented measures on indicators of professional adaptation and job satisfaction among teachers at the early stages of their professional careers.

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THE POTENTIAL OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY IN THE MORAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Nadolinskaya Tatyana Vasilievna

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Taganrog Institute named after A. P. Chekhov — Branch of Rostov State

University of Economics (RINH),

Taganrog, Russian Federation

Abstract. *The author examines the role and potential of computer technologies in the moral development of preschool children. The article examines the wide range of educational possibilities offered by computer technologies. The author outlines several advantages of incorporating computer technologies into the moral development of preschool children.*

Keywords: *technology, computer technology, moral development, preschool children.*

Computer technologies are increasingly integrated into the system of preschool education, responding to the needs of an advancing society. Rather than being regarded solely as an educational play tool, computers are recognized as universal information systems capable of enhancing and transforming the overall learning environment in kindergartens by engaging with various educational facets.

The need for reform of the entire education system arises in connection with the adoption of amendments to the Law ‘On Education.’ Therefore, the integration of information and computer technologies in preschool education facilitates the modernization of the educational process and provides significant support to educators. Studies in preschool pedagogy indicate that children aged 3 to 6 are capable of successfully acquiring computer skills during this critical period of cognitive development, which prepares them for the transition from concrete-figurative thinking to abstract-logical thinking.

However, it should be noted that the education system of the Russian Federation faces a complex set of challenges, among which a priority is the creation of an educational environment capable of effectively preparing the younger generation for the conditions of life in the contemporary era. This era is characterized by features such as a high level of competition, a rational approach to decision-making, and

an emphasis on practical outcomes. In the context of these trends, it is important to establish an educational process focused on developing the child's ability to effectively adapt and navigate a rapidly changing world, where deliberation and determination acquire particular significance. The spiritual and moral education of children, fostering their ability to comprehend, empathize, and show compassion, is becoming one of the foremost priorities in education [2, p. 126].

Information and computer technologies play a crucial role in various aspects of education, including educators' activities, methodologies in preschool institutions, and cooperation with parents and society. In contemporary society, information resources are as significant as material resources, energy, and labor. Computer skills have become essential not only in primary education but also during the preschool period. These technologies significantly enhance the capabilities of parents, educators, and specialists in preschool education, facilitating the comprehensive and effective development of children's abilities [1].

Information and communication technologies, unlike traditional instructional tools, offer the potential to accomplish more than merely providing children with a large corpus of carefully selected and well-organized knowledge. They also contribute to the development of intellectual and creative skills, as well as the essential ability to independently acquire new knowledge, particularly during early childhood.

Preschool children require engaging and stimulating games and activities for their moral development. Due to the shortage of suitable materials and visual aids, computer technologies incorporating multimedia capabilities can be beneficial in this regard. However, it is important to emphasize that the computer should function as a supplement to the educator rather than as a replacement.

Undoubtedly, the preschool period plays a fundamental role in the formation of the child's personality, as it is during this time that their cognition of the world and intellectual development take place. The computer possesses significant potential for both recreational and educational objectives, yet in itself it holds no intrinsic value. Positive outcomes can only be attained through effective collaboration among the educator, the child, and the computer, ensuring appropriate interaction.

The careful selection of tasks and the use of multimedia technologies in education can increase children's motivation to learn. By employing ICT, children are initially engaged as they perceive it as a game, which progressively transforms into an educational experience. This activity facilitates the development of cognitive motivation, voluntary memory, and attention, which are essential for the formation of logical thinking skills.

Presentations, slide shows, multimedia photo albums, and interactive games constitute effective tools for improving children's comprehension of the lesson's subject matter. These resources facilitate clarity in the classroom, allowing educators to logically and scientifically explain concepts through video clips. This approach

encompasses three types of children's memory: visual, auditory, and motor. Presentations enable a systematic study of complex material, addressing both current and previous topics. They also permit a more in-depth examination of complex issues. The inclusion of animation effects can enhance children's interest in the material [5].

In utilizing audio resources for the moral development of children, emphasis can be placed on employing native musical art to elucidate the profound spiritual significance of Russian art. This art embodies faith, goodness, love, and morality. By acquainting preschool children with artistic works and encouraging their active engagement in musical activities, they are provided with the opportunity to actively cultivate their emotional, moral, aesthetic, and value-based experiences. For example, when children hear the ringing of bells and learn about the profound attachment and respect afforded to them in Orthodox Russia, they begin to comprehend that the ringing of bells embodies a significance beyond the merely literal. It appeared to reflect the essence of the Russian soul and the Russian way of life.

The range of educational opportunities provided by video recordings includes the use of digital guides to parables, fairy tales, stories, cartoons, and songs to promote the teaching of moral and spiritual values to both preschool children and their parents [6].

The use of an interactive whiteboard during lessons enables children to improve their information literacy, practical information-handling skills, and overall adaptability. This contributes to the deliberate learning of preschool children and enhances their readiness for school.

The use of an interactive whiteboard introduces a novel approach to integrating didactic games, communicative games, problem-solving scenarios, and creative tasks into educational activities. The incorporation of game elements into multimedia programs stimulates children's cognitive activity and enhances the effectiveness of educational materials. The interactive whiteboard provides the opportunity to conduct virtual excursions and organize recreational activities aimed at spiritual and ethical upbringing. For example, it is possible to take a virtual tour of Chekhov's House, participate in quizzes on topics such as 'The Don Region,' 'Cossacks,' and 'My Family,' as well as engage in various developmental games [8].

Video has numerous characteristics: it is information-rich and produces a strong emotional impact on viewers. As part of the Mother's Day celebration, an authorial film titled 'Mama — a Dear Word' may be presented, serving an important role in fostering the spiritual and moral growth — particularly with an Orthodox focus — of children and their parents. The varied educational application of video recordings can be supplemented by the teacher's electronic thematic catalog, which may include parables, fairy tales, stories, cartoons, and songs. This resource supports efforts directed toward the moral development of both preschool children and their parents [9].

The utilization of multimedia presentations ensures effective and contemporary information transfer, providing clear, vivid, prompt, and engaging instructional methods for acquiring the desired knowledge. Notable advantages include enhancement of the content and facilitation of comprehension through diverse multimedia elements, the stimulation of children's interest via dynamic and well-designed presentations, as well as rapid orientation with essential information through the adaptation of multimedia presentations to specific events.

Consequently, the integration of multimedia in lessons accelerates the delivery of information to children, enhances comprehension, facilitates the development of various cognitive functions, thereby stimulating their interest in spiritual and moral education. The use of multiple information and communication technologies, such as computers, multimedia projectors, VCRs, DVD players, televisions, record players, video cameras, and interactive whiteboards, constitutes an integral component of the pedagogical approach employing computer technologies. Moreover, interactive materials such as photographs, videos, video clips (including films, fairy tales, and cartoons), and presentations may be utilized during the lesson [4].

Consequently, it can be noted that the integration of computer technologies into the moral development process of preschool children presents several advantages:

1. Enhances the attractiveness and modernity of knowledge through appealing informational design.
2. Computer technologies contribute to the consolidation of knowledge, abilities, and skills by facilitating the resolution of cognitive and creative tasks.
3. Ensures individualized instruction.
4. Facilitates the simulation of various scenarios [3].

The pedagogical conditions for utilizing computer technologies in the moral development of preschool children in kindergarten include:

1. Age-appropriate content: the educator must ensure that the computer technologies employed are specifically developed for preschool children, with content and activities aligned with their requirements for moral development.
2. Ensure that children utilize computer technologies under the supervision and guidance of qualified educators capable of providing support and assistance as required.
3. Integrate the use of computer technologies into the kindergarten curriculum in accordance with the goals and objectives of moral development.
4. Balancing the amount of time spent in front of screens. Establishing rules that ensure a balance between the use of computer technologies and other activities, such as outdoor play, social interaction, and practical learning experiences.
5. Facilitation of collaborative and interactive experiences through computer technologies, thereby providing children with opportunities to participate alongside peers and educators in moral discussions and problem-solving activities.

6. To teach children responsible and ethical use of computer technology, including Internet safety, privacy, and respect for others.

7. Regular evaluation of the effectiveness of applying computer technologies for moral development, providing feedback to both children and educators to facilitate ongoing enhancement [7].

It is essential to recognize that the use of computer technologies must be supplemented by a balanced approach that includes other forms of moral development activities, such as storytelling, role-playing, and experiential learning.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the potential of computer technologies in the moral development of preschool children is both promising and significant. Although computers can facilitate an interactive and engaging learning process, their use should be prudent and closely supervised to ensure they reinforce moral values rather than impede them. Maintaining a balance between technology, genuine social interactions, and ethical instruction is essential for supporting preschool children in developing sound moral judgment, empathy, and responsible digital citizenship. To optimize the positive influence of computer technologies, a deliberate approach is required, entailing cooperation among educators, parents, and technology developers to produce age-appropriate and ethically informed digital content for preschool-aged children.

Therefore, the following conclusions can be formulated:

1. Moral upbringing is understood as the process of the formation of the personality and the development of moral qualities and values.

2. Moral education of preschool children possesses specific features: the moral upbringing of a child depends on the example set by adults; by virtue of their age, children are not consistently obedient, and therefore often fail to adhere to assigned rules. The moral development of preschool children can be facilitated by various means, such as art, play, and nature.

3. The potential of computer technologies also holds a significant position among the tools for moral education of preschool children, particularly in the effective and engaging delivery of important information to them.

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FOLK PROVERBIAL EDIFICATION AS AN EDUCATIONAL IMPERATIVE

Tsallagova Zarifa Borisovna

*Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Leading Research Fellow
Institute of Anthropology and Ethnography of the Russian Academy of
Sciences*

Annotation. *In ethnopedagogics, the profile of the pedagogical impact of each of the folklore forms is clearly traced. The poetic genius of the people clothed in memorable short sentences universal manifestations of universal morality, moral attitudes. This thesis explains the regularity of the existence of many coincidences of aphoristic maxims in the most distant from each other historically and geographically ethnic groups. And the brevity of their form, convenient for memorizing and reproducing, allowed them to survive for centuries, to become a repository of concentrated pedagogical knowledge, which educators from the people relied on as hypotheses, assumptions, warnings, instructions, generalizations. Methodically competent use of this material makes it an essential part of the content of modern ethno-cultural education.*

Keywords: *folklore, edification, aphorisms, proverbs, sayings, ethnopedagogy, educational impact.*

Folklore is a centuries-old form of preserving and transmitting encyclopedically comprehensive information covering all aspects and dimensions of a people's life. One of the predominant missions of folklore is educational; Folk oral-poetic creativity educated, preserved, and propagated ideological heritage, shaping behavioral stereotypes and patterns of interpersonal interaction [Khayrullin, 1993, 5–8].

A clear species-specific delineation of the pedagogical influence of each folklore form can be identified. Thus, fairy tales contain unobtrusive yet deeply perceived admonitions, introducing moral and social evaluations of human actions and their relationships. Epic works, emerging at a later developmental stage, celebrate love and devotion to the homeland, heroism, and bravery. Folk song creativity promotes the popularization and enhancement of the educational impact of the people's ethnopedagogical principles and the norms of social ethics.

Folklore works of small forms carry a distinct educational expressiveness. Proverbial admonitions (proverbs, sayings, maxims, well-wishes, parting words, etc.), extremely concise in form yet profoundly meaningful, address pressing and eternally relevant questions of morality and truth in their mutual interrelation. These two fundamental principles — cognition and morality — as well as the interconnection between the natural world and the inner world of the individual, determine the pedagogical dominant of the people's aphoristic creativity. They advocate living in accordance with the logic of nature, which harmonizes human existence. Folk aphorisms are a kind of recipe for this harmony, formulated long before the emergence of modern religions and consisting of adhering to meticulous instructions that are simple and accessible, making a person wise, benevolent, and uniquely happy [Volkov, 1999, 7–11].

Aphoristic folk creativity is an integral part of folk wisdom and a time-tested pedagogical means of influence, which explains its strong educational imperative. The high educational value of this material, which has become the subject of close scrutiny by paremiologists in recent decades — who have identified the subtlest nuances of its artistic, rhythmic, and ethnological nature — can be appreciated within the domain of ethnopedagogical science. Folk aphorisms have been scarcely regarded as a remarkable educational phenomenon; this is largely explained by the lack of a theoretical foundation for such research and the underdevelopment of fundamental theoretical and terminological concepts.

Meanwhile, the issue of researching the theory and practice of the functioning of small forms of folklore, including proverbial admonitions, is especially relevant for ethnopädagogy, as it allows one to recognize in this material one of the effective educational resources. In aphoristic sayings, the pedagogical experience and educational ideas of the people are presented in a figurative form. Many customs, traditions, and everyday life regulations were embedded in sayings and proverbs, while individual ritual formulas and paremic expressions harmoniously intertwined within the syncretic framework of the folkloric phenomenon.

In a non-literate environment, over the centuries, a rigorous selection of the most expedient positive elements and the best educational examples, constituting the moral and pedagogical potential of the people, has taken place. Many of these have taken shape in linguistic practice as proverbial expressions and nationally specific aphoristic admonitions. In all of them, the manifestation of universal human morality and ethical attitudes is clearly discernible. This thesis explains the consistent occurrence of numerous similarities among didactic sententiae in ethnically and geographically widely separated peoples.

The special semantic significance of paremic teachings lies in the fact that an aphoristically expressed folk instruction is essentially the result of a spiral turn of information, which includes the statement and generalization of numerous facts

and examples, their analysis and abstraction, and finally, a renewed return to concreteness, though now to artistic concreteness. The figurative concretization of each folk aphoristic instruction thus embraces an enormous amount of information, transformed through mental activity into the smallest possible volume. As a rule, it is one sentence, rarely a single speech segment. The relationship between the actualizing situation and the proverbial saying can be clearly illustrated by comparing it to the relationship between the content of a book and its title.

Such a concise and convenient form for memorization and reproduction, into which pedagogical wisdom was densely packed, enabled its preservation across centuries, becoming a repository of concentrated pedagogical knowledge upon which folk educators relied as hypotheses, axioms, and conclusions that inventory the experience of folk education. This circumstance facilitated the memorization, use, and transmission of information from generation to generation; however, on the other hand, it now complicates the interpretation of meaning, as, by the will of historical fate, admonitory statements have fallen out of the context that originally generated them.

Functioning as, in a sense, a conclusion or moral teaching derived from complex and extensive heroic-epic, fairy-tale, and song genres, proverbial admonitions coexisted alongside these forms, finding within them the development and elucidation of their ideas and imagery; As speech formulas, they accompanied folk customs and rituals, as well as rules of etiquette. Aphorisms, thus, were a significant structural element of the holistic system of traditional education, all components of which are closely interconnected. The disruption of these connections, the disappearance of folkloric, festive, and ritual traditions from active life — traditions in which each representative of the succeeding generation was involved as a subject — and the forgetting of historical and commemorative events associated with them, lead to the loss not only of the educational functions of aphoristic means; at times, the very essence becomes difficult to determine, and the nuanced shades of meaning are leveled.

The correct interpretation of such sayings excludes dogmatism, offers food for thought, and largely depends on prior familiarity with the meaning of the saying, on mastery of a distinctive aphoristic cipher. This conclusion is supported by the analysis of extensive aphoristic materials from various ethnic traditions conducted by authors of authoritative works in the field of paremiology, the science of minor folklore forms: G. L. Permyakova, A. Dandis, M. Kussi, A. Taylor, E. Kenges-Marandu, E. Ya. Kokare, and others [3]. There is also the view that the primary purpose of certain paremiological units is the exchange of coded signs and symbols; specifically, to establish whether the participants in communication share the same cultural-linguistic code. This semiotic nature and brevity of form facilitate perception and memorization but complicate decoding. A successful and accurate interpretation of the pedagogical thought concentrated in an aphorism depends on whether a person ‘... possesses a key sufficiently adequate and flexible’ [1, pp.

25–27]. The emblematic character of folk aphorisms is closely connected to their inherent phenomenon of folklore variability, which is characterized by constant movement and change alongside the preservation of an invariant foundation. Moreover, sometimes the invariant itself is defined by the sum of its transformations.

Frequent use of proverbial exhortations in everyday speech endows it with imagery, figurativeness, and vividness. Such imagery, imparting a particular ‘Eastern’ color to the language, makes it expressive and pedagogically effective: ‘With just one word, I turn a coward into a brave man, a defender of his people; a thief into an honest person; no swindler dares to appear before my eyes...’ — this is how one of the Kabardian *geguako* — folk storytellers — defines the goal and strength of his creativity [2, p. 88]. The brief form of proverbial admonitions determines their coherent structure: the interrelation of their plan of expression and plan of content, where the didactic content, a complete thought, is expressed in a concise yet rich artistic form.

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VALUES OF ETHNIC CULTURE IN MEANINGFUL LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

Nyudyurmagomedov Abdulakhad Nyudyurmagomedovich

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Dagestan State University, Makhachkala, Russia

Abstract. *The article examines and justifies the necessity of integrating ethnic values into the university educational process to cultivate students' ability to construct their own meaning of the studied phenomena and the knowledge about them. One of the effective means proposed for this purpose is the use of meaningful learning technologies that promote the creation of a dialogue within the educational process between the values of ethnic culture and scientific knowledge, viewed from diverse perspectives of students' understanding and assessment.*

Keywords: *ethnic cultural values, educational process, meaningful technologies, students' independent thoughts and meanings*

Future societal plans emphasize the necessity of preparing viable youth distinguished by a solid, consciously formed foundational culture, professional mobility, a high level of responsible social activity, alternative thinking, and an optimistic outlook on life. Moreover, each young individual, mastering the aforementioned qualities, should be capable of understanding and advocating for the interests of their social, professional, and ethnic community. Researchers consider that the creation of pedagogical conditions and the search for approaches to the successful ethno-cultural adaptation of students are important within the multicultural environment of the university, taking into account contemporary development trends [1].

This approach to the organization of a regional university presupposes two positions: the established (traditional, significant) and the mobile (alternative and meaningful). Undoubtedly, both of these positions should interact in the development of the university. Thus, Korotova O. G. argues that the university, as part of the global cultural and educational community, should engage in the preservation, development, and dissemination of the cultures of the peoples of the region [3]. From this perspective, the ethnocultural orientation of the university's activities

can encourage students to recognize the importance of preserving and developing the ethnocultural heritage of their peoples and to foster a deeper understanding of the knowledge they study [2].

However, despite the established market relations and the declared freedom within social relations, professional education continues to focus on a basic, stable technological level of specialist training. Naturally, it is necessary to take into account a number of objective factors that negatively affect the initiative and activity of young people: the lack of clear long-term goals in society, difficulties with employment, the predominantly entertainment-oriented sociocultural life, expectations of quick and easy benefits in life, reluctance to overcome challenges, social and cognitive passivity, and so forth.

Practical observations demonstrate that it is very challenging to embed within the higher education pedagogical environment a model of a student who thinks critically, doubts, questions, argues, and constructs their own meaning of what is occurring and what is anticipated in their future social life and professional activities.

One of the effective means of organizing such an educational environment is the use of the values of ethnic culture in regional universities with a multinational student composition. This issue is particularly relevant in faculties of native languages and cultures. At the same time, it should be noted that, in addition to professional objectives, higher education institutions fulfill general cultural functions. However, the specific characteristics of the sociocultural environment in which the university operates, as well as the ethnocultural characteristics of the students, are insufficiently represented.

An analysis of established concepts of ethnocultural education shows that researchers in each regard culture as the primary means of education, although each individual understands it differently. For us, culture represents not only the totality of all values attained by each people and humanity worldwide but also a quality characterized by a high level of personal development and education, which enables an individual to adapt to the socio-cultural environment. Within this framework, culture among different peoples, despite many common features, possesses its own specificity, uniqueness, and distinctiveness. Education, the ultimate goal of which is to develop a highly qualified specialist with cultural identity and civic responsibility, can be defined as nationally oriented and ethno-cultural. At the same time, this term is unequivocally accepted in relation to general education, as a national school with native language instruction has long existed. The uniqueness of the Dagestan national school is that within a single republic, schools operate in fourteen languages, and there exists a pedagogical institute studying these languages, their methodologies, and means of instruction in schools.

However, in practice, native language instruction is provided only in the primary grades within areas of concentrated settlement of a single ethnic group. During the

period of study from fifth to eleventh grade, students encounter elements of national culture, and often the broader Dagestani culture, only sporadically in subjects such as “Culture and Traditions of the Peoples of Dagestan,” “Dagestani Literature,” “History of Dagestan,” and “Geography of Dagestan” [10]. In this context, issues of intercultural and interlinguistic interaction among the peoples inhabiting the republic, in conjunction with the development of interactive culture, are becoming increasingly relevant in Dagestan.

To determine the initial state of the problem, we surveyed approximately 500 senior high school students and first- and second-year students from various universities across the republic. Our interest lay in their attitudes towards the overall culture as well as towards specific spiritual and moral values characteristic of the lives of particular ethno-cultural groups in Dagestan. The results indicated that 46% of the youth preferred Dagestani culture, 19% identified with ethno-cultural values, and 16% favored global culture. With respect to individual spiritual and moral values, the following preferences were revealed: benevolence — 70%, truthfulness — 47%, compassion — 58%, politeness — 57%, modesty — 52%, courage — 67%, conscientiousness — 52%, perseverance — 41%, and sincerity — 38%.

In general, the comparative analysis of the examined results suggests that only about half of young people are able to appreciate the role of their ethnic cultural values in their personal lives. Even among them, such important qualities emphasized in folk traditions — truthfulness, sincerity, and persistence in achieving one’s goals through personal labor — received the lowest ratings (ranging from 38% to 47%). These data indicate that it remains difficult to assert the substantial quality of training specialists with ethnocultural competence and an understanding of the university educational process as a sociocultural space.

However, despite the established market relations and the declared freedom within social relations, professional education continues to focus on a basic, stable technological level of specialist training. Naturally, it is necessary to take into account a number of objective factors that negatively affect the initiative and activity of young people: the lack of clear long-term goals in society, difficulties with employment, the predominantly entertainment-oriented sociocultural life, expectations of quick and easy benefits in life, reluctance to overcome challenges, social and cognitive passivity, and so forth.

Practical observations demonstrate that it is very challenging to embed within the higher education pedagogical environment a model of a student who thinks critically, doubts, questions, argues, and constructs their own meaning of what is occurring and what is anticipated in their future social life and professional activities.

The obtained characteristics of students’ attitudes toward their identification with the ethnocultural environment of the national region gain particular importance in meaningful technologies for training mobile specialists, which are distinguished

by the accommodation of diverse ways of understanding the world, variability in knowledge and methods of activity, the distinctiveness of national character and mastery of known means of subsistence, engagement in innovative ideas, and a variety of situations stimulating personal initiative and self-expression [4]. Such educational technologies foster an atmosphere of intercultural dialogue, social responsibility, intellectual engagement, and the self-realization of specialists' potential within the university.

The key reference points of this approach to the interactive university environment are the categories of 'meaning' and 'sense' of the knowledge being studied. Meaning, as is well known, is associated with established, traditional classical experience and culture, with which we familiarize future specialists, cultivating their skills of professional work according to established models of classical education and production technologies.

Meaning, emerging based on familiar experience, leads the student to new ideas and thoughts, into a different educational, professional, and social environment with which they associate their successful and secure future. Accordingly, we define as meaning-constituting those educational technologies that stimulate students' efforts to express their attitudes, opinions, understanding, and the significance of known knowledge and modes of activity. Meaning is created through the formation of conditions within the educational process whereby students become engaged in generating the significance of the studied knowledge and modes of activity. Involvement, experiences, reflections, and intellectual difficulties are factors in the development of students' cognitive processes. Therefore, meaning-creating educational technologies enable tracing the qualitative changes occurring in students' development under the influence of education.

Based on this essential characterization of meaningful learning technologies and their implementation methods within national education systems, we have put forward the following principles for stimulating students' free thinking and meaning creation:

1. The principle of being educated, which implies demonstrating the ability to use the knowledge and experience acquired through education to freely explain phenomena and processes in nature and society.

2. The principle of meaning-oriented activity, which requires transforming the educational process so that each student seeks to understand the specifics of their cognitive processes and endeavors to provide their own interpretation of the acquired knowledge.

3. The principle of freedom of choice among various task options or methods of completion, which are more appealing or closer to one's life experience, interests, or cognitive style.

4. The principle of differentiation, which requires involving students in the process of identifying and explaining the essential properties and structural relationships of the studied phenomena.

5. The principle of complementarity, which enables each student to construct the completion of every task based on their own thoughts, ideas, and projects.

6. The principle of role-playing, which involves comparing each student's ideas with those of others and developing the skills to establish constructive relationships with peers and opponents.

7. The principle of self-organization, which directs the student to transform existing knowledge in its contradiction and to mobilize their own cognitive efforts to the level of overcoming learning difficulties.

Based on the characteristics of the utilized tools and their potential to stimulate students' meaning-making, our study developed eight types of meaning-generating educational tasks and the technologies for their implementation:

- variable tasks granting students the right to choose both the content and methods of their completion;

- assignments for analyzing the educational situation by key words method with variations in students' interpretations during responses;

- methods for cognitive reflection on associative educational material;

- methods of incompleteness and complementarity in tasks or their execution;

- approaches fostering dialogical equality among participants during problem discussions;

- brainstorming methods involving students supplementing and justifying their own new ideas, meanings, and projects;

- technologies of role-based educational cognition [5]. In each of these technologies, students have the opportunity to express their energetic and intellectual potential, formed within the socio-cultural environment under the influence of national consciousness and culture. By observing students' thoughts, actions, and meanings, educators obtain guidance for exploring diverse approaches in explaining, acquiring new knowledge, and methods of its evaluation aimed at fostering students' identification with their ethnic group.

Students encounter the distinction between sense and meaning in education, as well as their roles in comprehension and development, during classroom classes. The extensive time and content required for material assimilation compel the lecturer to employ traditional and conservative forms of lecture sessions. In our approach, lectures are restructured based on motivational, structural, and orientational-evaluative components and technologies. We propose a slightly different structure for lecture construction:

- a) any new knowledge is presented by the lecturer based on variable, contradictory, uncertain, and unexpected situations;

b) a brainstorming process regarding this situation generates diverse student interpretations, and through their comparison and generalization, new knowledge is formulated;

c) lecture notes are recorded at the level of proper, true, and objectified knowledge;

d) the instructor's explanations assist students in aligning their understanding with knowledge in its true meaning;

d) the instructor demonstrates the logical structure of material presentation that students should follow in their answers and reflections;

e) the instructor leaves several statements without detailed explanation, assigning students the task of independent inquiry.

This technology facilitates the development of students' abilities for concretization and generalization, abstraction and elaboration, distinguishing between sense and meaning, and articulating the specificity of their understanding.

During seminars and practical classes, students prepare responses in accordance with competency requirements, necessitating the completion of tasks of various types:

- at the beginning of each session, students complete independent work to demonstrate their comprehension and the meaning of the key concepts of the topic, and they receive grades based on the results;

- for the session, each student prepares theses answering one of the topic's questions on a single page, written with line spacing. They respond based on these theses within 5–6 minutes, commenting on each thesis with their own arguments. This way, they learn to clarify knowledge by expressing their own opinions, comparing and proposing different approaches, and demonstrating various analogies and options for the practical application of knowledge;

- each session concludes with a homework assignment that requires the application of the acquired knowledge and reflection on issues that were not fully addressed during the session;

Assessment of students' academic achievements is conducted at various levels:

- general understanding, comparison, differentiation, and identification of essential features, properties, and functions of knowledge;

- identification of the depth of understanding and establishment of significant connections between phenomena;

- transformation, expansion, and transfer to analogous situations;

- generation of original ideas and projects that enhance existing knowledge or its application;

- improvisation as the capacity for self-realization and the demonstration of changes occurring within oneself under the influence of learning;

Only such a system of purposeful technologies will enable students to produce their own meanings of the studied knowledge based on ethnic culture and

sociocultural experience. Our research has demonstrated the expediency of integrating the following connections between professional training and essential components of national and regional culture into the pedagogical process of a regional university:

- essential inherent natural forces and capacities aimed at acquiring a profession must be understood by students as their contribution to the future of their republic and nation;

- in national professional education systems, the teacher's work at the level of universal human culture should interact with the collaborative search by teachers and students for analogues between national and universal human culture, along with students' reflective activity in shaping their professional identity as representatives of a specific people;

- interaction between national traditional patterns of diligence and new ideas, meanings, and development projects of forms of national crafts traditional to the peoples of the region;

- use of dialogical communication forms and role-playing formats in educational activities as a condition for acquiring integrative experience;

- utilization of sociocultural mechanisms for regulating public behavior as a means of fostering specialists' responsibility for national issues of life arrangement.

Under such conditions of the educational process, it is possible to form traits of national character specific to ethnoculture, among which we highlight:

- the rational and practical nature of social life among mountaineers in the villages;

- a spirit of competitiveness and the testing of youth in physical endurance, mental agility, moral strictness, and emotional openness;

- adaptability to the natural rhythms of a measured and calm life;

- relationships of reverence and respect toward parents, elders, and the helpless;

- a constant striving for knowledge and respect for the educated, the scholar;

- inviolability of honor, sanctity of duty, faithfulness to one's word, defense of dignity, and the ability to overcome difficulties and dangers.

These foundations enable the formulation of a set of requirements for the implementation of meaning-generating educational technologies as a means of preparing students to preserve and advance ethnic culture:

1. To be oriented towards the development of students capable of freely engaging with the diversity of ways to understand and explain the phenomena of the world and the knowledge about them.

2. To possess the methodology, tools, and mechanisms for constructing meaning-generating educational technologies specific to one's academic disciplines.

3. To be able to create an open and trusting atmosphere of educational learning and supportive relationships between the instructor and students, which assists

students in understanding who they are, what they experience during classes, the extent of their autonomous development, and the challenges they face in self-identifying with their ethnic group.

4. To be capable of deliberately and purposefully creating 'support groups,' idea generators, and initiators of reflection and dialogue.

5. The ability to foster within a team an atmosphere of intercultural exchange, creative engagement, and an emotional environment conducive to open communication.

6. To master at least three different approaches to explaining fundamental scientific knowledge and to be prepared to resolve internal epistemic contradictions.

7. To possess skills in diagnosing and monitoring positive changes occurring in students during meaning-making activities.

8. To enable students to become participants in the collaborative pursuit of new knowledge by engaging them in scientific research technologies.

10. Be ready for continual reflection on one's own activities and on students' work aimed at their awareness as subjects of intercultural communication.

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SCULPTURE IS ONE OF THE LEADING DISCIPLINES IN THE TEACHING OF ARTISTIC BONE CARVING AT THE RUSSIAN UNIVERSITY OF TRADITIONAL ART AND CRAFTS

Karatayeva Nina Fodorovna

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, member of the Union of Artists of the Russian Federation,

Professor

Russian University of Traditional Arts and Crafts,

St. Petersburg, Russia

Abstract: *the article briefly provides historical background of the development of bone carving art in Russia, tells about the connection between sculpture and bone carving art and its importance in the professional training of students of the Higher School of Folk Arts (Academy) in the department of “Artistic Bone Carving”. Emphasis is placed on the creation of new programs in sculpture taking into account this specialization of students.*

Keywords: *sculpture, study, bone carving, Higher School of Folk Arts, program, traditional applied art, classes, teaching.*

Professional training of future artists of traditional applied art in the direction of “Artistic bone carving” is based on the classical form of sculpture training. This direction is closer than other traditional crafts to academic volumetric and relief sculpture. A bone carver who does not know how to sculpt and who has a poor perception of the shape of the depicted objects will never become a virtuoso master of bone carving. Even with good artistic abilities, a future carver must constantly train his eyes and hands in sculpting and carving. In bone carving, a person is often depicted, this is evident in the works of masters of artistic bone carving, in order to achieve the highest skill for this you need to do many sketches from life and have a good knowledge of anatomy. For students of the bone carving specialty, new programs and textbooks on academic sculpture, anatomy, drawing, design (composition) are created at the Higher School of Folk Arts (Academy), but in the general program of the Academy few hours are devoted to sculpture. Bone carving sculpture should become one of the main disciplines in teaching bone carving art, and not be considered a variable subject. In the Higher School of Folk

Arts (Academy), of the many areas of artistic carving, Kholmogory bone carving is taught, which differs from other craft centers in its elegance, fine lace openwork, variety of forms and compositions, closely related to relief and volumetric sculpture of small forms.

It is impossible to imagine the development of Kholmogory bone carving without linking it with centers that have deep roots in the cultural layers of not only ancient Rus', but also world culture. Academician B. A. Rybakov, relying on archaeological excavations, claimed that the beginning and sources of the development of Russian folk traditional art go back thousands of years and absorbed the culture of many peoples. The development of the crafts of Ancient Rus' was influenced by the religious art of Byzantium. In 988–990, Rus' adopted Eastern Orthodoxy, for this reason, for several centuries, it began to experience the comprehensive influence of Byzantium in the field of philosophy, theology, education, book culture, architecture, icon painting, sculpture and bone carving. The heyday of carved Byzantine bone icons came in the 10th–11th centuries. Byzantine relief bone works have survived to this day, which are two ivory plates fastened together in the form of a book (Fig. 1, 2).

Fig. 1. Bone carving. .
Byzantium, 10th — 11th centuries.

Fig. 2. Bone carving,
Byzantium, 10th — 11th centuries

Byzantine influence had a direct impact on the art of Ancient Rus, including the development of sculpture and sculpture-like art, bone carving and wood carving, since the task of religious art was to reflect spirituality, and bodily image was tacitly denied, for this reason, three-dimensional sculptural images of a person were rarely used in ancient Russian churches and cathedrals, mainly sculpture was presented in artistic relief inserts in architecture, in carved altars and on household items in the form of ornaments. The adoption of Orthodoxy and the desire to

depict only the spiritual in the religious art of Rus' led to the rejection of a realistic depiction of a person in painting and sculpture and extended the heyday of these arts until the 18th century, almost until the opening of the Imperial Academy of Arts in Russia in 1757, unlike Western countries, where painting, sculpture and bone carving developed very quickly. In Western works of art of all kinds, in many works a person was realistically depicted. The materials used for bone carving in ancient times and at present are horns of ungulates (deer, elk, cow, maral, etc.), tubular shinbones of large ungulates — tarsus (camel, cow, horse), mammoth or elephant tusks, sperm whale teeth, walrus tusk, rhinoceros horn, narwhal horn were also used. The size and density of the materials determined the size and quality of the products carved from them, therefore bone carvings are mostly small in size, varied and unique in compositional designs, we will give examples of Russian bone carvers from different regions of the country. The main schools of carving that have developed in Russia are: Kholmogory, Tobolsk, Chukotka, Chukchi-Eskimo, Yakut (Fig. 3–13).

Fig. 3. Comb
Kholmogory,
Russian Federation

Fig. 4. Fan
Kholmogory,
Russian Federation

Fig. 5. Carriage
Kholmogory,
Russian Federation

Fig. 6. Kholmogory,
Russian Federation

Fig. 7. Kholmogory,
Russian Federation

Fig. 8. Tobolsk, Russian Federation.

Fig. 9. Tobolsk, Russian Federation Fig. 10. Tobolsk, Russian Federation

Rice. 11. Chukotka, Yamal. RF

Fig. 12. Yakutia, Russian Federation

Rice. 13. Yakutia, Russian Federation

The first art schools in Rus' were founded by the Byzantines, or Russian masters trained in Byzantium. In Kievan Rus' of the 9th-13th centuries, religious art reached a fairly high level and influenced the entire way of life. Bone carving in Russia began to develop rapidly from the 12th to the 19th century, when the main artistic centers of Russian carving gradually formed, especially in ancient Novgorod, where many ancient artistic bone products were found during archaeological research.

The construction of the city of St. Petersburg on the banks of the Neva and the resettlement of the nobility were accompanied by orders for the creation of paintings, sculptures and the manufacture of rich, elegant bone items for the imperial court and its entourage. In several places at once, industrial centers of bone carving were created, which began to develop actively.

The heyday of Russian bone carving crafts dates back to approximately the 16th — 19th centuries (Fig. 14). We will turn to the most interesting and unusual Kholmogory craft, since the Higher School of Folk Arts (Academy) currently teaches Northern Russian Kholmogory artistic carving.

Fig. 14. Kholmogory bone carving, Russia, 16th-19th centuries.

The Kholmogory craft developed rapidly, fueled by the vibrant cultural and commercial life of the Russian north and commissions from the nobility. The development of the style was influenced by cultural interactions with the major art centers of Novgorod, Moscow, and St. Petersburg. The Russian port of Arkhangelsk played a significant role in northern trade from the second half of the 16th century. Craftsmen sold their works in Arkhangelsk, where they also drew inspiration and were influenced by the carvings and artworks brought by European merchants on ships. The first written mention of Kholmogory carvers dates back to the 17th century. The main works of Kholmogory craftsmen were household items: combs, bracelets, boxes, snuffboxes, secretaries, tabletop chests of drawers, clock stands, and portrait plaques. The works of northern carvers were highly prized; some were exhibited in the Armory Chamber in Moscow and the new capital, St. Petersburg, and later in the Hermitage. Others became part of the everyday life

of wealthy nobles. The carver had to find the most expressive, clear, and precise silhouette in harmonious unity with the shape and size of the bone blank, then apply the engraving or carving. If the design on the piece was skillfully composed, plastically modeled, and cleanly cut, complementing and embellishing the form of the object, this demonstrated the carver's skill and artistic ability. Northern Russian bone carving is characterized by a rare miniature quality that has become traditional. Kholmogory carving achieves refinement, filigree, and lacy openwork, distinguishing it from other bone carving centers, creating the distinctive characteristics of this style. In the 20th century, after the Revolution, in 1934, the Presidium of the All-Russian Central Executive Committee adopted a special resolution on the activities and development of Kholmogory carving. In 1937, Kholmogory carvings received a "Gold Medal Diploma" at an international exhibition in Paris. The Kholmogory school, closely linked to academic sculpture and not shying away from complex thematic compositions depicting human figures, became a classic of bone carving, the principles of which have been the teachings of many generations of bone carvers (Figs. 15–22).

Ris. 15.
Brosh's olenyami.

Ris. 16. Mat's rebonkom

Ris. 17. Brosh's olenyami

Ris. 18. Bibleyskiy syuzhet

Ris. 19. Korobochka.

Ris. 20. Portret

Ris. 21. Kholmogorskaya rez'ba po kosti, Rossiya,

Ris. 22. Kholmogorskaya rez'ba po kosti, Rossiya

In 2003, to support and further develop traditional folk crafts, the Higher School of Folk Arts (now an academy) was opened by decree of the Russian government. It is the only educational institution in Russia that teaches traditional folk crafts, headed by Doctor of Sciences and Honored Teacher Valentina Fedorovna Maksimovich. Because no other institution offering traditional folk arts education existed prior to the academy's opening, teachers at the academy create their own unique programs and textbooks. These programs are constantly updated, improved, updated with new assignments, and tested during teaching. The general educational program for all areas of traditional applied art includes the study of artistic subjects: sculpture, plastic anatomy, drawing, painting, composition, design, modeling, craftsmanship, and art history. These subjects have their own specifics depending on the specialization of students studying at the Higher School of Folk Arts (academy). Teaching the fundamentals of sculpture to future artists in traditional applied arts for many years has shown that sculpture programs depend on the number of hours allocated to this discipline by the Ministry of Education, with particularly few hours allocated to the specializations of artistic bone carving and wood carving.

Of all traditional disciplines, bone carving is most closely related to academic three-dimensional and relief sculpture. Old masters, before carving their work from bone, sculpted a model of it, and the better the master conveyed the shape and proportions in the sculpting, the better, more competently, and more qualitatively the work would be carved in the material. This has created an objective need to develop teaching methods and create innovative curricula and a textbook for academic sculpture that will take into account the specific training of future artistic bone carvers and allocate more hours to this discipline for specializations related to three-dimensional and relief sculpture. To this end, new educational assignments in sculpture are being developed, accompanied by visual teaching aids and display stands, educational charts, and photo albums on lesson topics. Students' coursework from the methodological collection is used as exhibitions, enriching the pedagogical process and increasing the effectiveness of sculpture teaching. However, all these efforts will be useless in training bone carvers if they have few hours of sculpture instruction and little time to sculpt and practice sculpting birds, animals, and humans, images of which are abundant in their works.

The specific nature of sculpture training lies in the need to teach techniques for sculpting volumes and reliefs, their stylization, the decorative execution of compositions, and the development of students' decorative and figurative language when creating molded models for future projects, which are dominated by small-scale sculpture. The educational goal is to gradually develop students' professional knowledge and skills in sculpting and to apply this knowledge in artistic bone carving.

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IMPROVEMENT OF POSTURAL STABILITY INDICATORS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL-AGE CHILDREN WITH MILD MENTAL RETARDATION BASED ON THE USE OF THE STABILAN 01-2 HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE SYSTEM

Mezentsev Viktor Vladimirovich

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

Far Eastern State Academy of Physical Culture

Vorobyova Olga Sergeevna

Adaptive physical education teacher

Regional State Budgetary General Educational Institution Boarding

School No. 4,

Khabarovsk, Russia

Abstract. *The study found that the use of a method including exercises to develop coordination skills according to the A. A. Dmitriev method and the developed adaptive outdoor games in combination with the use of stabilographic training games on the Stabilan 01–2 hardware and software complex in an experimental group of primary school-aged children with mild mental retardation improved the quality of the balance function in the Romberg test, while there was a decrease in oscillatory movements in the frontal and sagittal planes, a decrease in the speed of movement of the center of pressure and a decrease in the support area on the stabiloplatform, which influenced the improvement of certain coordination skills.*

Keywords: *Children with mild mental retardation, Romberg test, postural stability, coordination abilities, neurophysiological diagnostics, balance function quality, Stabilan 01–2 hardware and software system, stabilographic training games*

Introduction

Physical education for children with intellectual disabilities generally has a positive impact on their health, helps develop important personality traits, and prepares children for successful, independent life in society. It is important to pay particular attention to coordination skills.

Children with intellectual disabilities most clearly exhibit deficiencies in the development of coordination skills [2]. Coordination skills play an important role

in controlling human movement, specifically, coordinating and organizing diverse motor actions into a unified whole in accordance with the assigned motor task.

Coordination skills are controlled by those biological and mental functions that are defective in children with intellectual disabilities (the more severe the impairment, the more severe the coordination errors) [3].

Due to the existing organic damage to individual brain structures and the uncoordinated interaction of the regulatory and executive organs, children with intellectual disabilities are unable to simultaneously control all their functions.

Developing coordination skills in children with intellectual disabilities is a pressing issue, aimed at developing a foundation of motor skills and abilities as a prerequisite and basis for the successful development of other physical abilities and social adaptation in general.

Therefore, the most promising approach currently offers a comprehensive approach to developing the coordination skills of children with intellectual disabilities. This approach is based on the use of hardware and software systems for psychophysiological and neurophysiological monitoring. This will make the development of their coordination skills manageable and significantly improve the effectiveness of physical education classes in adaptive physical education at school.

One such hardware and software system, based on neurophysiological diagnostics, can be used to assess the functional state of the systems maintaining upright posture at rest or to assess postural stability indicators. The “Stabilan 01–2” stabilometric platform can be used. Improving postural stability indicators, which characterize the state of the human vestibular system, can significantly influence the development and formation of coordination abilities in primary school-aged children with mild intellectual disabilities.

Consequently, the aim of our study is to use stabilographic training games on the Stabilan 01–2 hardware and software system in a method for developing coordination abilities in primary school-aged children with mild intellectual disabilities to improve postural stability indicators.

1. The experimental part

To achieve the stated goal of the study, a pedagogical experiment was conducted from November 2024 to May 2025 at the Khabarovsk State Budgetary Educational Institution School of Physical Education No. 4 and in the Laboratory of Biomechanics and Human Functional Capabilities of the Far Eastern State Academy of Physical Culture in Khabarovsk. Five boys and two girls participated in the experiment. The experimental group of children studied according to A. A. Dmitriev’s method three times a week for 40 minutes, with the inclusion of exercises to develop coordination skills in the third physical education lesson at school, as well as specially developed adapted outdoor games and stabilometric training games

on the Stabilan 01–2 stabiloplatform in the Laboratory of Biomechanics and Human Functional Capabilities of the Far Eastern State Academy of Physical Culture [1]. To assess postural stability in children with mild intellectual disabilities, the Romberg test was used on the Stabilan 01–2 hardware and software system. This allowed us to evaluate the state of the upright posture maintenance systems under various sensory system conditions. To improve postural stability, the stabilometric training games “Balls” and “Hunt” were used.

The goal of the “Balls” game is to score as many points as possible while minimizing errors. The playing field consists of three baskets, a ball, and a cursor. When the game starts, the ball appears at the top of the playing field. When the ball appears, one of the baskets changes color.

The selected basket can be in any of three positions, which change randomly when the ball is placed. The patient’s task is to grab the ball with the cursor, which represents the position of the patient’s center of pressure on the stabiloplatform, and place it in the basket.

To grab the ball, the patient must align the cursor with the ball. To align the ball and the center of pressure, the patient must smoothly shift their body weight from one foot to the other, onto the toes of both feet, or onto the toes of each foot, depending on the game situation. To place the ball in the basket, the cursor with the ball in hand must align with the highlighted basket, shifting to the heel of each foot or both feet together, depending on the position of the highlighted basket. Correctly completing the game (placing the ball in the highlighted basket) awards 1 point. Incorrect completion (placing the ball in the gray basket) increases the number of errors.

The goal of the “Hunt” game is to score as many points as possible while making a minimum of errors. The playing field consists of a target and a cursor representing the position of the patient’s center of pressure on the stabiloplatform. The default target in this game is a bird. The child’s task is to keep the cursor on the target at a large zoom level. If the child completes the task correctly, the cursor remains green. When the cursor moves off the target, its color turns red. Moving the cursor off the target increases the number of errors. If the score reaches (100 points) or (–50) errors, the training session ends, regardless of the recording time. The difficulty level of the game task can be adjusted by zooming in or out. Success is determined by the overall ratio of points scored to errors made. The more points the child scores, the better the game was played [4].

2. Results

In the experimental group of primary school-aged children, a comparative intragroup analysis of postural stability indicators after the experiment revealed significant improvements across all indicators ($p < 0,05$) (Table 1). The largest percentage increase was observed in the average speed of the center of pressure

with eyes open and closed (32,5%). There was a significant decrease in speed by 3,9 mm/sec with eyes open and by 5.1 mm/sec with eyes closed, and in the area of the confidence ellipse with eyes open and closed (43% and 31,5%, respectively). There was a significant decrease in the area of support on the stabiloplatform by 103 mm² with eyes open and by 79,6 mm² with eyes closed ($p < 0,05$).

In the experimental group of primary school-aged children, significant differences ($p < 0,05$) were observed across all parameters on the “Balls” simulator (Table 2). The largest increases were observed in the number of points scored (6 points) (a 54,5% increase), speed at the catch stage (mm/sec) (39,66 mm/sec) (a 40,7% increase), and speed at the catch stage (mm/sec) (a 41% increase) ($p < 0,05$).

Table 1. Comparative analysis of postural stability indicators of primary school-age children in the experimental group during the experiment

Indicators	Experimental group				difference in units		percentage increase		P
	before the experiment	after the experiment	before the experiment	after the experiment	open eyes	closed eyes	open eyes	closed eyes	
	open eyes M±m	open eyes M±m	closed eyes M±m	closed eyes M±m					
V _{ep} , MM/cek	12,0±1,3	8,1±0,8	15,7±2,5	10,6±1,0	3,9	5,1	32,5	32,5	<0,05
S _{Ellip} , MM ²	239,6±53,9	136,6±20	253±63,8	173,4±33,6	103	79,6	43	31,5	<0,05
KФP, %	113±7,6		144±5,2		31		27,4		<0,05
Qx, MM	4,1±0,8	2,9±0,3	4,3±0,5	3,3±0,5	1,2	1	29,3	23,3	<0,05
Qy, MM	5,4±0,7	4,3±0,5	6,6±1,0	5,0±0,5	1,1	1,6	20,4	24,3	<0,05

Table 2. Performance indicators on the “Balls” simulator for primary school-age children in the experimental group during the experiment

Balls simulator	Experimental group M±m		difference in units	percentage increase	P
	before the experiment	after the experiment			
Number of points scored	11±1,5	17±1,0	6	54,5	<0,05
Number of errors, times	3,0±0,6	2,3±0,8	0,7	23,3	<0,05
Capture interval duration, sec	4,55±0,4	3,03±0,3	1,52	33,4	<0,05
Duration of the laying interval, sec	4,14±0,8	3,19±0,6	0,95	23	<0,05

Speed at the capture stage, mm/sec	97,42±9,7	137,08±18,4	39,66	40,7	<0,05
Speed at the laying stage, mm/sec	99,86±11,9	140,82±13,9	40,96	41	<0,05

In the experimental group of primary school-aged children, significant differences were observed across all indicators on the “Cubes” simulator during the course of the experiment ($p < 0,05$) (Table 3). The number of points scored significantly improved by 8.6 points (a 25,1 % increase), while the playing time (seconds) significantly decreased by 20,6 (a 23,2 % increase) ($p < 0,05$).

Table 3. Performance indicators on the “Cubes” simulator for primary school-age children in the experimental group during the experiment

Indicators	Experimental group		difference in units	percentage increase	P
	before the experiment M±m	after the experiment M±m			
Number of points scored	-34,3±6,4	-25,7±5,6	8,6	25,1	<0,05
Game time, sec	88,9±10,1	68,3±15,4	20,6	23,2	<0,05

3. Conclusions

Thus, training in an experimental group of primary school-aged children with mild intellectual disabilities using the developed experimental integrated methodology, including exercises to develop coordination skills according to A. A. Dmitrieva’s methodology and the developed adaptive outdoor games, combined with the use of stabilographic training games on the Stabilan 01–2 hardware and software system, improved the postural stability of children with mild intellectual disabilities, which resulted in improvements in certain coordination skills. The use of stabilographic training games on the Stabilan 01–2 hardware and software system improved balance performance in the Romberg test on the Stabilan 01–2. This resulted in a reduction in oscillatory movements in the frontal and sagittal planes, a decrease in the speed of the center of pressure, and a decrease in the support area on the stabiloplatform, which increased the time it took to hold a posture in the Romberg test. The use of coordination exercises based on A. A. Dmitrieva’s methodology and the developed adaptive outdoor games, combined with stabilographic training games, allowed for a reduction in the time required to run the 3x5 meter shuttle run and an increase in the accuracy of hitting the ball on target.

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**PERSONALIZED DIGITAL COACHING IN ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL
EDUCATION OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES:
AN ANALYTICAL MODEL AND EVIDENCE BASE**

Terekhina Evgeniya Nikolaevna

PhD in Biology, Associate Professor

South Ural State University (National Research University)

Shelgacheva Kamilla Batyrbekovna

Senior Lecturer

South Ural State University (National Research University)

Yashenko Ekaterina Vyacheslavovna

PhD, Associate Professor

South Ural State University (National Research University)

Bondarenko Natalia Yurievna

top-category coach

South Ural State University (National Research University)

Abstract. *This article presents an analytical study of personalized digital coaching in adaptive physical education for university students with disabilities. The purpose was to synthesize current evidence on digital coaching for physical activity, identify the intervention components associated with better outcomes, and develop a university-oriented support model that combines pedagogical personalization with medical safety. The analysis drew on international physical activity guidelines, studies on students with disabilities, systematic reviews and meta-analyses of chatbot and digital interventions, accessibility frameworks, and exercise recommendations for asthma, hypertension, diabetes, and musculoskeletal disorders. The evidence indicates a stable small-to-moderate positive effect of digital coaching on total physical activity, daily steps, and moderate-to-vigorous physical activity. At the same time, the literature shows that such tools are beneficial only when they are individualized, accessible, transparent, and supervised by a teacher or another qualified specialist. On this basis, an analytical model is proposed that includes initial assessment, digital support, self-monitoring, profile-specific load adaptation, and mandatory human oversight. The model can serve as a methodological basis for pilot implementation in university practice and for subsequent empirical testing.*

Keywords: *personalized digital coaching; adaptive physical education; students with disabilities; physical activity; university education; evidence base; exercise safety.*

Introduction

Insufficient physical activity among university students with disabilities has pedagogical, biomedical, and social consequences. International recommendations stress that people living with disability or chronic health conditions should be offered adapted opportunities for regular movement, reduction of sedentary time, and accessible formats of participation. In real university practice, however, this group still encounters barriers such as inaccessible infrastructure, limited individualized support, anxiety about symptom worsening, scheduling difficulties, and weak self-monitoring routines. As a result, many students do not reach recommended activity levels, while irregular participation reduces both health benefits and educational inclusion [1–4].

Adaptive physical education is intended to compensate for these barriers through individualized content, gradual progression, and pedagogical support. Yet even well-designed in-class programs are often insufficient on their own, because students need continuity between formal sessions: reminders, clarification of tasks, reassurance regarding symptoms, and feedback on completed activity. This makes the question of supportive technologies especially important for higher education institutions that work with heterogeneous student populations and limited staff resources.

Against this background, personalized digital coaching is of particular interest as a practical support technology. Chatbots, messaging systems, and simple digital assistants can deliver timely prompts, brief feedback, and structured goal support without replacing the teacher. The literature nevertheless remains fragmented. Evidence on digital coaching is often discussed separately from adaptive physical education, separately from disability studies, and separately from exercise safety in people with chronic conditions and functional limitations. For university educators, this creates a methodological gap between promising digital tools and the real requirements of safe inclusive teaching [5–9].

The purpose of this study was to analytically justify the use of personalized digital coaching in adaptive physical education of university students with disabilities, summarize the most relevant scientific findings, and develop a practical support model suitable for university implementation. The study focused not only on the effectiveness of digital interventions as such, but also on the conditions under which they become pedagogically and medically acceptable.

Methods

The study was designed as an analytical review with elements of content synthesis and pedagogical modeling. The evidence base included five groups of materials: (1) international guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour; (2) studies on physical activity in people with disabilities and university students with disabilities; (3) systematic reviews and meta-analyses of digital and chatbot-based physical activity interventions; (4) accessibility and Universal Design for Learning guidance; and (5) safety recommendations for exercise in asthma, arterial hypertension, diabetes, and musculoskeletal disorders [1–12].

The analytical procedure covered four thematic blocks: participation barriers and physical activity deficits; effectiveness of digital coaching; accessibility and individualization in adaptive physical education; and medical safety of exercise. Sources were included when they were peer-reviewed or represented official guidance, were directly relevant to the topic, and could be translated into a university adaptive physical education context. Priority was given to reviews, meta-analyses, consensus documents, and studies with clear practical implications for educational settings.

The methods of analysis included analytical review, comparative synthesis of published results, content analysis of intervention components, and pedagogical extrapolation from clinical or public-health guidance to the context of adaptive physical education. Quantitative indicators from systematic reviews were used not as a basis for a new meta-analysis, but as an evidence benchmark for judging the magnitude and direction of digital intervention effects. Qualitative interpretation focused on whether the reported components of successful interventions could realistically be incorporated into routine university practice.

The original analytical contribution of the article lies in the integration of fragmented findings into a single university-oriented framework. Instead of treating digital coaching, adaptive physical education, accessibility, and exercise safety as separate domains, the study combines them into one model of pedagogically supervised personalized support.

Results

The reviewed evidence shows that digital coaching should be considered an adjunct to, rather than a substitute for, teacher-led adaptive physical education. In the meta-analysis by Wang et al. focused on chatbot-based exercise interventions, the pooled effect on physical activity was small but statistically significant (standardized mean difference, $SMD = 0.20$). In the broader review by Singh et al., the effect sizes were $SMD = 0.28$ for total physical activity, $SMD = 0.28$ for steps, and $SMD = 0.53$ for moderate-to-vigorous physical activity (MVPA) [5, 6]. These findings suggest that digital coaching is most useful when it supports concrete goals, repeated prompts, and simple behaviour-change routines.

At the same time, the evidence does not support uncontrolled or universal use of digital tools. The reviewed studies differ in duration, technical implementation, outcome measures, and methodological quality. Some interventions rely on chatbots, some on mobile applications, and some on mixed digital support formats. For adaptive physical education, the key practical conclusion is not that one platform is universally superior, but that digital support becomes effective only when it reflects the student's health profile, functional capacities, motivation, and accessibility needs, and when safety remains under human supervision [5–9].

Table 1. Main findings underlying the analytical model

Source	Design	Focus	Key finding	Implication for adaptive PE
WHO, 2020; Bull et al., 2020	Guideline	Physical activity in disability and chronic conditions	Regular adapted physical activity and reduced sedentary behaviour are recommended	Provides the general framework for safe university programs
Ubeda-Colomer et al., 2019	Cross-sectional study	University students with disabilities	A substantial share of students does not achieve recommended activity levels	Justifies the need for adherence-supporting technologies
Wang et al., 2025	Meta-analysis	Chatbot exercise interventions	Overall physical activity effect: SMD = 0.20	Digital coaching can strengthen participation but not replace the teacher
Singh et al., 2023	Systematic review and meta-analysis	Chatbots for lifestyle behaviour change	Total PA = 0.28; steps = 0.28; MVPA = 0.53	The most promising interventions are regular and personalized
CAST, 2024; WHO, 2021	Guidelines	Accessibility and ethical use of AI	Accessibility, transparency, and human oversight are essential	Digital coaching must remain understandable, inclusive, and supervised

Table 1 summarizes the main evidence blocks that support the proposed analytical model. It demonstrates that the rationale for digital coaching in adaptive physical education is cumulative rather than based on a single study. General movement recommendations define the normative framework, disability studies identify the participation problem, digital health reviews demonstrate the behavioural potential of technology, and accessibility and ethics guidance set the limits within which such technology should operate.

Figure 1. Published effects of digital coaching on physical activity

Figure 1. Published effects of digital coaching on physical activity

Figure 1 shows that digital coaching exerts a consistent positive effect, although the magnitude is usually small to moderate. The largest pooled effect was reported for MVPA, indicating that structured support may be especially useful when students need help sustaining planned, sufficiently intense activity. For adaptive physical education, this points to the value of digital tools for participation support, graded progression, and self-organization rather than for autonomous decision-making.

A content comparison of the reviewed studies also identified the intervention components most often associated with positive outcomes: personalized feedback on well-being and progress, reminder systems, self-monitoring logs, and adaptation of exercise load to current health status. These components are directly relevant for university adaptive physical education, where daily one-to-one supervision is rarely feasible but regular low-burden contact is possible through messaging or telephone-based support [5–8].

Figure 2. Key components of effective digital interventions

Figure 2 visualizes the functional core of effective digital support. What is important in pedagogical terms is not technical sophistication as such, but the recurrence of several simple mechanisms: a student receives an understandable task, is reminded about it, records completion or symptoms, and obtains brief personalized feedback.

For students with disabilities, this logic may reduce uncertainty and increase confidence because the support becomes predictable and structured.

Table 2. Analytical model of personalized digital coaching in adaptive physical education

Component	Content	Evidence base	Practical effect
Initial assessment	Brief assessment of current activity, motivation, symptoms, functional limitations, preferred communication format, and contraindications	Physical activity guidelines; adaptive PE literature	Improves starting-point personalization and reduces risk
Digital support	Messenger or phone-based reminders, micro-goals, brief motivational prompts, and feedback on task completion	Meta-analyses of chatbot and digital interventions	Increases regular participation and adherence
Self-monitoring	Weekly check-in on fatigue, pain, sleep, mood, dyspnea, blood glucose or pressure indicators when relevant, and completed sessions	Behaviour-change and digital coaching literature	Supports autonomy and informed self-regulation
Profile-specific load adaptation	Modification of exercises for respiratory, cardiometabolic, and musculoskeletal profiles; adjustment of intensity, volume, pace, and recovery	Safety guidance for asthma, hypertension, diabetes, and functional limitations	Reduces the probability of adverse events
Human oversight	Periodic teacher review and, when needed, physician consultation or referral	WHO ethics guidance on AI in health	Preserves pedagogical responsibility, transparency, and safety

The proposed model is intentionally simple and suitable for routine educational use. Its function is to organize communication and support rather than to automate complex rehabilitation decision-making. In practical terms, the model may be implemented through existing university channels: a teacher, curator, or adaptive physical education specialist sets tasks, sends reminders, receives short feedback from the student, and adjusts the load according to predetermined safety rules. This makes the model realistic for pilot use even in institutions with limited technological infrastructure.

A particularly important result of the analysis is the need for profile-specific adaptation. Students with asthma may require warm-up emphasis, symptom monitoring, and attention to triggers; students with hypertension need control of load progression and avoidance of abrupt excessive effort; students with diabetes may need coordination with meal timing, medication, and signs of hypo- or hyperglycemia; students with musculoskeletal limitations often need modified amplitude,

reduced impact, and individualized recovery intervals [10–12]. Digital coaching is therefore acceptable only when it translates these profile differences into understandable day-to-day instructions.

Discussion

The analytical results support the view that digital coaching is most productive in adaptive physical education when it amplifies an existing teacher-led program. Its main contribution is not the replacement of professional judgment but the extension of individualized contact beyond the classroom. In university settings this can improve regularity of participation, reduce uncertainty about exercise, and strengthen self-monitoring routines that are essential for students with disabilities.

The comparison of reviews further indicates that the effect of digital coaching increases when interventions are individualized, repeated, and behaviourally specific. This is fully consistent with the logic of adaptive physical education: students need clear and accessible algorithms of action, not generic motivation. Therefore, the proposed model combines pedagogical support, digital communication, and explicit safety control. From this perspective, even relatively simple digital channels may be more valuable than technically sophisticated systems that are difficult to understand or inaccessible for users with diverse needs.

Accessibility is not an auxiliary requirement but a central condition of effectiveness. If prompts are linguistically complex, visually inconvenient, poorly timed, or incompatible with a student's preferred communication format, the intervention will fail regardless of its theoretical merit. The relevance of Universal Design for Learning and ethical AI guidance lies precisely in this point: digital support must remain understandable, transparent, and controllable by the human educator [8, 9].

Safety remains the central condition of acceptability. For students with respiratory, cardiometabolic, or musculoskeletal limitations, even low-intensity exercise support should be tailored and monitored. The main analytical contribution of this article is thus the integration of evidence from digital intervention studies with adaptive physical education and exercise-safety guidance, translating general digital evidence into a university-ready framework [7–12].

The study also has limitations. It is analytical rather than experimental, and therefore it does not provide direct data from a student cohort or a controlled university intervention. In addition, the evidence base includes heterogeneous digital formats and populations, not only students with disabilities. Nevertheless, the consistency of the behavioural mechanisms identified in the literature makes it possible to formulate a grounded model for pilot implementation and further evaluation.

Conclusions

1. Personalized digital coaching and chatbot interventions have a statistically significant positive effect on physical activity, with effect sizes typically in the small-to-moderate range.

2. In adaptive physical education, the most important gains are not only quantitative increases in activity, but also improved adherence, self-monitoring, accessibility, and personalized support.

3. An analytical model suitable for university practice should include initial assessment, digital support, self-monitoring, profile-specific load adaptation, and mandatory human oversight.

4. The practical value of the model lies in its compatibility with ordinary university communication channels and its focus on safe pedagogical support rather than technological complexity.

5. The proposed framework can be used as a methodological basis for pilot implementation and for further empirical evaluation in real student cohorts.

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PROJECT-BASED LEARNING (PBL) APPROACH IN THE GLOBAL CONTEXT: A REVIEW OF RESEARCH AND PRACTICE

Ermakova Irina

Researcher-Educator

Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology

Annotation. *This article examines the process of integration of English-language project-based learning (PBL) approach into the system of higher education within the context of globalization and the standardization of educational norms. The central hypothesis posits that PBL, particularly when conducted in English, the lingua franca of science and technology, serves as a key tool for cultivating the professional, communicative, and critical thinking competencies required for effective performance in the international labor market.*

The study employs an overview of international experiences in implementing PBL in higher education. It provides a review of contemporary scientific literature, highlighting the empirically confirmed effectiveness of PBL in developing professional competencies, problem-solving abilities, and collaborative skills. The international practice section analyzes successful cases from Vietnam, India, Lithuania, and Israel, confirming the viability of English as a medium for project-based instruction.

The conclusion affirms the significant potential of English-language PBL as an integral component of modern education. It underscores the necessity of accounting for theoretical foundations (e.g., activity theory, CDIO standards) and adapting methodologies to specific professional and institutional contexts. The article argues for the strategic importance of further empirical research and the development of tailored methodological recommendations to facilitate the successful scaling of English-language project-based courses within the Russian higher education system.

Keywords: *project-based learning (PBL), English-language education, higher education, internationalization, competency-based approach, CDIO.*

Introduction

In the context of globalization and the standardization of educational norms, the need to develop human resource potential capable of effective functioning in the international professional arena becomes increasingly urgent. Contemporary

companies are not willing to spend time and resources on educating young specialists, they require employees developed professional skills and clear understating of working process. A key tool for developing these skills and competencies is project-based learning, particularly when conducted in English. In this case the English language, as the lingua franca of science and technology, is not just a subject, but it is transforming into an integral component of the educational paradigm. However, the integration of project-based activities in English into higher education curricula is accompanied by a set of challenges.

The aim of this study is to provide theoretical evidence for the necessity of integrating project-based learning activities in English into the university educational system and to analyse already existing educational programmes worldwide.

Review of Scientific Literature on the Integration of PBL in Higher Education

In recent decades, the integration of project-based learning, particularly in a foreign language, including English, into higher education curricula has become a central point of attention for the international scientific and pedagogical community. Contemporary academic research confirms that project-based learning (PBL) plays a significant role in the development of students' professional competencies. The implementation of PBL into the educational process intensifies the formation of skills in critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, collaboration, and leadership, which constitute the foundation for successful professional realization.

International research emphasizes the high effectiveness of project-based learning (PBL) in fostering professional and communicative competencies among students. For instance, in the article "Project-Based Learning as an Experiential Pedagogical Methodology in Engineering Education," the authors Lavado-Anguera, Velasco-Quintana, and Terrón-López note that PBL promotes the development of skills necessary for solving real-world professional tasks, such as critical thinking, teamwork, and communication. Furthermore, the integration of PBL with the CDIO (Conceive, Design, Implement, Operate) methodology allows students to experience the entire product development cycle, thereby enhancing their professional preparedness [Lavado-Anguera et al., 2024, p. 85].

As for the process of teaching English as a foreign language (EFL), project-based learning has also proven to be an effective method. The research conducted by Y. Y. Kovaleva, A. V. Soboleva, and A. Kerimkulov demonstrates that the use of PBL in English language instruction contributes to the development of both written and oral communication skills among university students. The authors emphasize the importance of such skills for future engineers aiming to work in an international professional environment [Kovalyova et al., 2016, p. 153].

A notable example is a research study analyzing the impact of PBL on the formation of entrepreneurial competencies in higher education. The authors conclude that PBL fosters the development of skills such as creativity, innovative thinking, leadership potential, and resilience, which are of particular importance in a dynamically transforming labor market. This study underscores the importance of integrating project-based learning into educational programs as a factor in preparing students for future professional activity [Chitamba et al., 2025, p. 113].

Another significant piece of research is the work “Project-based learning and project-based teaching: a guide,” which utilizes activity theory to analyze professional learning in workplace settings. This study highlights the importance of considering the context and tools of activity when designing educational programs, which can be useful for implementing PBL into the education system [Wallenquest, 2025].

International Practice of Applying Project-Based Learning (PBL) in Higher Education

The international experience of implementing project-based learning in English at higher education institutions demonstrates a diversity of approaches and practices aimed at developing students’ linguistic and professional competencies. Recent research confirms the effectiveness of such methods in the context of preparing students for professional activity in a globalized world.

A notable example is a study conducted at the university of foreign languages in Vietnam. At this institution, students studying English as a foreign language actively participate in project-based activities, which contributes to the development of their language skills and professional competencies. The study found that project-based learning helps students improve their communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills, which are essential for successful professional activity in international environment [Andargie et al., 2025, p. 7].

In India, specifically in engineering colleges in Tamil Nadu, project-based learning in English is also actively implemented. Research conducted among teachers of English as a second language showed that project-based learning contributes to improving students’ language skills and fosters their capacity for independent learning and critical thinking. However, certain difficulties were identified, such as a lack of time and resources, as well as the need for additional teacher training for the effective implementation of project-based learning [Andargie et al., 2025, p. 21].

Furthermore, in Lithuania, researchers from Kaunas University of Technology conducted a review of existing practices of project-based learning in English in higher education. They noted that project-based learning fosters the creation of an authentic educational environment where students can apply their language skills in real-world situations. The importance of ensuring student choice and opportunities for self-expression in the learning process was also emphasized [Jaleniauskiene et al., 2025, p. 26].

Research conducted at the Technion — Israel Institute of Technology demonstrated that introducing project-based learning into foundational courses in engineering programs contributes to the development of students' teamwork skills, creative thinking, and ability to independently solve engineering problems. Students participating in such courses report increased learning motivation and improved communication skills [Guo et al., 2020].

In turn, work published in the *English Review: Journal of English Education* examines the use of project-based learning for teaching English as a foreign language in Russian universities. The authors note that this approach contributes to improving students' communicative skills, which is an important aspect of their preparation for professional activity in an international environment [Yamin, 2025, p. 363].

Thus, contemporary research confirms the effectiveness of PBL as a means of developing professional competencies. However, for the successful implementation of PBL in higher education, it is necessary to consider theoretical foundations, such as activity theory, as well as to adapt methodologies considering the specifics of the professional field and educational context. Additionally, further empirical research aimed at identifying the specifics of implementing PBL in English in Russian universities is needed, along with the development of methodological recommendations for teachers and educational institutions.

Conclusion

As seen above, the process of implementing the Project-based learning methodology into the higher education curriculum has undergone a significant shift recently with many universities worldwide adding PBL courses taught in English into their educational programme. The overview of scientific studies devoted to the impact of PBL on the development of professional skills has shown that Project-Based Learning approach allows students to apply their theoretical knowledge in practice, which is particularly important for the formation of professional competencies, such as team work, problem-solving and effective communication. As a result, students demonstrate enhanced skills in interdisciplinary collaboration, teamwork, and independent decision-making.

When it comes to technical education, for instance, the engineer departments, the PBL methodology in combination with theoretical knowledge and technical training is especially effective as it prepares the students for real working process which requires not only theoretical literacy, but critical thinking, problem-solving skills, the ability to quickly adapt to new technological conditions and communicative competence.

An overview of recent scientific publications and university programmes shows that project-based activity in English is gradually becoming an integral part of training highly qualified personnel. But, despite the obvious advantages, it should

be noted that implementing PBL requires significant resources, careful planning, and constant monitoring of results. Nevertheless, the prospects for integrating such programs look quite convincing, and it is possible that this direction will only expand in the coming years.

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DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' PHRASEOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

Abzalova Galiya Alikovna

postgraduate student

*South Kazakhstan Pedagogical University named after O. Zhanibekov,
Shymkent, Kazakhstan*

Narozhnaya Valentina Dmitrievna

Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

*South Kazakhstan Pedagogical University named after O. Zhanibekov,
Shymkent, Kazakhstan*

Abstract. *The article addresses the problems of students' use of phraseological units within the framework of the modern educational environment. The relevance of the study is determined by the necessity to develop phraseological literacy as a fundamental component of learners' communicative and linguistic-cultural competence.*

The aim of the study is to identify the level of interpretation of phraseological units, determine their frequency of use in both oral and written speech, and to identify typical difficulties in their semantic analysis.

The identified trends indicate the necessity for systematic work on the development of phraseological competence, including contextual analysis, comparison of literal and figurative meanings, as well as recourse to cultural commentary.

The analysis of the obtained data leads to the conclusion that work with phraseological material in educational practice is insufficiently systematic. The obtained results can be applied in the practice of teaching the Russian language and in the development of educational and methodological materials aimed at enhancing learners' linguistic worldview.

Keywords: *phraseological unit, phraseological competence, linguistic worldview, surveying, speech activity, students.*

Introduction

The contemporary state of the Russian language is characterized by dynamic changes in its vocabulary and speech practices, which are particularly pronounced in the student environment. In the context of the digitalization of communication

and the transformation of the educational environment, the issue of preserving and ensuring the active functioning of the figurative means of language, in particular phraseological units, becomes increasingly relevant.

Phraseological units constitute a significant component of the national-cultural code, reflecting the historical experience, value attitudes, and worldview orientations of native speakers [5, p. 89]. Their use contributes to enhancing the expressiveness of speech, the formation of communicative competence, and the development of the linguistic personality of the learner.

In the scientific tradition represented by the works of V. V. Vinogradov [2], N. M. Shansky [6], and A. V. Kunin [4], phraseology is considered an independent subsystem of the language with its own structure, semantics, and functional features. The problems of the functioning of phraseological units in contemporary speech and the issues of their teaching are actively addressed in the works of V. P. Zhukov [3] and N. F. Alefirenko [1]. However, in the context of modern educational practice, there is a need for empirical research into the extent to which students actively and consciously use phraseological units in oral and written communication.

The relevance of this research is determined by the decrease in the frequency of use of fixed expressions in academic discourse and the predominance of simplified forms of communication in digital environments. This is due to the fact that some phraseological units include archaic forms that are no longer consciously recognized in contemporary Russian. These primarily include phraseological units containing lexical archaisms within their components: *to bow down in respect*, *to cherish like the apple of one's eye*, *to admit a peculiar kind of carriage nearby*, *naked as a hawk*, as well as grammatical archaisms such as — *a parable on everyone's lips*, *dark water in the clouds*, *passed away*, *waver and it will open*, *everything is in God's hands*, *to lie down among the bones*, *killing seven at one stroke*, *without any doubt*, *barely managing*, and others.

Results and Discussion

To understand the meaning of phraseological units containing historicisms, it is necessary to identify the characteristic that underlies such a phrase and to establish its etymology. For example, a person who carries himself with dignity is said to *hold the trump card* (the trump card — a collar on the coat of noblemen in Ancient Rus', embroidered with gold, silver, or pearls, which was therefore stiff and imparted a proud, dignified posture to its wearer). The meanings of phraseological units

in the middle of nowhere(very far away, in other remote locations),

solid ground(earth, land),

the floodgates of heaven opened(it began to rain heavily, a torrential downpour)

become understandable if it is established that *kuliga* denotes ‘a wooded, remote, swampy place’; *tverd’*– Old Church Slavonic *tverd’*– ‘sky’; *khlyab’*– Common Slavic *khlyab’*– ‘water depth, abyss’ (3, pp. 56–72). The Russian language contains many fixed expressions related to peasant life (горе лыковое, лыка не вяжет, не лыком шит, ни кола ни двора, мели Емеля: твоя неделя), as well as the speech of various craftsmen and artisans, merchants, and traders (бить баклуши, точить лясы, положить зубы на полку, разделить под орех, сбоку припека, белыми нитками шито, попал впросак, мерить на свой аршин, попробовать на зубок and others).

Определите фразеологизмы-синонимы	
Кот наплакал	
В двух шагах	
Сложь руки	
Засучив рукава	
Ни рыба ни мясо	
Семиимильными шагами	
<i>Для справки: ни то ни се, бить баклуши, капля в море, рукой подать, точить лясы, по пальцам можно пересчитать, считать ворон, черепаший шаг, не покладая рук.</i>	
Определите фразеологизмы-антонимы	
Капля в море	
Рукой подать	
Не покладая рук	
Засучив рукава	
Выйти из себя	
<i>Для справки: куры не клюют, в двух шагах, засучив рукава, на краю света, лежать на боку, сложь руки, спустя рукава, взять себя в руки, кот наплакал, яблоку негде упасть.</i>	

Analyzing such phraseological units, students draw conclusions about the synonymy and antonymy of phraseological units, perform creative assignments, and, in case of difficulty, refer to phraseological dictionaries.

In this regard, the analysis of students’ level of understanding, interpretation, and practical use of phraseological units across various fields of study is of particular importance. Identifying these trends allows for the refinement of the content of methodological work and the determination of effective approaches to the development of phraseological competence within the higher education system.

An experimental survey was conducted to determine the degree to which students understand the meanings of phraseological units and how they employ them in speech. The survey was carried out among students from the 1st to 4th years at the South Kazakhstan Pedagogical University named after Uzbekali Zhanibekov. The study involved 64 respondents. Analysis of the age distribution showed

that the majority of the sample consisted of participants aged 18–22 years (52 individuals, 81%), which allows the group to be characterized as predominantly composed of students. By gender, there is a marked predominance of the female audience: 53 (83%) are female and 11 (17%) are male.

Most participants have incomplete tertiary education, which confirms the student status of the respondents. The primary language of instruction is Russian, which is directly linked to the success in performing tasks related to knowledge of Russian phraseological units.

The following responses were obtained to the question regarding the frequency of phraseological unit usage in speech:

- the most common option is «*sometimes*» (30 respondents, 48%);
- 15 respondents indicated the option «*seldom*» (23%);
- 12 respondents indicated «*often*» (18%);
- 7 respondents chose the option «*constantly*» (11%).

This suggests that phraseological units constitute an active vocabulary of the majority of respondents; however, their usage is predominantly situational.

Analysis of responses to test assignments revealed a high level of command over the phraseological stock of the Russian language:

- *to loaf around* — 53 correct answers (82.8%);
- *vanished without a trace* — 52 correct answers (81.3%);
- *to make a mental note* — 53 correct answers (82.8%);
- *at full speed* — 54 correct answers (84.4%);
- *to keep one's mouth shut* — 58 correct answers (90.6%);
- *to count crows* — 44 correct answers (68.7%).

The majority of respondents demonstrated a stable understanding of commonly used phraseological units. The greatest difficulty was caused by the phraseological unit *to count crows*, which may indicate a decrease in its frequency of use among modern youth.

In response to the request to name 2–3 frequently used phraseological units, respondents cited expressions such as: *the soul went into the heels, like two peas in a pod, hands don't reach, to beat baklushi, a perfect match*.

This confirms that phraseological units are not only recognized but also actively used in the speech of contemporary youth. At the same time, in certain instances, there was observed a conflation of phraseological units with fixed colloquial expressions, which indicates the necessity of a clearer differentiation of these concepts within the educational process.

Conclusions

The analysis of the test section of the questionnaire (17 tasks) revealed, overall, a high level of phraseological competence development: the average score was

15.98 out of 17 possible points, with a minimum score of 13 and a maximum of 17. This testifies to a solid mastery of the basic set of commonly used phraseological units.

The highest percentage of correct responses was observed in the interpretation of the expression *держат язык за зубами* (90.6%), as well as in identifying the meaning of 'very quickly' — *со всех ног* (84.4%). The phraseological units *бить баклуши* and *зарубить на носу* were accurately interpreted in 82.8% of cases, while the expression *как в воду канул* was correctly understood in 81.3%. A relatively lower indicator was demonstrated by the comprehension of the phraseological unit «*to count crows*» (68.7%).

The analysis of self-assessed frequency of use showed that, despite a high level of semantic understanding, there is only a moderate degree of their active use in speech. To validate the obtained data, students were given a creative task designed to assess the level of understanding of the meanings of phraseological units.

Укажите фразеологизмы, происхождение которых связано с					
ремеслом	медициной	рыбной ловлей	охотой	искусством	фольклором
<i>Для справок: Точить лясы, паралич хватил, убить двух зайцев, сорвать маску, бить баклуши, сматывать удочку, искать жар-птицу, снять стружку, в здоровом теле здоровый дух, песенка спета, доводить до белого каления, кровь с молоком, надеть маску, молочные реки и кисельные берега, попасться в ловушку, биться как рыба об лед, сойти со сцены, ни пуха ни пера, проглотить горькую пилюлю, играть первую скрипку, попасться на удочку, упасть в обморок, переменить декорации, убить бобра, закинуть удочку, белыми нитками шито, играть роль, ловить рыбу в мутной воде, этот номер не пройдет, за тридцать земель, на ловца и зверь бежит, делить шкуру неубитого медведя, по щучьему веленью, через час по чайной ложке, у разбитого корыта.</i>					

The data obtained allow us to conclude that the receptive level of phraseological competence is developed, while productive activity remains comparatively less pronounced. This confirms the necessity of strengthening practice-oriented work with phraseological units, aimed at promoting their active use in oral and written communication.

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PERSPECTIVES OF ARTISTIC GYMNASTICS MEANS AND METHODS IN THE SPORT OF PERSONS WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES

Novikova Marie

Professional Sports Coach

Prague, Czech Republic

Novikov Vladislav Vladimirovich

Associate Professor

South Ural State University,

Chelyabinsk, Russia

Abstract. *The article deals with the problem of developing a methodology of artistic gymnastics with children and adults with intellectual disabilities. The author describes the methods and exercises of artistic gymnastics, suitable for physical training of persons with intellectual disabilities and mastering technically complex motor actions. The article concludes that there is a great potential for the use of means and methods of artistic gymnastics by persons with intellectual disabilities.*

Keywords: *persons with intellectual disabilities; artistic gymnastics; adapted sport; training methodology; physical training means.*

Relevance. According to statistics, there are about 15 million disabled people in Russia, which makes up 10% of the total population [5]. In our opinion, a major perspective in solving the problem of integration and socialization of persons with disabilities consists in the use of sportsmanship provisions formulated by V. K. Balsevich and L. I. Lubysheva [2] in the organization of physical activity of disabled people.

Physical training of children with intellectual disabilities differs by insufficient coordination of movements and reduced development of strength. During physical activity, these children find it difficult to make sudden movements or take part in active games. They perform significantly worse than their healthy peers. According to N. A. Antipanova and M. A. Datsko, children with intellectual disabilities lag behind their normally developing peers in physical development [1].

Cognitive development is closely linked to language development, as children with intellectual disabilities are unable to communicate fully and their thinking and related functions take longer to develop. Children find it difficult to express their thoughts and

convey information to others. V.V. Cherkasov et al. generalise that "...people with disabilities have a reduced level of motor activity, which negatively affects physical development, cold immunity, adaptation to learning and socialisation" [6].

Artistic gymnastics is a complex co-ordination sport. The exercises of artistic gymnastics are very diverse and require flexibility, strength and speed. Artistic gymnastics has a number of advantages over other sports due to its variability, the possibility of flexible dosage and selection of load parameters in accordance with the level of physical training of students. The possibility of combining different exercises and methods of their execution is a distinctive methodological feature of gymnastics classes. Another significant methodological feature of means and methods of artistic gymnastics is the ability to solve different teaching tasks. Competent application of means and methods of artistic gymnastics can contribute to the health improvement of students, physical development, teaching motor actions, solving hygienic issues of physical education and sport. The structure and content of gymnastic exercises allows the teacher to vary the degree of physical load depending on the tasks and goals. The gymnastic apparatus and equipment contributes to the expansion of gymnastics means. The degree of complexity of performing a particular gymnastic exercise varies depending on the width, height and properties of the equipment used.

The objective is to explore the prospective application of means and methods of artistic gymnastics with persons with intellectual disabilities.

Organization and methodology of the study. The study was aimed at comparing the dynamics of physical preparedness of children with intellectual disabilities using the means and methods of artistic gymnastics and traditional adapted physical education classes. Two groups of boys 12–14 years old took part in the study. The participants were divided into groups of 8 people each. The children of the control group had adapted physical education classes three times a week. Children in the experimental group also trained three times a week. They exercised with stuffed balls; walked and ran on a treadmill; did general exercises; did exercises on wall bars; and played physical games. Classes were held three times a week for six months from February to June 2022.

Since persons with intellectual disabilities need adapted exercises, physical exercises for healthy peers can not always be useful. The coach needs to use calisthenics, exercises of rhythmic gymnastics, choreography, physical games with gymnastic with persons with intellectual disabilities. Additional means can be used as part of training in artistic gymnastics, and naturally complement the overall educational process. Besides, parents can be involved in doing the exercises [4].

In complex coordination sports, including artistic gymnastics, motor activity is characterised by extremely high requirements for movement technique, therefore, the pure-part and whole methods of teaching motor actions are widely used. Due

to the division of complex elements into its component parts (phases) it is possible to achieve the desired result in movement training.

The results of performing certain motor test exercises selected on the basis of children's physical capabilities are the most objective indicators of their physical development level.

Results. Control testing was done before and after the classes. We revealed higher dynamics of physical ability growth in the experimental group. The results of the first testing are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 — Results of physical abilities testing of children with intellectual disabilities before the classes started

No	Testing	Control group	Experimental group	p
1	Push-ups, number of times	7.4±0.4	7.5±0.3	≥ 0.05
2	Standing long jump, cm	154.5±5.6	155.5±6.5	≥ 0.05
3	Sit and reach, cm	1.2±0.1	1.2±0.2	≥ 0.05
4	Running 30 m (sec)	6.10±0.2	6.08±0.2	≥ 0.05
5	Tennis ball throwing into the target (number of hits)	3.5±0.4	3.5±0.3	≥ 0.05

The results of the first testing show that children of the control and experimental groups have no reliable difference in the level of physical ability, and during the test exercises the participants demonstrated rather low physical indicators. This fact is known, described in sufficient detail in the previous studies and does not require additional research.

After six months of training, we conducted the second testing of physical abilities in both groups to find out the dynamics. The results of the second testing are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 — Results of physical abilities testing of children with intellectual disabilities after training sessions

No	Testing	Control group	Experimental group	p
1	Push-ups, number of times	7.6±0.3 3%	8.9±0.5 15%	≤ 0.05
2	Standing long jump, cm	158.3±4.6 2.5%	168.2±6.5 15.5%	≤ 0.05
3	Sit and reach, cm	1.3±0.1 8%	2.2±0.1 30%	≤ 0.05
4	Running 30 m (sec)	6.0±0.2 1.5%	5.64±0.2 12.4%	≤ 0.05
5	Tennis ball throwing into the target (number of hits)	3.6±0.3 5%	4.9±0.3 19.5%	≤ 0.05

The obtained data confirm the perspective of using the means and methods of artistic gymnastics to improve the physical functioning of children with intellectual disabilities. This is demonstrated by the reliable ($p \leq 0.05$) differences in the participants' physical development indicators in the two groups and the given percentages of increase in the participants' physical ability indicators.

Conclusion. Therefore, we can conclude that the concept of 'sportification' is reflected in adapted physical culture. Artistic gymnastics contribute to the development and improvement of the physical abilities and motor skills of people with intellectual disabilities. A wide variety of exercises enables the training process to be diversified and the means of training to be selected in accordance with students' motor capabilities.

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DEVELOPING LEGAL COMPETENCE OF EDUCATORS THROUGH THE CASE METHOD

Stsepanets Volha Uladzimirauna

Methodologist, Postgraduate Student

Academy of Education,

Minsk, Republic of Belarus

The relevance of the pressing issue of developing legal competence among educators through the case method stems from the fact that modern teachers face situations requiring legally sound decisions on a daily basis: interacting with parents, protecting children's rights, responding to conflicts and bullying. Insufficient legal competence can lead to serious consequences — from violations of the rights of participants in the educational process to the teacher themselves being held legally accountable.

The theoretical foundations of this problem have been developed by numerous researchers. S.S. Alekseev viewed legal competence as an integral part of a teacher's professional culture. E.A. Pevtsova emphasizes legal awareness and legal culture as crucial components. V.V. Serikov defines this competence as the ability to mobilize knowledge and experience in situations with a legal context. Z.S. Mustafaeva proposes a structure comprising cognitive, activity-based, and value-oriented components.

The case method (case-study) is an active learning approach based on the analysis of real situations. It allows one to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge of legal norms and their practical application.

As researchers Z.U. Kolokolnikova and V.V. Koreneva note, the case method offers a range of significant advantages that make it particularly effective in the context of legal competence development for educators. First and foremost, it fosters the development of analytical skills, enabling teachers to break down complex professional situations into their constituent elements, identify key issues, and evaluate them from multiple perspectives. Secondly, it contributes to the formation of the ability to work with information — a critical skill in an era when legal documents, school regulations, and conflicting accounts must be sifted through to extract what is truly relevant. Thirdly, the method promotes the development of teamwork skills, as educators often analyze cases in small groups,

learning to articulate their reasoning, listen to colleagues, and build consensus around the most effective course of action. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, it cultivates the ability to make decisions under conditions of uncertainty, preparing teachers to act confidently even when faced with incomplete information or ambiguous circumstances.

Creating effective legal cases for teacher training requires adherence to a set of well-defined principles. Each principle serves to ensure that the case is not merely a hypothetical exercise but a genuinely useful tool for professional growth.

First, realism of the plot. The situation presented must be recognizable and typical for the professional environment of a teacher. Cases drawn from real incidents — whether from school archives, media reports, or judicial practice — resonate more deeply with educators, who immediately perceive their relevance.

Second, presence of a legal conflict. An effective case must contain an element of dispute or ambiguity — a situation where different interpretations are possible and where the correct course of action is not immediately obvious. This creates the tension necessary for productive discussion and forces participants to engage with the nuances of the law.

Third, relevance of the legal framework. The case must be grounded in current legislation. References to outdated laws or regulations diminish the practical value of the exercise. Developers should ensure that all normative documents referenced are those currently in force.

Fourth, exclusion of value judgments. The case description should present only facts, stripped of evaluative language. Rather than stating that a parent “rudely demanded” something, the case should simply describe what was said and done. This allows participants to form their own judgments without being led by the case author.

Fifth, clear formulation of the task. Educators must understand precisely what is expected of them. A well-formulated task might include specific questions such as: “Which articles of the Federal Law ‘On Education’ apply to this situation?” or “What documents must the teacher provide, and what documents may be withheld?”

Sixth, methodological support. Cases should be accompanied by commentary for facilitators, including identification of typical errors that participants might make (“traps”), provocative questions to deepen discussion, and multiple possible solutions with their respective justifications.

Seventh, consideration of the audience’s level. Cases should be differentiated according to the experience and training of the participants. Beginning teachers may benefit from more structured cases with clear signposts, while experienced educators can handle unstructured cases requiring independent research and more complex reasoning.

To illustrate the application of these principles, two brief case examples are provided below.

Case No. 1: “Conflict with a Parent”

Background: A young teacher, Ekaterina, in her second year of teaching, discusses the academic performance and behavioral challenges of a student, Artyom, during a routine parent-teacher meeting. She speaks in general terms but notes that Artyom consistently fails to complete homework and disrupts the class. The following day, Artyom’s mother arrives at the school accompanied by a lawyer. She demands to review all of Artyom’s written work, the gradebook, and requests a written explanation from the teacher regarding what she terms “psychological harassment” of her child. The school principal advises Ekaterina to “handle it herself.”

Task: Participants are asked to evaluate the legality of the actions taken by each party—the teacher, the parent, and the principal. They must then develop a step-by-step behavioral algorithm for Ekaterina: how should she respond to the mother’s initial confrontation? What should she say when faced with the lawyer? What documentation, if any, must she provide? Finally, participants propose strategies for preventing such situations in the future.

Case No. 2: “Bullying in the Classroom”

Background: In a seventh-grade class, a group of students led by a popular classmate has been systematically bullying a quieter student, Ilya. The bullying takes multiple forms: verbal insults in social media, damage to personal belongings, physical intimidation in hallways, and social exclusion. The class teacher, an experienced educator of fifteen years, has tried various interventions: individual conversations with the bullies, meetings with parents (the leader’s father is a local official), consultations with the school psychologist, and discussion at pedagogical council meetings. None have been effective. Ilya’s parents have now threatened to contact the prosecutor’s office and the media unless immediate action is taken. The principal, concerned about the political connections of the bully’s family, urges the class teacher to “resolve things quietly without washing dirty linen in public.”

Task: Participants must first analyze the legal status of each party and identify which laws and regulations apply (the Convention on the Rights of the Child, Federal Law No. 273 “On Education,” the Code of Administrative Offenses, etc.). They then develop a comprehensive action plan comprising: legal measures (documentation, official notifications, engagement of external agencies), psycho-pedagogical measures (support for the victim, work with the bullies and their families, classroom climate interventions), and measures for protecting the teacher from potential accusations of inaction. Finally, participants prepare talking points for three critical conversations: with Ilya’s parents, with the family of the bully, and with the school principal.

Summing up, the application of the case method offers educators three interconnected benefits that together contribute to the development of genuine legal competence.

First, it allows teachers to immerse themselves in the context of real professional activity. Unlike passive lectures or abstract reading, case analysis places educators in the midst of authentic challenges, engaging both their intellect and their professional judgment. This experiential dimension is essential for internalizing legal principles.

Second, it enables them to practice algorithms for action in both typical and atypical situations. Through repeated engagement with varied cases, teachers internalize not just isolated facts but structured approaches to legal problems—approaches they can later draw upon when similar situations arise in their own practice.

Third, and most fundamentally, the case method helps bridge the gap between theory and the practice of applying legal norms. Legal knowledge acquired in isolation often remains inert; it is only through the process of application to concrete situations that such knowledge becomes truly operational. The case method provides a safe, reflective space in which to practice this application before facing the high-stakes reality of a genuine legal conflict.

In conclusion, as investment in teacher professional development continues to grow, the case method deserves recognition as a particularly effective tool for cultivating the legal competence that modern educators increasingly require. The creation of a comprehensive bank of legal cases drawn from authentic school practice, supported by digital tools for collaborative analysis, represents a promising direction for future development.

A promising direction for the development of this topic is the creation of a bank of legal cases based on real situations from the practice of educational institutions, as well as the development of digital tools for collective work with cases in a distance learning format.

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**OSSETIAN-DAGESTANI HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL
RELATIONS. AN ETHNOLOGICAL OVERVIEW BY
PROFESSOR L. A. CHIBIROV**

Tsallagova Zarifa Borisovna

*Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor; Leading Researcher
Institute of Anthropology and Ethnology of the Russian Academy of
Sciences*

Annotation. *This article examines the views of renowned Russian ethnologist Professor Ludwig Alekseevich Chibirov on the history of Ossetian-Dagestani historical and cultural relations. It outlines the scholar's approaches to examining the problem from a historical perspective, from ancient times to the present, and presents his materials demonstrating the intensive contemporary cooperation between the two regions in various spheres of life.*

Keywords: *Ossetia, Dagestan, historical and cultural heritage, interethnic contacts, good-neighborly relations.*

Professor L. A. Chibirov is a recognized authority in humanitarian Ossetian studies. He is an ethnologist, Nart scholar, historian of science, and educator, whose high prestige is reinforced by his public mandates and his role as the first President of the Republic of South Ossetia. His fundamental research (3–6) is widely known and frequently cited not only among ethnographic specialists. The scholar's scientific works, produced at the highest level, are of interest not only to researchers but also introduce all interested readers to the world of their native culture, serving as a distinctive ethnocultural guide and a stimulus for sustained reflection on the phenomena described and the various interpretations thereof by the widest possible readership. The scholar's focus includes not only ethnology and ethnic history, the history of state formation in Ossetia, and Nart studies, but also the history and current state of interethnic relations between the Ossetians and neighboring peoples.

The stated problem is touched upon to varying degrees in many works by L. A. Chibirov and is often motivated by the goal of considering the broadest context of the issues he investigates. However, it is specifically the Ossetian-Dagestani relations to which he dedicated a monograph, the materials of which he collected over many years. Published by L. A. Chibirov in 2025, the book 'Alania-Ossetia and

Dagestan. Historical and Cultural Past and Present' (2) is the first to examine the problem of Ossetian-Dagestani cultural-historical relations in a monographic format.

This book 'illuminates' a blank spot in one of the numerous interethnic contacts of the Ossetians: the study of Ossetian-Dagestani historical-cultural relations, which, according to the author himself, significantly lags behind the level of research on Ossetian relations with the peoples of the Karachay-Balkar, Abkhaz-Adyghe, and Vainakh groups. Various nuances of interaction between the Ossetians and these peoples of the Caucasus are documented by the relevant extensive bibliographical source base presented in the book.

Returning to the theme of the monographic study by L. A. Chibirov, it should be noted that the theme he outlined is revealed in a broad diachronic aspect, covering the period from the earliest evidence and events to the present day. The publication incorporates rich factual material (including illustrative content, among which are numerous photographs from his personal archive), which apparently was accumulated over a lengthy period. The synthesis of L. A. Chibirov's own research together with the analysis of the currently available scientific literature on this issue has enabled the author to convincingly address the task of reconstructing the overall picture of relations between the two friendly peoples.

The author himself, indicating the relevance of the large-scale research he has undertaken, partly explains his motivation by appealing to the thesis of Vasily Ivanovich Abaev, who repeatedly recommended Ossetian researchers studying the past of the Ossetian people not to limit it to the territory of modern Ossetia but to direct their attention to the entire central North Caucasus, occupied by Alania from the borders with Dagestan to Abkhazia during the period of the Alan kingdom's flourishing. In building the methodological foundation of his work, L. A. Chibirov also draws on the research of another eminent scholar — ethnologist and Caucasus specialist A. N. Genko, who emphasized that the territory historically inhabited by the Ossetians was vastly larger (1).

As an experienced scholar who has long contemplated the subject, L. A. Chibirov, recognizing the impossibility of comprehensively addressing the issue within a single monograph, outlines research directions whose further development will enable his students and future generations of researchers to do so, thereby assisting younger scholars in defining the focus of their studies.

In particular, in the section 'Ossetian-Dagestani Epic Parallels' of the third chapter of the book, when discussing the extent of dissemination of epic tales among the peoples of Dagestan and outlining his rationale for approaching this issue, the author provides a detailed plan-prospect for the development of this theme. In the same section, he provides a list of key sources for studying the question, citing the works of A. M. Adzhiev, B. K. Dalgat, V. F. Minorsky, P. K. Uslar, A. M. Ganieva, M. R. Khalidova, K. Yu. Rakhno, and others. Acknowledging the well-founded

viewpoint of researcher U. B. Dalgat on this matter, the author refers not only to her published works but also highlights that in the SOIGSI VNC RAN scientific archive, within the 'Folklore' collection, there is a manuscript by Uzdyat Bashirovna, prepared as a report for the Nart studies conference in 1956. Familiarity with this manuscript enabled L. A. Chibirov to observe that the researcher's remarks regarding the main plots and particularities of the Nart tales of the region confirm P. K. Uslar's views on the extent of the spread of Nart tales in this area, leading to the conclusion that Dagestan represents a periphery in the dissemination of Nart tales: '...here they are practically no longer found.' In their place, there are Nart tales in which epic plots typical of the Ossetian Nart epic have been preserved" (Chibirov, 2025, p. 91).

The following section of the third chapter, titled 'Epic-Folklore Parallels,' not only provides comprehensive knowledge regarding the history and current state of research on this scientific issue but also reveals a deep understanding of various genres of Dagestani folklore (the author presents their plots, motifs, images, and names as comparative parallels to those found in the respective Ossetian oral-poetic works). In support of his scientific postulates, L. A. Chibirov also refers to the popular worldview attitudes and phraseological expressions of the two peoples, emphasizing the deeply rooted positive image of the Narts in the everyday life and ethnic consciousness of both groups. The Ossetian ideal of the perfect personality, as the author clearly demonstrates with examples, closely corresponds to the image of the epic Nart: 'The highest praise for an Ossetian is to call him a "Nart," and his abundant table a "Nart feast."' When praising a young man, they called him a 'true Nart' (2, p.117). A number of examples from the folklore and ethnocultural traditions of the peoples of Dagestan, which the scholar presents, convincingly support the discussion on the exceptional status of the epithet-definition 'Nart,' and the perception of the concept 'Nart' as a standard, as an exemplar.

To reinforce the argumentation of his claims, L. A. Chibirov refers throughout the book to the scientific heritage of his Dagestani colleagues (the bibliographic list of referenced works is impressive in its breadth), offering creative portraits and an enumeration of their achievements in the relevant sections (Literary Meridians, On the Scientific Path, In Military Service, Stage Without Borders, At the Origins of Cinematography, among others) in the sixth chapter of the book.

As an example, I will mention the Caucasian folklorist repeatedly referenced by the author, Uzdiat Bashirovna Dalgat, daughter of the well-known Dargin cultural figure Bashir Kerimovich Dalgat; reference material about her is provided in the section 'On the Scientific Path.' To the merits noted by L. A. Chibirov, I would add that U. B. Dalgat is not only a native of Vladikavkaz and a prominent folklorist-Caucasologist specializing in the Nart epic of the peoples of the Caucasus, but she also serves as the responsible editor of the three-volume academic edition 'Narts.'

Ossetian Heroic Epic” (Moscow: Nauka, 1989, 1990, 1991). She also contributed to Ossetian folkloristics as the academic advisor to a number of graduate and doctoral students from Ossetia, who studied in the postgraduate program at the Institute of World Literature of the Russian Academy of Sciences and successfully defended their dissertations there (Khanaeva Z. K., Dedegkaev Dzh.M., Dzhanaeva N. A., Tsallagova Z. B., Sokaev D. V., et al.). I believe that several other events, facts, and key figures of interethnic interaction noted by the author can be more fully explored in journalistic works and become topics for term papers, theses, and dissertations by young researchers, as a further development of this subject.

In light of this work, many well-known names in Ossetia and Dagestan have come to the fore. Some of them are inscribed on memorial plaques of houses in Vladikavkaz, while others are authors of works in artistic culture and regional history. Yet it is precisely in this publication that they stand as fundamental bonds of friendship and cooperation between the two peoples. And what is even more important, given the ever-relevant issue of interethnic contacts: the account of episodes of good-neighborly cooperation between the Ossetians and the peoples of Dagestan serves as a vivid demonstration of the productivity inherent in the example of friendship, respect, and mutual assistance among neighboring peoples. In the contemporary world, this serves as a vibrant slogan — a call for living in interethnic harmony, as well as a distinctive example and guideline for how nonviolent, neighborly cooperation can be established both in other regions and in different historical periods. Furthermore, how such peaceful and mutually respectful cooperation can be passed on to future generations. Expanding on the previous point, it is appropriate to note that this book should be included in the recommended reading list for relevant academic courses across various levels of the educational system. The author himself also rightly emphasizes not only the scientific but also the practical significance of the publication, which will contribute to strengthening and developing the traditions of friendly interaction between the two peoples in new circumstances.

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UNPACKING THE CULTURAL OTHER IN A GLOCAL EDUSCAPE: COMMUNICATING WITH DISSIMILAR OTHERS

Moshnyaga Elena Viktorovna

*Doctor of Sciences (Philosophy of Culture), Professor
National Research University "Higher School of Economics",
Moscow, Russia*

Hussain Irfan

*Master's degree student
National Research University "Higher School of Economics",
Moscow, Russia*

Abstract. *The paper focuses on case studies combined with participant observation and duoethnography as the core research methods. Duoethnographic analysis of a series of cross-cultural cases collected by us as co-authors from 2 different cultures (Russia and Pakistan) provides for a variety of culture-specific interpretations of intercultural misunderstanding, tensions and clashes observed by us in a multicultural class of a Russian university. Numerous real-life cases highlight some recurring problems of intercultural communication between culturally dissimilar Others in the educational space of a university promoting international programs worldwide and conceptualized as a glocal eduscape. Duoethnographic interpretation of the observed challenging situations in the cross-cultural cases, allows not only to identify discrepancies in the worldviews, beliefs and values of the participants, but also to propose some solutions based on the assumption that effective communication of all participants in the educational process requires unlocking and unpacking dissimilar cultural Others. From this perspective, cross-cultural cases can be used for constructing a typology of communication challenges and for modelling transcultural communication in future culture contacts in eduscapes.*

Keywords: *cultural Other, dissimilar Other, glocal eduscape, Stranger, Alien, cross-cultural case, duoethnography, intercultural communication*

In a drop of water there is an ocean!

We have chosen “*In a drop of water there is an ocean!*” for our epigraph since we are convinced that each of the cross-cultural cases (i.e. specific situations that took place in real time and in specific contexts where different cultures meet) we have collected, reveals the beliefs and values of a national and/or ethnic culture that enters into communication with a dissimilar cultural Other. Taken together, the cross-cultural cases reproduce a mosaic of cultures and a polyphony of multi-lingual voices (ideas, opinions, assumptions, and judgments) that are important to see and hear since they help to unlock and unpack culturally dissimilar Others as a phenomenon of international higher education worldwide.

International academic mobility involves residing of students, educators, researchers, and administrators from various cultures in a different cultural environment for a particular period of time, determined by their specific goals. Participants in international programs bring their multiple identities into a common communicative space. In this way, they create a new environment both for themselves and for other participants in intercultural interaction. This cross-cultural space (imagined cross-culture) lacks fixed and clear boundaries, stable configurations, and characteristics, since the composition of participants, as agents of change, is constantly changing.

The educational spaces of universities promoting international programs are now referred to as glocal “eduscapes” (Abdi and Naseem, 2008), following the ‘scape’ approach to the conceptualization and verbalization of global semiotic spaces proposed by the American anthropologist Arjun Appadurai (Appadurai, 1996) in the 1990s. An eduscape is understood as a space of exchange and continuous flow of ideas, activities, programs, and research pertaining to internationalization of the educational environment (Jung, 2017, p. 19). Every new culture, represented by its participants, entering an eduscape inevitably changes the nature of relationships within it, the level of expectations and attitudes, preferences and priorities, the degree of understanding and misunderstanding, acceptance and rejection, openness and closedness, harmony and conflict. Each new (previously unknown or little-known) culture poses a challenge to the other cultures involved in communication, and first and foremost, to the host culture.

As a result of the ever-changing trends of cultural globalization (for example, the emergence of “Global South” segment in Russian higher education) eduscapes are facing a changed demographics of participants that has a significant impact on their academic culture. In practical terms, this means that universities that host multicultural foreigners need to understand (unlock and unpack) a new glocalized image of the Other Student (in most cases, a dissimilar Other: the Stranger and the Alien). The “Stranger Other”, after a certain period of adaptation and mutual

desire and aspiration of the ingroup members and the Other to mentally and communicatively move towards each other, can feel like a member of the ingroup, understanding and accepting the culture of the hosts, acting in conformity with their expectations and value orientations, without experiencing any particular discomfort. The “Alien Other” with fundamentally different systems of beliefs and values will remain Alien (distant, strange, incomprehensible and misunderstood); communication with Alien Other causes mutual discomfort, uncertainty, fear and, as a result, avoidance of contact.

The distinction between the Other Alien and the Other Stranger is conditional and relative. Understanding these differences is linked, in particular, to cultural (ingroup) and individual orientations and attitudes that are formed as a result of established interaction practices and relevant experience. It is also impossible to deny the objectively persistent opposing tendencies of rejecting the Other (with hostility towards them) and appropriating the Other (without hostility and with the endowment of them with “one’s own” qualities). We also cannot deny the rather persistent opposing tendencies found in some cultures: the rejection of the Other (with a hostile attitude towards them) and the appropriation of the Other (without hostility and endowing them with qualities inherent in “one’s own” ingroup) (Shapinskaya, 2009 p.52).

The problems of alienation and rejection of the dissimilar Other (perceiving them as Stranger or Alien) are also associated with situations of closeness to culture and distance from it (Geertz, 2017), known as the emic approach or the view from within the cultural code and the etic approach or the view from outside the culture when interpreting communicative acts and events, as well as the beliefs and values underlying them.

At the core of any culture is a system of beliefs and values. Culture, being a mental matrix or a product of collective mental programming (according to Hofstede: “the Software of the Mind”) (Hofstede, 2010), is not amenable to reformatting (or, alternatively, it is a complex, painful, lengthy process, and only partially feasible), even in the context of migration as a way of life familiar to many today. As a result, many universities worldwide are discovering a new Other, frequently, culturally dissimilar Other: the student, graduate student, intern, professor, or researcher. First American and European universities, and now Russian ones too, are forced to respond to the challenges of this cultural and demographic globalization, or rather, glocalization, in which global trends are refracted locally and implemented in glocal products: educational programs that integrate global trends, national educational standards, and the educational expectations of students from different national and ethnic cultures.

Given the obvious heterogeneity and novelty of international student flows, university communities build communication with Others intuitively, stereotypically, without differentiating between them, often through trial and error. At the same time, international students at international universities bring not only their own educational goals and objectives, intentions and expectations, academic priorities

and preferences, forms and methods of instruction based on previous experience to the educational environment, but also spiritual and ethical behavioral patterns and communication styles that are alien (and foreign) to the host academic environment, reflecting, in particular, collectivist values through the prism of religious beliefs.

Cultural traits of students create obstacles, barriers, tensions and conflicts. In this regard, there is a need to adapt the content and forms of teaching many disciplines, modify joint scientific research and projects, and adjust communication patterns in a multicultural class.

As a subject of power relations and a source of educational guidance, teachers face at threat of reputational losses. Sometimes, teachers themselves can become a source of phobias for students. (They are seen as the Other too: Stranger or Alien.) This becomes especially evident when ideological and/or religious worldviews clash in a multicultural class.

In this study, we examine a series of cross-cultural cases: specific situations that reveal the problems of communication with a dissimilar Other. All cases took place in a multicultural class and in the conditions of an eduscape, therefore we refer to them as ‘cross-cultural’. The cases show that the cultural norms and behavioral orientations are based on beliefs and values. In our opinion, exploring and understanding, adequate interpretation and consideration of the beliefs and values of a dissimilar Other in the practice of intercultural interaction can increase the success of communication in the cross-culture of the glocal eduscape.

The case studies we collected demonstrate that beliefs and values underlie cultural norms and behavioral guidelines for cultural representatives. Understanding, interpreting, and using these beliefs in intercultural interactions helps ensure successful communication in a multicultural class.

Among the identified and categorized challenges of intercultural interaction in a multicultural class presented in our case studies, the following stand out:

- **Intercultural conflicts** that appeal to specific stages in the relationship between countries, certain (often tragic and traumatic) events, and collective historical memory. The conflicting parties have their own alternative history and culture-specific interpretation of the events. Meanwhile, such differences can be a knowledge gap for other students in class and for the teacher. Without recognizing the threat of intercultural conflict, a teacher, following a proven seminar plan, can provoke conflict on those topics and issues under discussion that previously, in groups with a different cultural composition, did not cause heated discussions and clashes of cultures. (See cases 1–2 below).

- **The religious worldview** of students from South-Asian (Muslim) countries. Islamic teachings conflict with the Christian beliefs, atheistic convictions, or agnosticism of non-Muslim students. For non-religious students and faculty members, religion is mythology. Theological postulates and dogmas, built on faith, conflict

with evidence-based science and secular theories. Beliefs, religious guidelines and orientations, as well as prayers and other rituals, influence the course of study, teaching and research methodology, secular procedures and practices. In Muslim countries accommodation of religious needs is common in universities and colleges. Prayer rooms are common and praying is part of regular campus life. Students hear the adhan (call for prayers) and have breaks in their schedule for prayers. Thus, religious life is closely intertwined with academic life. The secular university does not have prayer rooms, and the educational process does not include religious practices. In Russia, for example, prayer rituals are not prohibited, but may only be performed in designated buildings and historical premises, if any. Setting prayer rooms at a university involves addressing a number of complex legal, ethical, educational, organizational, and technical issues. There are currently no established procedures or proven practices for organizing prayer rooms at Russian universities. (See cases 3–6 below)

• **Silence as respect and avoidance of contact for face-saving** of students from East Asian cultures. In Asian cultures silence is an important communicative resource signaling respect, politeness and focused on face-saving and harmony. Asian cultures are reactive, i.e. they are listening cultures whose members are “programmed” to listen attentively and respectfully, rather than to speak explicitly and proactively. However, in the cross-cultural context of an eduscape, silence works against the student, as communication takes place within the formal regulations of academic culture. A student’s silence in class may be interpreted by the teacher (and by students from other cultures) as: “not ready,” “incapable,” “not interested,” “unwilling” to participate in classroom activities as all students enrolled in the program are familiar with the university’s academic rules and requirements. If classroom activity is one of elements for assessment, then silence would affect the final grade for the course. Saving face, as it is understood and practiced in Asian cultures, is not practiced when interacting with people from other countries. Russian teachers and students don’t understand why Chinese or Japanese students are reluctant to participate in class discussions and debates. They do not understand why students keep silent, avoid eye contact, and even skip classes. The common interpretation of their reticence is that “they’re simply shy.” Unwillingness and/or inability to adequately respond to “foreign” forms of expressing respect and politeness creates a persistent feeling of being out of one’s usual cognitive framework, existential uncertainty, and, to some extent, a sense of being lost. For a teacher in a cross-cultural context, this is a question of their insufficient intercultural competence (or cross-cultural intelligence). (See cases 7–10 below)

Here are a few cross-cultural cases from the practice of interacting with students in a multicultural Master’s class at the HSE School of Foreign Languages in 2023–2025 (Moscow, Russia):

1) Discussing symbolism within the framework of transcultural communication a student from Pakistan made an example of weapons found in all houses of Pashuns in Afghanistan as symbols of bravery, calling them brave warriors and protectors who decorate their houses with guns as a cultural symbol. The Pakistani student truly and admiringly meant it, calling Afghani people brave warriors and protectors, understanding cultural values and appreciating brotherhood of Pakistan-Afghani people but the students from Afghanistan interpreted it as expressed hostility, they were hurt. One of them addressed the lecturing professor: *"If you do not stop it, I will complain! I will address the academic supervisor and then the vice-rector! This is expressed hostility!"*

(2) During a seminar discussing the dimensions of national cultures, a question arose about the differences between the cultures of China and Taiwan. A Taiwanese student spoke of the values and advantages of his culture, emphasizing the country's democratic development and freedom. This provoked a critical response from a Chinese student: *"Taiwan is just a province of China! Taiwan is completely dependent on China, economically and technologically. Where would you be without us? Don't believe him; it's not like that at all!"*. The Taiwanese student remained silent in response.

(3) In a course on axiological linguistics, when the binarism of values Life and Death were discussed at a seminar, Russian students classified Life as a value ("the beginning of everything"), and Death as an anti-value ("the end of everything"). A student from Afghanistan rejected this perspective of evaluation: *"Death is a value for us because it is the beginning of a new and eternal life, the completion of earthly trials, liberation from suffering, pacification, but Life can be an anti-value if it is filled with unvirtuous deeds and the fall from grace."*

Other students in another group supported the idea of Death as a value and Life as anti-value: *"We lose our loved ones in Life! But we will get reunited with all of them after Life! Death will make us meet again!"*

(4) A student from Algeria, at the seminar on intercultural and cross-cultural communication, challenged the thesis that a person's cultural identity is the result of enculturation and socialization: *"No! I was born a Muslim! I agree that nature created us as biological beings, culture created us as individuals, but both nature and culture are created by God (Allah). Therefore, everything in us is from God!"*

(5) When discussing Martin Heidegger's concept of "Humans' Thrownness" (Geworfenheit des Menschen), which states that people are born without choosing their place and conditions of life, they have no power over circumstances, and are literally "thrown" into the world without expressing their will, a student from Pakistan categorically disagreed: *"God (Allah) determines where we live and what our mission here is!"*

(6) Students from Afghanistan and Pakistan approached the educational program academic adviser with a request: *"We need a prayer room at the university!"*. They explained that they experience inconvenience when performing prayers. They are forced to look for a place to pray, and the places they find are generally unsuitable for prayer (near the elevator, behind the stairwell, in an empty classroom). Prayer situations are morally and ethically hard to bear not only for Muslim students, but also for those around them (faculty members, administrators, non-Muslim students) in terms of behavior and communication.

(7) A student from Taiwan refused to speak at seminars and explained to her professor in a private conversation: *"When I hear my voice in a room with many other students, I feel like I could lose consciousness!"* *"If I realize that I'm wrong and answer publicly in a way that's not expected of me, I'm ready to die or disappear!"*

(8) A student from China, explaining her non-participation in a discussion at a seminar when professor suggested critically examining the proposed thesis, explained her silence (after the class): *"I cannot allow myself to argue with the professor! Professor is the Teacher! You don't argue with the Teacher!"*

(9) At the end of the program, the professor discovered that she had been mispronouncing a Taiwanese student's name throughout the course. *"Why didn't she ever correct me?"* the professor asked another Taiwanese student. *"Because you're a teacher!"* he replied.

(10) A student from Japan, while participating in project-based seminars, always chose a seat away from other students, always kept silent, and only asked the professor for clarification on assignments during breaks. After several seminars, she stopped attending classes and sent a letter to the professor explaining that she had missed the deadlines for the completed assignments and therefore could no longer come to class: *"You spent a lot of your precious time explaining to me how to complete the assignments, but I displayed disrespect, irresponsibility, incompetence, laziness, and unreliability!"*. A Taiwanese student shared a similar fear: *"If I don't complete an assignment on time, I'd rather not show up for class than lose face in public explaining why I didn't complete it!"*

The responsibility for resolving problems of intercultural misunderstanding in a multicultural class lies largely with the teacher as a facilitator of the educational process, a cultural broker, and a mediator of intercultural and cross-cultural communication. However, given the radically changed composition of the multicultural class, educators increasingly encounter communication situations in which they realize that they lack the intercultural competence to adequately and effectively resolve issues of cultural clashes. A new level of intercultural competence is becoming relevant, that is the formation of cross-cultural (or transcultural) intelligence as a personally and professionally significant quality of a teacher in a multicultural class. This is the ability and readiness for greater openness to

change and cultural diversity (to the emergence of a multifaceted and dissimilar Other in class: the Stranger and the Alien), cultural sensitivity, flexibility and adaptability in interpreting unusual and non-standard opinions, decisions and actions of students, and broad inclusiveness.

Some principles of intercultural pedagogy include the recognition of context and the “situated knowledges”. It is an approach discussed by Donna Haraway, who proposed abandoning the idea of the universality of knowledge and asserted that any knowledge is partial and is formed by the uniqueness of the subject in a specific historical, social and cultural context (Haraway, 2013). Some important principles also include the teacher’s awareness of variable ways of verifying truth; teaching based on conducted directed research in a specific multicultural class, and the widespread use of formative feedback (Hailu et al., 2017).

Involving international students themselves, as diverse and different Others, as consultants and teaching assistants allows for more successful resolution of problems of intercultural misunderstanding and conflictual behavior in a multicultural group. Students’ designing of case studies as models of behavior both in their own culture and in an imaginary cross-culture to reveal beliefs, value orientations, and behavioral norms helps all participants in the educational process develop their cross-cultural intelligence.

Thus, cross-cultural cases are valuable units of research, since they allow both to typify intercultural communication conflict situations and to model situations of communication with a dissimilar Other in educational spaces in further contacts between cultures. The pragmatics of a cross-cultural case analyzed and interpreted duoethnographically lies in diagnosing a current problem and modelling future perspectives.

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COMMON SENSE AND ORDINARY KNOWLEDGE AS THE BASIS FOR THE SAFETY OF LIFE

Chernyakova Natalia Stepanovna

Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, Professor

Herzen State Pedagogical University of Russia

Abstract. *The article argues that common sense and ordinary knowledge is the basic level of mental activity of people as socio-cultural subjects. The main socio-cultural function of common sense and ordinary knowledge is to be the basis for the safety of life, since they carry with them the fundamental features of mental activity as such: caution and prudence in relation to everything unknown; trust only in what has passed practical testing; reliance on personal and collective experience; reproduction of proven patterns of behavior in standard situations; analysis of available data and weighing all the pros and cons, if necessary to perform a new, unusual action.*

Keywords: *forms of knowledge, common sense, ordinary knowledge, mental activity, truth, delusion, safety of life.*

Common sense is the ability of a person to judge about surrounding phenomena on the basis of direct practical sensual contact with them. Common sense develops in the process of everyday existence of people as socio-cultural subjects and is the basic level of their mental activity and obtaining ordinary knowledge.

The idea that ordinary knowledge and common sense generate only misconceptions and illusions, which are overcome in the process of developing and spreading of scientific knowledge, has long been refuted by science itself. Research studies of the history of human society development have shown [1; 6], that, guided by common sense and carrying out everyday knowledge, people have learned already at the early stages of their development to adapt successfully to extremely diverse natural conditions and develop effective ways of interacting with each other [7; 8].

If the goal of cognition is to reproduce reality in ideal images of consciousness, then there is only one criterion for achieving this goal — substantive and practical interaction with the known reality. No other form of thinking has such a degree of reliability as common sense, the objects of which never go beyond the boundaries

of the actual life activity of a cultural subject. The truth of common sense' judgments finds direct practical verification not only in the experience of generations, but also in the individual experience of each person. It is only in everyday practical activity that a subject of cognition can directly compare the content of his judgments with objects: the drawing of the terrain — with the terrain itself, footprints on the ground — with the image of animals or people who could leave them, the radio receiver circuit — with the radio receiver itself, etc.

There is absolutely no reason to consider ordinary, non-scientific knowledge less plausible and practically significant than the results of scientific knowledge. On the contrary, if, for example, an indigenous inhabitant of a given area, based on the experience of his ancestors and his own observations, sets the dates of sowing and harvesting, determines the beneficial properties of plants or predicts weather events, then the degree of reliability of his statements, and therefore the degree of trust in them, will not be able to surpass the entire world science. No science talks about a single thing: about "this one" phenomenon, object, or process, although ordinary knowledge of this particular phenomenon: this area, this plant, or this animal, etc., is no less important to a person than scientific knowledge of the general, repetitive, and regular features of reality.

The knowledge of individual, specific aspects and properties of reality, acquired by a person in the process of everyday practice and common sense judgments of the world, will always be fundamentally different from scientific knowledge in that it has neither universal significance (because it is knowledge about what can be known or not known to everyone) or intersubjectivity (because there are no universal means for expressing, preserving, and transmitting it), no the ability to penetrate into the laws of reality phenomena (since for this it is necessary to go beyond the limits of the singular).

Yet, some set of ideas about the world necessarily underlies any kind of human activity, and this set of ideas can never be completely false, precisely because of the practical nature of human activity: someone who had an absolutely erroneous opinion about how to make fire or heal wounds died many thousands of years ago; someone who has an absolutely erroneous idea about mushrooms or drugs today is doomed to perish if he/she acts on the basis of her/his false ideas.

A true thought, a true image, is one that gives us the opportunity to act in the world around us in accordance with our goals. The very possibility of achieving these goals indicates that our ideas reproduce (represent, reflect) in some way the object (phenomenon, process, etc.) that they replace in our consciousness. This means, that people can regularly achieve their goals only because they are guided by true ideas about reality.

So, it is safe to say, that if some set of ideas, acting as the basis for motivating human activity, actually led to the achievement of the set goal, then this happened

only and exclusively because this set of ideas is not absolutely false and that, adhering to these ideas, people have never been completely mistaken.

However, the principle of the practical criterion of cognition does not eliminate the fundamental contradiction between reality and thinking about reality. Despite the fact that it is through practice that the cognizing subject is connected with the object of cognition, the truth assessment of the results of cognition based on their correspondence to a specific type and level of development of practice, ordinary or scientific-experimental, cannot be considered as absolute. This is due to the fact that the practice itself is relatively objective, and therefore generates both true and false ideas [2].

Delusion is something that, being realized as true and, therefore, as knowledge, is not it. At the moment of realizing one's delusion, a person stops deluding himself, but until that moment, no one knows the content of their delusions, because it is impossible to evaluate a statement as true and at the same time realize that one is mistaken! Therefore, arguments about the "cognitive functions" or "practical benefits" of misconceptions should not be taken literally. Delusions have no functions in cognition, since no one ever relies on delusions in their cognitive activity. The delusion is not recognized as an actual delusion of the subject of cognition himself. The error is known only in retrospect or from the outside [3].

Thus, at any given moment in time, the subject of cognition knows something about the world, but does not know with absolute certainty whether his knowledge is knowledge but not delusion. That is why we are always mistaken, but we never know at the moment which of our images are delusions.

Yet, any misconceptions prevail in the public and individual consciousness only because they do not directly threaten human life. Moreover, it would not be an exaggeration to say that it is precisely "safe misconceptions" that give so much diversity to the cultural and historical development of mankind. After all, to make a mistake in mine clearing an area, eating poisonous mushrooms or touching a bare high-voltage electrical wire with naked hands one can only once. But nothing threatens the life and health of those who use the term "culture" to designate art or believes that "value" is something that has some equivalent in hard currency. And to be mistaken about the origin of life on the Earth or the structure of the Universe people can be throughout the entire existence of mankind.

Thus, whatever the delusions of ordinary consciousness were generated by the limitations of common sense, if these delusions continue to exist, it means that none of them threatens human life. Dangerous misconceptions cannot linger in the ordinary consciousness. Their eradication is paid for by the death of those who was their native speaker, and whose example is fixed by common sense as prohibited for reproduction.

Common sense and ordinary knowledge perform their life-preserving functions due to the rigid connection with a certain natural and socio-cultural environment in

which they were formed. Being in direct practical contact with reality, people feel themselves within the limits of the already well-known, unquestionable world [4; 5].

At the same time, common sense and ordinary knowledge carry with them the fundamental features of mental activity as such: caution and prudence in relation to everything unknown; trust only in what has passed practical testing; reliance on personal and collective experience; reproduction of proven patterns of behavior in standard situations; analysis of available data and weighing all the pros and cons, if necessary to perform a new, unusual action.

So, no matter of how high the level of scientific knowledge would be, the main socio-cultural function of common sense and ordinary knowledge continues to be the function of basis for the safety of life as it has been for thousands of years.

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